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In [1]: # use python 3.6 or 3.7 environment
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Experiment MM25913 Data in: /dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2 /dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2

```
import getpass, pprint
from datacat import datacat_visit_info
dcat = datacat_visit_info.DataCatalogueVisitInfo('spc93',
getpass.getpass())
pprint.pprint(dcat.get_visit_info('MM25913-1'))
```

{'endDate': '2020-04-11 09:00:00+01:00', 'proposal': 'MM25913', 'startDate': '2020-04-09 09:00:00+01:00', 'summary': 'We have recently observed a feature in the Gd L1 XAS spectrum of gallium gadolinium garnet that we believe, on the basis of energy and anisotropy, and theoretical modelling, to be the first example of electric octupole resonance in x-ray spectroscopy. Specifically, the peak is believed to arise from interference between dipole and octupole events, driven by hybridization between the highly localized 4f and delocalized 6p orbitals. This is thought to be indicative of bonding between 4f states and neighbouring oxygen ligands. While evidence for this interpretation appear sound, several aspects of the work are novel and observation of the same spectral feature by an alternative technique would be extremely valuable. We proposal to carry out such a study using resonant forbidden x-ray diffraction. A positive result would represent the first observation of octupole resonant x-ray scattering., 'title': 'Electric Octapole resonant forbidden diffraction as a possible new probe of 4f hybridization', 'visitId': 'MM25913-1'} lattice = [12.3829, 12.3829, 12.3829, 90.0, 90.0, 90.0] gd_l1, gd_l2, gd_l3 = 8.376, 7.930, 7.243 allowed: 004, 220, 321, 420, ... forbidden: 002, 006, 220, ... 002 psi max = 45 (4-fold, arief = [1,0,0]) # 002, 006 forbidden Gd reflections 200: E1E1, E2E2 222: tensor allowed but all zero intensity E1E1 K=2 tensor zero E1E2 K=3 tensor not zero; intensity zero E2E2 K=4 tensor zero 022: A 122: X 222: T (0) 322: X 422: A 522: X 123: A Issues Pilatus small window missaligned and shadowing at edge IC1 ~220 on 14/7 ~ 1000 on 15/7 - helium leak? Beamline log 14/7/2020 GV1 was closed on interlock - pressure ok - reset & open cm26473-2 ic1 out of range during energy cal - flush helium - 1068 check pin on camera - moved but moved back after flush - no change ptl3cal - ok go8kev - ok - ic1 220 alignpinh - 23.2 - 22.5 mm repeat - same alignpinv - ok aligns5 - all ok except s5ytrans - -0.075 - 0; re-check - ok diode 2774 (8keV Rh) scan energy with Rh and Si (310, 311); use Si pil3 gain 1 found 004 @ 8 keV lattice almost perfect - use calc tth check harmonics (see plots) - very low look for 022 - ok phi ~43 look for 123 - ok azihkl = [1, 0, 0] 28/7/20 - official beam time (MM25913-2) test scan - 828091 - metadata back in .dat file mono bragg problem ... 30/07/20 Mono back after being tweaked by Brian Nutter ptl3cal() - #828131 energy shift 0.1 eV 31/7/20 power outage - network and LN problem. Very little data collected 4/8/20 - try again following last week's mono problems 4/8/20 - mono fault again. fixed in evening. script night04aug2020a.py started (potentially script for whole experiment)

```
In [2]: import sys
sys.path.append('/dls_sw/apps/scisoftpy/2.7')
sys.path.append('/dls_sw/i16/software/python')
from dlstools import *
from dlstools.pdinx import *
from matplotlib.pyplot import *

from dlstools.quickfit import *
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

#%matplotlib inline
%matplotlib notebook
#%matplotlib nbagg

p = '/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2/%i.nxs'
```

=== Importing dlstools package

```
In [3]: pd.set_option('display.max_rows', 9999)
def showscans(scans, metadata = []):
    # md is metadata list e.g. ['entry1/sample/name']
    _scanlist = []
    for scan in scans:
        _n = pdinx(p % scan)
        dic = {}
        dic['scan'] = scan
        dic['length'] = len(_n)
```

```

dic['command'] = _n.nx.entry1.scan_command
dic['start_time'] = _n.nx.entry1.start_time
for meta in metadata:
    dic[meta.split('/')[-1]] = _n.nx[meta]

_scanlist += [dic]

return pd.DataFrame(_scanlist)

```

```

In [4]: n = pdnx(p % 823290) # energy calibration (0.2 eV change but previous was noisy)
n.plot('DCMenergy', 'ic1')

```

Out[4]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x7f2b9a5e6390>


```

In [5]: n = pdnx(p % 823310) # Rh coating
figure()
plot(n.DCMenergy, n.diode)
n = pdnx(p % 823311) # Si coating
plot(n.DCMenergy, n.diode)

```

Out[5]: [<matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f2b99ce34a8>]


```

In [6]: n = pdnx(p % 823317) # atten 200 7.5e-9
figure()
plot(n.eta, n['sum']); title('hk1 = 004')
n = pdnx(p % 823311) # atten 170 7.6e-8

```



```
In [7]: n = pdnx(p % 823324) # atten 170 7.6e-8
n.plt('eta', 'sum'); title('hkl = 022')
```

```
Out[7]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'hkl = 022')
```



```
In [8]: n = pdnx(p % 823329) # L1
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
n.plot('DCMenergy', 'sum')
figure()
plot(n['DCMenergy'], n['i_norm'])
n = pdnx(p % 823330) # L1
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
plot(n['DCMenergy'], n['i_norm']); grid(1)

n = pdnx(p % 823332) # L2
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
n.plt('DCMenergy', 'i_norm')

n = pdnx(p % 823333) # L3
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
n.plt('DCMenergy', 'i_norm')
```


In [9]:

```

n = pdnx(p % 823335) # L1 E=8.39 keV
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
figure()
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum)
n = pdnx(p % 823340) # L1 E=7.935 keV nominal [004] atten 50
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum); grid(1)
title(n.nx.entry1.title + ' L1')

n = pdnx(p % 823336) # L2 E=7.935 keV
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
figure()
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum)
n = pdnx(p % 823339) # L2 E=7.935 keV nominal [004] atten 50
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum); grid(1)
title(n.nx.entry1.title + ' L2')

n = pdnx(p % 823337) # L3 E=7.248 keV
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
figure()
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum)
n = pdnx(p % 823338) # L3 E=7.248 keV nominal [004] atten 50
n['norm_sum'] = n['sum']/max(n['sum'])
plot(n.pil3_tresh, n.norm_sum); grid(1)
title(n.nx.entry1.title + ' L3')

```

Out[9]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'scan pil3_tresh 5 9 0.1 pil3_100k 1 L3')


```
In [10]: showscans(range(823364, 823483+1))
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```
Out[10]:
```

	command	length	scan	start_time
0	scan eta 20.931272102811946 21.13127210281195 ...	41	823364	2020-07-14T17:12:05.478+01:00
1	scan chi 89.35441462626818 90.35441462626818 0...	21	823365	2020-07-14T17:13:42.129+01:00
2	scan eta 21.02127210281294 21.041272102812943 ...	21	823366	2020-07-14T17:14:32.142+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
3	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823367	2020-07-14T17:15:15.65+01:00
4	scan eta 22.18501356543095 22.385013565430953 ...	41	823368	2020-07-14T17:24:48.077+01:00
5	scan chi 89.35441462626818 90.35441462626818 0...	21	823369	2020-07-14T17:26:24.089+01:00
6	scan eta 22.27001356543195 22.290013565431952 ...	21	823370	2020-07-14T17:27:13.899+01:00
7	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823371	2020-07-14T17:27:58.342+01:00
8	scan eta 24.438620193379947 24.63862019337995 ...	41	823372	2020-07-14T17:37:36.496+01:00
9	scan chi 89.35441462626818 90.35441462626818 0...	21	823373	2020-07-14T17:39:13.735+01:00
10	scan eta 24.523620193380946 24.54362019338095 ...	21	823374	2020-07-14T17:40:28.598+01:00
11	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823375	2020-07-14T17:41:12.422+01:00
12	scan eta 20.933808870272273 21.133808870272276...	41	823376	2020-07-14T17:50:50.698+01:00
13	scan chi 89.35490120387247 90.35490120387247 0...	21	823377	2020-07-14T17:52:24.577+01:00
14	scan eta 21.018808870272277 21.03880887027228 ...	21	823378	2020-07-14T17:53:14.75+01:00
15	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823379	2020-07-14T17:53:57.883+01:00
16	scan eta 22.187550332891277 22.38755033289128 ...	41	823380	2020-07-14T18:03:31.845+01:00
17	scan chi 89.35490120387247 90.35490120387247 0...	21	823381	2020-07-14T18:05:10.844+01:00
18	scan eta 22.27255033289128 22.292550332891285 ...	21	823382	2020-07-14T18:06:00.797+01:00
19	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823383	2020-07-14T18:06:44.572+01:00
20	scan eta 24.44115696084127 24.641156960841272 ...	41	823384	2020-07-14T18:16:23.293+01:00
21	scan chi 89.35490120387247 90.35490120387247 0...	21	823385	2020-07-14T18:17:57.087+01:00
22	scan eta 24.521156960841278 24.54115696084128 ...	21	823386	2020-07-14T18:18:47.09+01:00
23	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823387	2020-07-14T18:19:31.053+01:00
24	scan eta 20.93633675930704 21.136336759307042 ...	41	823388	2020-07-14T18:29:19.074+01:00
25	scan chi 89.35543198005905 90.35543198005905 0...	21	823389	2020-07-14T18:31:15.716+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
26	scan eta 21.01633675930705 21.03633675930705 0...	21	823390	2020-07- 14T18:32:05.796+01:00
27	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823391	2020-07- 14T18:32:49.215+01:00
28	scan eta 22.19007822192704 22.39007822192704 0...	41	823392	2020-07- 14T18:42:14.958+01:00
29	scan chi 89.35543198005905 90.35543198005905 0...	21	823393	2020-07- 14T18:43:54.422+01:00
30	scan eta 22.270078221927047 22.29007822192705 ...	21	823394	2020-07- 14T18:44:44.869+01:00
31	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823395	2020-07- 14T18:45:29.234+01:00
32	scan eta 24.44368484987605 24.643684849876053 ...	41	823396	2020-07- 14T18:55:07.157+01:00
33	scan chi 89.35543198005905 90.35543198005905 0...	21	823397	2020-07- 14T18:56:47.436+01:00
34	scan eta 24.51868484987605 24.538684849876052 ...	21	823398	2020-07- 14T18:57:37.385+01:00
35	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823399	2020-07- 14T18:58:21.362+01:00
36	scan eta 20.938854999890275 21.138854999890277...	41	823400	2020-07- 14T19:07:56.184+01:00
37	scan chi 89.35600679314452 90.35600679314452 0...	21	823401	2020-07- 14T19:09:30.234+01:00
38	scan eta 21.013854999890274 21.033854999890277...	21	823402	2020-07- 14T19:10:48.525+01:00
39	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823403	2020-07- 14T19:11:30.578+01:00
40	scan eta 22.192596462509265 22.392596462509267...	41	823404	2020-07- 14T19:21:05.458+01:00
41	scan chi 89.35600679314452 90.35600679314452 0...	21	823405	2020-07- 14T19:22:41.441+01:00
42	scan eta 22.267596462509264 22.287596462509267...	21	823406	2020-07- 14T19:23:31.475+01:00
43	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823407	2020-07- 14T19:24:14.966+01:00
44	scan eta 24.44620309045927 24.646203090459274 ...	41	823408	2020-07- 14T19:33:50.583+01:00
45	scan chi 89.35600679314452 90.35600679314452 0...	21	823409	2020-07- 14T19:35:29.526+01:00
46	scan eta 24.516203090459275 24.536203090459278...	21	823410	2020-07- 14T19:36:19.467+01:00
47	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823411	2020-07- 14T19:37:03.447+01:00
48	scan eta 20.94136282493102 21.141362824931022 ...	41	823412	2020-07- 14T19:46:42.291+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
49	scan chi 89.35662546803253 90.35662546803253 0...	21	823413	2020-07- 14T19:48:13.865+01:00
50	scan eta 21.01136282493101 21.031362824931012 ...	21	823414	2020-07- 14T19:49:03.906+01:00
51	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823415	2020-07- 14T19:49:47.094+01:00
52	scan eta 22.19510428755102 22.39510428755102 0...	41	823416	2020-07- 14T19:59:18.692+01:00
53	scan chi 89.35662546803253 90.35662546803253 0...	21	823417	2020-07- 14T20:01:24.119+01:00
54	scan eta 22.265104287551022 22.285104287551025...	21	823418	2020-07- 14T20:02:14.307+01:00
55	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823419	2020-07- 14T20:02:58.293+01:00
56	scan eta 24.448710915500016 24.64871091550002 ...	41	823420	2020-07- 14T20:12:31.72+01:00
57	scan chi 89.35662546803253 90.35662546803253 0...	21	823421	2020-07- 14T20:14:10.641+01:00
58	scan eta 24.51371091550001 24.533710915500013 ...	21	823422	2020-07- 14T20:15:00.514+01:00
59	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823423	2020-07- 14T20:15:44.509+01:00
60	scan eta 20.94385947051549 21.143859470515494 ...	41	823424	2020-07- 14T20:25:29.179+01:00
61	scan chi 89.35728781626503 90.35728781626503 0...	21	823425	2020-07- 14T20:27:05.202+01:00
62	scan eta 21.008859470515485 21.02885947051549 ...	21	823426	2020-07- 14T20:27:55.085+01:00
63	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823427	2020-07- 14T20:28:38.944+01:00
64	scan eta 22.19760093313549 22.397600933135493 ...	41	823428	2020-07- 14T20:38:11.257+01:00
65	scan chi 89.35728781626503 90.35728781626503 0...	21	823429	2020-07- 14T20:39:48.464+01:00
66	scan eta 22.262600933135484 22.282600933135488...	21	823430	2020-07- 14T20:41:05.53+01:00
67	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823431	2020-07- 14T20:41:50.452+01:00
68	scan eta 24.451207561084487 24.65120756108449 ...	41	823432	2020-07- 14T20:51:17.556+01:00
69	scan chi 89.35728781626503 90.35728781626503 0...	21	823433	2020-07- 14T20:52:56.763+01:00
70	scan eta 24.511207561084316 24.53120756108432 ...	21	823434	2020-07- 14T20:53:47.296+01:00
71	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823435	2020-07- 14T20:54:31.479+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
72	scan eta 20.928727222965896 21.1287272229658963 ...	41	823436	2020-07-14T21:04:03.549+01:00
73	scan chi 89.35397239546506 90.35397239546506 0...	21	823437	2020-07-14T21:05:37.292+01:00
74	scan eta 21.023727222965796 21.0437272229657964 ...	21	823438	2020-07-14T21:06:27.406+01:00
75	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823439	2020-07-14T21:07:10.685+01:00
76	scan eta 22.18246869227896 22.382468692278962 ...	41	823440	2020-07-14T21:16:47.691+01:00
77	scan chi 89.35397239546506 90.35397239546506 0...	21	823441	2020-07-14T21:18:24.094+01:00
78	scan eta 22.27746869227796 22.297468692277963 ...	21	823442	2020-07-14T21:19:14.226+01:00
79	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823443	2020-07-14T21:20:24.337+01:00
80	scan eta 24.436075320227957 24.63607532022796 ...	41	823444	2020-07-14T21:29:28.924+01:00
81	scan chi 89.35397239546506 90.35397239546506 0...	21	823445	2020-07-14T21:31:34.816+01:00
82	scan eta 24.526075320226962 24.546075320226965...	21	823446	2020-07-14T21:32:25.309+01:00
83	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823447	2020-07-14T21:33:08.956+01:00
84	scan eta 20.92617502601705 21.12617502601705 0...	41	823448	2020-07-14T21:42:48.689+01:00
85	scan chi 89.35357464617321 90.35357464617321 0...	21	823449	2020-07-14T21:44:26.418+01:00
86	scan eta 21.026175026017054 21.046175026017057...	21	823450	2020-07-14T21:45:16.619+01:00
87	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823451	2020-07-14T21:46:00.051+01:00
88	scan eta 22.179916488636053 22.379916488636056...	41	823452	2020-07-14T21:55:34.291+01:00
89	scan chi 89.35357464617321 90.35357464617321 0...	21	823453	2020-07-14T21:57:14.032+01:00
90	scan eta 22.27491648863605 22.29491648863605 0...	21	823454	2020-07-14T21:58:04.69+01:00
91	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823455	2020-07-14T21:58:49.608+01:00
92	scan eta 24.43352311658606 24.633523116586062 ...	41	823456	2020-07-14T22:08:26.084+01:00
93	scan chi 89.35357464617321 90.35357464617321 0...	21	823457	2020-07-14T22:10:28.145+01:00
94	scan eta 24.533523116586398 24.5535231165864 0...	21	823458	2020-07-14T22:11:19.736+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
95	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823459	2020-07-14T22:12:03.435+01:00
96	scan eta 20.923616269320434 21.123616269320436...	41	823460	2020-07-14T22:21:45.423+01:00
97	scan chi 89.35322149955316 90.35322149955316 0...	21	823461	2020-07-14T22:23:27.238+01:00
98	scan eta 21.023616269320424 21.043616269320427...	21	823462	2020-07-14T22:24:18.946+01:00
99	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823463	2020-07-14T22:25:02.867+01:00
100	scan eta 22.177357731939424 22.377357731939426...	41	823464	2020-07-14T22:34:52.737+01:00
101	scan chi 89.35322149955316 90.35322149955316 0...	21	823465	2020-07-14T22:36:27.113+01:00
102	scan eta 22.27735773193943 22.29735773193943 0...	21	823466	2020-07-14T22:37:18.705+01:00
103	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823467	2020-07-14T22:38:04.124+01:00
104	scan eta 24.43096435988943 24.630964359889433 ...	41	823468	2020-07-14T22:47:38.115+01:00
105	scan chi 89.35322149955316 90.35322149955316 0...	21	823469	2020-07-14T22:49:21.491+01:00
106	scan eta 24.530964359889435 24.550964359889438...	21	823470	2020-07-14T22:50:40.905+01:00
107	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823471	2020-07-14T22:51:24.657+01:00
108	scan eta 20.91848221624918 21.118482216249184 ...	41	823472	2020-07-14T23:00:58.694+01:00
109	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823473	2020-07-14T23:02:40.649+01:00
110	scan eta 21.028482216250172 21.048482216250175...	21	823474	2020-07-14T23:03:31.871+01:00
111	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823475	2020-07-14T23:04:16.442+01:00
112	scan eta 22.17222367886918 22.372223678869183 ...	41	823476	2020-07-14T23:14:10.349+01:00
113	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823477	2020-07-14T23:15:44.308+01:00
114	scan eta 22.28222367887017 22.302223678870174 ...	21	823478	2020-07-14T23:16:35.661+01:00
115	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823479	2020-07-14T23:17:21.359+01:00
116	scan eta 24.425830306818177 24.62583030681818 ...	41	823480	2020-07-14T23:26:52.397+01:00
117	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823481	2020-07-14T23:28:29.141+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
118	scan eta 24.535830306819182 24.555830306819185...	21	823482	2020-07- 14T23:29:20.148+01:00
119	scan energy 7.21 7.2700000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823483	2020-07- 14T23:30:29.281+01:00

```
# newub - ggg_july_2020 #pil3_thresh=SingleEpicsPositionerSetAndGetOnlyClass('pil3_tresh','BL16I-EA-PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','BL16I-EA-PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','keV', '%.2f', help='Pilatus3 100K threshold via Epics Jython class') #con gam 0 mu 0 phi phi() #con gam 0 mu 0 bisect #addref [0,0,4] '004specular' GdL1 = 8.376 GdL2 = 7.930 GdL3 = 7.243 #823329-30 then stopped #pos atten 0 #for ener in [GdL1, GdL2, GdL3]: # pos energy ener # scan energy ener-.05 ener+.15 .0005 pil3 1 # scan energy ener-.05 ener+.15 .0005 pil3 1 #continue with shorter scans #823333- #pos atten 0 #for ener in [GdL2, GdL3]: # pos energy ener # scan energy ener-.03 ener+.1 .001 pil3 1 #schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1; schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.)) edic = {'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh': 7.0}, 'l2': {'eres': 7.93, 'ethresh': 6.7}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.24, 'ethresh': 6.5}, } con gam 0 mu 0 psi 0 pos psic 45 # ENERGY H K L PHI CHI ETA MU DELTA GAM TAG # 1 8.000 0.00 0.00 4.00 0.0000 89.5000 14.3811 0.0000 28.9921 -0.0000 004specular # 2 8.000 0.00 2.00 2.00 41.9902 44.5128 10.4431 0.0000 20.3899 0.0000 022 # 3 8.380 0.00 0.00 6.00 177.7565 89.8542 21.0300 0.0000 42.0093 0.0000 006_L3_psi45 #calcutb 3 2 #823364 - 823483 #ended ok mostly multiple scattering but some L2,L3 resonance pos atten 0 for psival in [45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 44, 43, 42, 40]: pos psic psival for ed in edic: print(ed) pos pil3_thresh edic[ed]['ethresh'] ener = edic[ed]['eres'] pos energy ener pos hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 41 checkbeam pil3 1 lcroi scroi go maxval scancn chi .05 21 checkbeam pil3 1 schiroi go maxval scancn eta .001 21 checkbeam pil3 1 lcroi scroi go maxval hh = hkl() scan energy ener-.03 ener+.03 .0005 hkl hh checkbeam pil3 1 lcroi scroi
```

In [11]:

```
#alignment and energy scans, L1, L2, L3. Lots of multiple scattering!
```

```
en_l1_scans = range(823367, 823475+1, 12)
en_l2_scans = range(823371, 823479+1, 12)
en_l3_scans = range(823375, 823483+1, 12)
eta_fine_l1_scans = range(823366, 823474+1, 12)
eta_fine_l2_scans = range(823370, 823478+1, 12)
eta_fine_l3_scans = range(823374, 823482+1, 12)
eta_l1_scans = range(823364, 823472+1, 12)
eta_l2_scans = range(823368, 823476+1, 12)
eta_l3_scans = range(823372, 823480+1, 12)
chi_l1_scans = range(823365, 823473+1, 12)
chi_l2_scans = range(823369, 823477+1, 12)
chi_l3_scans = range(823373, 823481+1, 12)
```

```
figure()
for scan in chi_l1_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.chi, n.schiroi_sum)
    title('Gd L1')
ylim([0,1e7])
```

```
figure()
for scan in chi_l2_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.chi, n.schiroi_sum)
    title('Gd L2')
ylim([0,1e7])
```

```
figure()
for scan in chi_l3_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.chi, n.schiroi_sum)
    title('Gd L3')
ylim([0,1e7])
```

```
figure()
for scan in eta_l1_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L1')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in eta_l2_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L2')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in eta_l3_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L3')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in eta_fine_l1_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L1')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in eta_fine_l2_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L2')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in eta_fine_l3_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L3')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in en_l1_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.DCMenergy, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L1')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in en_l2_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.DCMenergy, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L2')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in en_l3_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.DCMenergy, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L3')
ylim([0,1e7])
```

Out[11]: (0, 10000000.0)


```
#schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1;
schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.)) #scroi_bg =
HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=13; jw=15;
scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.-16)) edic = { 'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh': 7.0},
'l2': {'eres': 7.93, 'ethresh': 6.7}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.24, 'ethresh': 6.5}, } #823484 - crashed 487 timeout after threshold
#823504 - 676 - ok but lots of m/s and falling off peak pos atten 0 for psival in range(20, 71, 2): pos psic psival
for ed in edic: print(ed) pos pil3_thresh edic[ed]['ethresh'] pos w 10 #wait for threshol ener = edic[ed]['eres'] pos
energy ener pos hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 61 checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi go maxval scancn chi .05 21
checkbeam pil3 .5 schiroi go maxval scancn eta .001 21 checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi go maxval hh = hkl() scancn
psic .05 81 hkl hh pil3 .5 lcroi scroi_bg scroi
```

```
In [12]: showscans(range(823504, 823640+1))
```

Out[12]:

	command	length	scan	start_time
0	scan eta 20.81725180660414 21.117251806604138 ...	61	823504	2020-07-15T10:42:40.881+01:00
1	scan chi 89.35680910427088 90.35680910427088 0...	21	823505	2020-07-15T10:44:25.587+01:00
2	scan eta 21.062251806604696 21.0822518066047 0...	21	823506	2020-07-15T10:45:05.473+01:00
3	scan psi 18.0 22.0 0.05 hkl [0.008640045276201...	81	823507	2020-07-15T10:45:40.298+01:00
4	scan eta 22.07099326922414 22.370993269224137 ...	61	823508	2020-07-15T10:48:12.628+01:00
5	scan chi 89.35680910427088 90.35680910427088 0...	21	823509	2020-07-15T10:49:44.969+01:00
6	scan eta 22.315993269224695 22.335993269224698...	21	823510	2020-07-15T10:50:49.095+01:00
7	scan psi 18.0 22.0 0.05 hkl [0.008344832514091...	81	823511	2020-07-15T10:51:24.256+01:00
8	scan eta 24.324599897173137 24.624599897173134...	61	823512	2020-07-15T10:53:58.56+01:00
9	scan chi 89.35680910427088 90.35680910427088 0...	21	823513	2020-07-15T10:55:28.887+01:00
10	scan eta 24.569599897174133 24.589599897174136...	21	823514	2020-07-15T10:56:08.518+01:00
11	scan psi 18.0 22.0 0.05 hkl [0.010135645797905...	81	823515	2020-07-15T10:56:42.814+01:00
12	scan eta 20.822271895896442 21.12227189589644 ...	61	823516	2020-07-15T10:59:19.368+01:00
13	scan chi 89.35559072340106 90.35559072340106 0...	21	823517	2020-07-15T11:01:23.223+01:00
14	scan eta 21.06227189589622 21.082271895896223 ...	21	823518	2020-07-15T11:02:03.916+01:00
15	scan psi 20.0 24.0 0.05 hkl [0.007456723484583...	81	823519	2020-07-15T11:02:39.205+01:00
16	scan eta 22.076013358516455 22.376013358516452...	61	823520	2020-07-15T11:05:15.558+01:00
17	scan chi 89.35559072340106 90.35559072340106 0...	21	823521	2020-07-15T11:06:49.548+01:00
18	scan eta 22.311013358516224 22.331013358516227...	21	823522	2020-07-15T11:07:32.224+01:00
19	scan psi 20.0 24.0 0.05 hkl [0.007456723484630...	81	823523	2020-07-15T11:08:08.658+01:00
20	scan eta 24.329619986465453 24.62961998646545 ...	61	823524	2020-07-15T11:11:14.434+01:00
21	scan chi 89.35559072340106 90.35559072340106 0...	21	823525	2020-07-15T11:12:50.23+01:00
22	scan eta 24.56461998646545 24.58461998646545 0...	21	823526	2020-07-15T11:13:32.799+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
23	scan psi 20.0 24.0 0.05 hkl [0.009223970062696...	81	823527	2020-07-15T11:14:07.554+01:00
24	scan eta 20.827331448460534 21.12733144846053 ...	61	823528	2020-07-15T11:16:49.028+01:00
25	scan chi 89.35454828330631 90.35454828330631 0...	21	823529	2020-07-15T11:18:24.376+01:00
26	scan eta 21.0573314484616 21.077331448461603 0...	21	823530	2020-07-15T11:19:07.184+01:00
27	scan psi 22.000000000000004 26.000000000000004...	81	823531	2020-07-15T11:19:42.258+01:00
28	scan eta 22.081072911079524 22.38107291107952 ...	61	823532	2020-07-15T11:22:43.171+01:00
29	scan chi 89.35454828330631 90.35454828330631 0...	21	823533	2020-07-15T11:24:14.988+01:00
30	scan eta 22.311072911080604 22.331072911080607...	21	823534	2020-07-15T11:24:55.024+01:00
31	scan psi 22.000000000000004 26.000000000000004...	81	823535	2020-07-15T11:25:30.124+01:00
32	scan eta 24.33467953902953 24.634679539029527 ...	61	823536	2020-07-15T11:28:11.296+01:00
33	scan chi 89.35454828330631 90.35454828330631 0...	21	823537	2020-07-15T11:29:42.372+01:00
34	scan eta 24.564679539030525 24.584679539030528...	21	823538	2020-07-15T11:30:48.025+01:00
35	scan psi 22.000000000000004 26.000000000000004...	81	823539	2020-07-15T11:31:22.714+01:00
36	scan eta 20.832424299941565 21.13242429994156 ...	61	823540	2020-07-15T11:34:01.611+01:00
37	scan chi 89.35368305406314 90.35368305406314 0...	21	823541	2020-07-15T11:35:31.655+01:00
38	scan eta 21.05742429994115 21.077424299941153 ...	21	823542	2020-07-15T11:36:11.211+01:00
39	scan psi 24.0 28.0 0.05 hkl [0.005516775967390...	81	823543	2020-07-15T11:36:46.545+01:00
40	scan eta 22.086165762561563 22.38616576256156 ...	61	823544	2020-07-15T11:39:25.049+01:00
41	scan chi 89.35368305406314 90.35368305406314 0...	21	823545	2020-07-15T11:41:22.799+01:00
42	scan eta 22.30616576256156 22.326165762561562 ...	21	823546	2020-07-15T11:42:02.182+01:00
43	scan psi 24.0 28.0 0.05 hkl [0.007435595546148...	81	823547	2020-07-15T11:42:38.193+01:00
44	scan eta 24.33977239051056 24.639772390510558 ...	61	823548	2020-07-15T11:45:16.76+01:00
45	scan chi 89.35368305406314 90.35368305406314 0...	21	823549	2020-07-15T11:46:46.36+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
46	scan eta 24.559772390510556 24.57977239051056 ...	21	823550	2020-07-15T11:47:25.661+01:00
47	scan psi 24.0 28.0 0.05 hkl [0.007529716947928...	81	823551	2020-07-15T11:48:00.409+01:00
48	scan eta 20.83754424541103 21.13754424541103 0...	61	823552	2020-07-15T11:51:08.689+01:00
49	scan chi 89.35299608984097 90.35299608984097 0...	21	823553	2020-07-15T11:52:43.537+01:00
50	scan eta 21.052544245410612 21.072544245410615...	21	823554	2020-07-15T11:53:23.501+01:00
51	scan psi 26.0 30.0 0.05 hkl [0.004384043786266...	81	823555	2020-07-15T11:53:59.258+01:00
52	scan eta 22.09128570803103 22.391285708031027 ...	61	823556	2020-07-15T11:56:38.406+01:00
53	scan chi 89.35299608984097 90.35299608984097 0...	21	823557	2020-07-15T11:58:09.833+01:00
54	scan eta 22.30628570803103 22.326285708031033 ...	21	823558	2020-07-15T11:58:49.117+01:00
55	scan psi 26.0 30.0 0.05 hkl [0.006564804275153...	81	823559	2020-07-15T11:59:24.611+01:00
56	scan eta 24.344892335980028 24.644892335980025...	61	823560	2020-07-15T12:02:31.496+01:00
57	scan chi 89.35299608984097 90.35299608984097 0...	21	823561	2020-07-15T12:04:02.009+01:00
58	scan eta 24.554892335980032 24.574892335980035...	21	823562	2020-07-15T12:04:41.265+01:00
59	scan psi 26.0 30.0 0.05 hkl [0.006657266258819...	81	823563	2020-07-15T12:05:16.601+01:00
60	scan eta 20.842685046927976 21.142685046927973...	61	823564	2020-07-15T12:08:01.44+01:00
61	scan chi 89.35248822761508 90.35248822761508 0...	21	823565	2020-07-15T12:09:30.389+01:00
62	scan eta 21.047685046928425 21.06768504692843 ...	21	823566	2020-07-15T12:10:35.908+01:00
63	scan psi 27.999999999999996 31.999999999999996...	81	823567	2020-07-15T12:11:11.648+01:00
64	scan eta 22.09642650954799 22.396426509547986 ...	61	823568	2020-07-15T12:13:53.079+01:00
65	scan chi 89.35248822761508 90.35248822761508 0...	21	823569	2020-07-15T12:15:28.002+01:00
66	scan eta 22.30142650954844 22.32142650954844 0...	21	823570	2020-07-15T12:16:08.22+01:00
67	scan psi 27.999999999999996 31.999999999999996...	81	823571	2020-07-15T12:16:44.152+01:00
68	scan eta 24.350033137496986 24.650033137496983...	61	823572	2020-07-15T12:19:27.879+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
69	scan chi 89.35248822761508 90.35248822761508 0...	21	823573	2020-07- 15T12:21:28.887+01:00
70	scan eta 24.55503313749698 24.575033137496984 ...	21	823574	2020-07- 15T12:22:08.281+01:00
71	scan psi 27.999999999999996 31.999999999999996...	81	823575	2020-07- 15T12:22:43.364+01:00
72	scan eta 20.847840441135894 21.14784044113589 ...	61	823576	2020-07- 15T12:25:26.923+01:00
73	scan chi 89.35216008615102 90.35216008615102 0...	21	823577	2020-07- 15T12:26:59.852+01:00
74	scan eta 21.042840441135883 21.062840441135886...	21	823578	2020-07- 15T12:27:39.211+01:00
75	scan psi 30.0 34.0 0.05 hkl [0.005062020335689...	81	823579	2020-07- 15T12:28:15.302+01:00
76	scan eta 22.101581903754884 22.40158190375488 ...	61	823580	2020-07- 15T12:31:20.25+01:00
77	scan chi 89.35216008615102 90.35216008615102 0...	21	823581	2020-07- 15T12:32:53.145+01:00
78	scan eta 22.296581903754888 22.31658190375489 ...	21	823582	2020-07- 15T12:33:32.411+01:00
79	scan psi 30.0 34.0 0.05 hkl [0.004973212989864...	81	823583	2020-07- 15T12:34:08.511+01:00
80	scan eta 24.35518853170489 24.655188531704887 ...	61	823584	2020-07- 15T12:36:45.16+01:00
81	scan chi 89.35216008615102 90.35216008615102 0...	21	823585	2020-07- 15T12:38:16.886+01:00
82	scan eta 24.55018853170488 24.570188531704883 ...	21	823586	2020-07- 15T12:38:56.626+01:00
83	scan psi 30.0 34.0 0.05 hkl [0.005062020335688...	81	823587	2020-07- 15T12:39:31.625+01:00
84	scan eta 20.853004146899757 21.153004146899754...	61	823588	2020-07- 15T12:42:37.758+01:00
85	scan chi 89.35201206524525 90.35201206524525 0...	21	823589	2020-07- 15T12:44:10.31+01:00
86	scan eta 21.043004146898756 21.06300414689876 ...	21	823590	2020-07- 15T12:44:49.789+01:00
87	scan psi 32.0 36.0 0.05 hkl [0.004167196868431...	81	823591	2020-07- 15T12:45:25.101+01:00
88	scan eta 22.106745609519756 22.406745609519753...	61	823592	2020-07- 15T12:48:07.28+01:00
89	scan chi 89.35201206524525 90.35201206524525 0...	21	823593	2020-07- 15T12:49:41.766+01:00
90	scan eta 22.29174560951876 22.311745609518763 ...	21	823594	2020-07- 15T12:50:48.636+01:00
91	scan psi 32.0 36.0 0.05 hkl [0.003906747119527...	81	823595	2020-07- 15T12:51:24.547+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
92	scan eta 24.360352237468767 24.660352237468764...	61	823596	2020-07- 15T12:54:02.18+01:00
93	scan chi 89.35201206524525 90.35201206524525 0...	21	823597	2020-07- 15T12:55:32.761+01:00
94	scan eta 24.545352237467757 24.56535223746776 ...	21	823598	2020-07- 15T12:56:12.161+01:00
95	scan psi 32.0 36.0 0.05 hkl [0.003906747119484...	81	823599	2020-07- 15T12:56:46.768+01:00
96	scan eta 20.858169872955912 21.15816987295591 ...	61	823600	2020-07- 15T12:59:29.078+01:00
97	scan chi 89.35204434524272 90.35204434524272 0...	21	823601	2020-07- 15T13:01:27.641+01:00
98	scan eta 21.0381698729559 21.058169872955904 0...	21	823602	2020-07- 15T13:02:06.953+01:00
99	scan psi 34.0 38.0 0.05 hkl [0.003304082144865...	81	823603	2020-07- 15T13:02:42.663+01:00
100	scan eta 22.11191133557591 22.41191133557591 0...	61	823604	2020-07- 15T13:05:25.54+01:00
101	scan chi 89.35204434524272 90.35204434524272 0...	21	823605	2020-07- 15T13:06:59.227+01:00
102	scan eta 22.286911335575905 22.306911335575908...	21	823606	2020-07- 15T13:07:39.06+01:00
103	scan psi 34.0 38.0 0.05 hkl [0.003134642059102...	81	823607	2020-07- 15T13:08:15.582+01:00
104	scan eta 24.36551796352491 24.665517963524906 ...	61	823608	2020-07- 15T13:11:24.057+01:00
105	scan chi 89.35204434524272 90.35204434524272 0...	21	823609	2020-07- 15T13:12:56.433+01:00
106	scan eta 24.540517963524902 24.560517963524905...	21	823610	2020-07- 15T13:13:35.776+01:00
107	scan psi 34.0 38.0 0.05 hkl [0.003049922014714...	81	823611	2020-07- 15T13:14:11.628+01:00
108	scan eta 20.863331325578457 21.163331325578454...	61	823612	2020-07- 15T13:16:54.485+01:00
109	scan chi 89.35225688681469 90.35225688681469 0...	21	823613	2020-07- 15T13:18:24.565+01:00
110	scan eta 21.03833132557845 21.058331325578454 ...	21	823614	2020-07- 15T13:19:04.035+01:00
111	scan psi 36.0 40.0 0.05 hkl [0.002723169523389...	81	823615	2020-07- 15T13:19:40.054+01:00
112	scan eta 22.11707278819746 22.41707278819746 0...	61	823616	2020-07- 15T13:22:46.198+01:00
113	scan chi 89.35225688681469 90.35225688681469 0...	21	823617	2020-07- 15T13:24:18.645+01:00
114	scan eta 22.28707278819746 22.307072788197463 ...	21	823618	2020-07- 15T13:24:58.063+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
115	scan psi 36.0 40.0 0.05 hkl [0.002310568116190...	81	823619	2020-07-15T13:25:33.967+01:00
116	scan eta 24.37067941614646 24.670679416146456 ...	61	823620	2020-07-15T13:28:12.18+01:00
117	scan chi 89.35225688681469 90.35225688681469 0...	21	823621	2020-07-15T13:29:44.11+01:00
118	scan eta 24.540679416146457 24.56067941614646 ...	21	823622	2020-07-15T13:30:48.126+01:00
119	scan psi 36.0 40.0 0.05 hkl [0.002228047832506...	81	823623	2020-07-15T13:31:23.636+01:00
120	scan eta 20.868482216249184 21.16848221624918 ...	61	823624	2020-07-15T13:34:09.701+01:00
121	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823625	2020-07-15T13:35:40.347+01:00
122	scan eta 21.028482216250172 21.048482216250175...	21	823626	2020-07-15T13:36:20.06+01:00
123	scan psi 38.0 42.0 0.05 hkl [0.001764839659563...	81	823627	2020-07-15T13:36:56.002+01:00
124	scan eta 22.122223678869183 22.42222367886918 ...	61	823628	2020-07-15T13:39:32.335+01:00
125	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823629	2020-07-15T13:41:28.937+01:00
126	scan eta 22.28222367887017 22.302223678870174 ...	21	823630	2020-07-15T13:42:08.901+01:00
127	scan psi 38.0 42.0 0.05 hkl [0.001524179715551...	81	823631	2020-07-15T13:42:44.867+01:00
128	scan eta 24.37583030681818 24.675830306818177 ...	61	823632	2020-07-15T13:45:23.183+01:00
129	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823633	2020-07-15T13:46:55.334+01:00
130	scan eta 24.535830306819182 24.555830306819185...	21	823634	2020-07-15T13:47:35.62+01:00
131	scan psi 38.0 42.0 0.05 hkl [0.001443959733199...	81	823635	2020-07-15T13:48:11.25+01:00
132	scan eta 20.873616269320436 21.173616269320434...	61	823636	2020-07-15T13:51:24.487+01:00
133	scan chi 89.35322149955316 90.35322149955316 0...	21	823637	2020-07-15T13:52:58.215+01:00
134	scan eta 21.023616269320424 21.043616269320427...	21	823638	2020-07-15T13:53:39.556+01:00
135	scan psi 40.0 44.0 0.05 hkl [0.000778219437478...	81	823639	2020-07-15T13:54:15.524+01:00
136	scan eta 22.127357731939426 22.427357731939424...	61	823640	2020-07-15T13:56:49.541+01:00

In [13]:

```
%matplotlib notebook
#azimuthal (multiple scattering) scans
#Losing alignment. check with 004 allowed.

psi_l1_scans = range(823507, 823640+1, 12)
psi_l2_scans = range(823511, 823640+1, 12)
psi_l3_scans = range(823515, 823640+1, 12)

figure()
for scan in psi_l3_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.psi, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L3')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in psi_l2_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.psi, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L2')
ylim([0,1e7])

figure()
for scan in psi_l1_scans:
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    plot(n.psi, n.roi1_sum)
    title('Gd L1')
ylim([0,1e7])
```

Out[13]: (0, 10000000.0)

```
In [14]: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
pdnx(p % 823680).plt('psi', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)
```

```
pdx(p % 823684).plt('psi', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
pdx(p % 823702).plt('DCMenergy', 'roi1_sum', ax = ax)
pdx(p % 823706).plt('DCMenergy', 'roi1_sum', ax = ax)
```

```
In [15]: showscans(range(823760, 824137+1))
```

```
Out[15]:
```

	command	length	scan	start_time
0	scan eta 20.868482216249184 21.16848221624918 ...	61	823760	2020-07-15T18:03:49.912+01:00
1	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823761	2020-07-15T18:05:25.579+01:00
2	scan eta 21.028482216250172 21.048482216250175...	21	823762	2020-07-15T18:06:07.769+01:00
3	scan psi 39.75 40.25 0.05 hkl [0.0017648396595...	11	823763	2020-07-15T18:06:44.659+01:00
4	scan eta 21.031124807320648 21.05112480732065 ...	21	823764	2020-07-15T18:07:04.021+01:00
5	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823765	2020-07-15T18:07:40.348+01:00
6	scan eta 22.121580609807573 22.42158060980757 ...	61	823766	2020-07-15T18:17:40.105+01:00
7	scan chi 89.35259053333019 90.35259053333019 0...	21	823767	2020-07-15T18:19:16.1+01:00
8	scan eta 22.281580609808575 22.30158060980858 ...	21	823768	2020-07-15T18:20:26.283+01:00
9	scan psi 39.5 40.0 0.05 hkl [0.001529745611281...	11	823769	2020-07-15T18:21:03.973+01:00
10	scan eta 22.28122349393635 22.30122349393635 0...	21	823770	2020-07-15T18:21:24.334+01:00
11	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823771	2020-07-15T18:22:01.604+01:00
12	scan eta 24.37583030681818 24.675830306818177 ...	61	823772	2020-07-15T18:32:19.161+01:00
13	scan chi 89.3526494310059 90.3526494310059 0.0...	21	823773	2020-07-15T18:33:51.143+01:00
14	scan eta 24.535830306819182 24.555830306819185...	21	823774	2020-07-15T18:34:33.33+01:00
15	scan psi 39.74999999999997 40.24999999999997 0...	11	823775	2020-07-15T18:35:09.578+01:00
16	scan eta 24.533472947672134 24.553472947672137...	21	823776	2020-07-15T18:35:29.178+01:00
17	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823777	2020-07-15T18:36:06.016+01:00
18	scan eta 20.871051739000443 21.17105173900044 ...	61	823778	2020-07-15T18:45:56.698+01:00
19	scan chi 89.35291306317944 90.35291306317944 0...	21	823779	2020-07-15T18:47:30.832+01:00
20	scan eta 21.031051739000436 21.05105173900044 ...	21	823780	2020-07-15T18:48:13.014+01:00
21	scan psi 40.75 41.25 0.05 hkl [0.0017387260106...	11	823781	2020-07-15T18:48:49.695+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
22	scan eta 21.033693155256902 21.053693155256905...	21	823782	2020-07- 15T18:49:09.679+01:00
23	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823783	2020-07- 15T18:49:46.548+01:00
24	scan eta 22.124279671438032 22.42427967143803 ...	61	823784	2020-07- 15T18:59:52.279+01:00
25	scan chi 89.35285674964219 90.35285674964219 0...	21	823785	2020-07- 15T19:01:54.534+01:00
26	scan eta 22.27927967143803 22.299279671438033 ...	21	823786	2020-07- 15T19:02:36.899+01:00
27	scan psi 40.55 41.05 0.05 hkl [0.0011890850392...	11	823787	2020-07- 15T19:03:13.673+01:00
28	scan eta 22.279921407855685 22.299921407855688...	21	823788	2020-07- 15T19:03:33.898+01:00
29	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823789	2020-07- 15T19:04:11.435+01:00
30	scan eta 24.37775788637252 24.677757886372518 ...	61	823790	2020-07- 15T19:14:30.771+01:00
31	scan chi 89.35284295137166 90.35284295137166 0...	21	823791	2020-07- 15T19:16:04.92+01:00
32	scan eta 24.53275788637252 24.55275788637252 0...	21	823792	2020-07- 15T19:16:47.244+01:00
33	scan psi 40.499999999999986 40.999999999999986...	11	823793	2020-07- 15T19:17:23.292+01:00
34	scan eta 24.533399684219813 24.553399684219816...	21	823794	2020-07- 15T19:17:42.139+01:00
35	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823795	2020-07- 15T19:18:18.609+01:00
36	scan eta 20.873616269320436 21.173616269320434...	61	823796	2020-07- 15T19:27:59.625+01:00
37	scan chi 89.35322149955316 90.35322149955316 0...	21	823797	2020-07- 15T19:29:30.252+01:00
38	scan eta 21.023616269320424 21.043616269320427...	21	823798	2020-07- 15T19:30:36.479+01:00
39	scan psi 41.75 42.25 0.05 hkl [0.0007782194374...	11	823799	2020-07- 15T19:31:11.929+01:00
40	scan eta 21.024256433898184 21.044256433898187...	21	823800	2020-07- 15T19:31:29.735+01:00
41	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823801	2020-07- 15T19:32:05.855+01:00
42	scan eta 22.127613880298227 22.427613880298225...	61	823802	2020-07- 15T19:41:50.466+01:00
43	scan chi 89.35325480392233 90.35325480392233 0...	21	823803	2020-07- 15T19:43:21.981+01:00
44	scan eta 22.277613880298215 22.29761388029822 ...	21	823804	2020-07- 15T19:44:01.534+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
45	scan psi 41.84999999999998 42.34999999999998 0...	11	823805	2020-07- 15T19:44:37.667+01:00
46	scan eta 22.277253906854813 22.297253906854817...	21	823806	2020-07- 15T19:44:56.007+01:00
47	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823807	2020-07- 15T19:45:32.216+01:00
48	scan eta 24.38083626401015 24.680836264010146 ...	61	823808	2020-07- 15T19:55:36.479+01:00
49	scan chi 89.35320501502977 90.35320501502977 0...	21	823809	2020-07- 15T19:57:07.975+01:00
50	scan eta 24.53083626401015 24.550836264010155 ...	21	823810	2020-07- 15T19:57:47.717+01:00
51	scan psi 41.699999999999974 42.199999999999974...	11	823811	2020-07- 15T19:58:23.325+01:00
52	scan eta 24.5304765114716 24.550476511471604 0...	21	823812	2020-07- 15T19:58:43.185+01:00
53	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823813	2020-07- 15T19:59:19.099+01:00
54	scan eta 20.87617502601705 21.17617502601705 0...	61	823814	2020-07- 15T20:09:05.666+01:00
55	scan chi 89.35357464617321 90.35357464617321 0...	21	823815	2020-07- 15T20:11:02.236+01:00
56	scan eta 21.026175026017054 21.046175026017057...	21	823816	2020-07- 15T20:11:41.927+01:00
57	scan psi 42.75 43.25 0.05 hkl [0.0006892846220...	11	823817	2020-07- 15T20:12:17.377+01:00
58	scan eta 21.02581363506039 21.045813635060394 ...	21	823818	2020-07- 15T20:12:37.549+01:00
59	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823819	2020-07-15T20:13:13.9+01:00
60	scan eta 22.129405236627015 22.429405236627012...	61	823820	2020-07- 15T20:23:07.019+01:00
61	scan chi 89.35350044499715 90.35350044499715 0...	21	823821	2020-07- 15T20:24:40.91+01:00
62	scan eta 22.279405236627017 22.29940523662702 ...	21	823822	2020-07- 15T20:25:20.324+01:00
63	scan psi 42.55 43.05 0.05 hkl [0.0005378520808...	11	823823	2020-07- 15T20:25:56.522+01:00
64	scan eta 22.277044193711465 22.297044193711468...	21	823824	2020-07- 15T20:26:16.153+01:00
65	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823825	2020-07- 15T20:26:52.346+01:00
66	scan eta 24.383395327914045 24.68339532791404 ...	61	823826	2020-07- 15T20:37:08.522+01:00
67	scan chi 89.353559285795 90.353559285795 0.0...	21	823827	2020-07- 15T20:38:41.002+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
68	scan eta 24.528395327914037 24.54839532791404 ...	21	823828	2020-07-15T20:39:20.709+01:00
69	scan psi 42.699999999999974 43.199999999999974...	11	823829	2020-07-15T20:39:56.562+01:00
70	scan eta 24.530034048921383 24.550034048921386...	21	823830	2020-07-15T20:40:36.906+01:00
71	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823831	2020-07-15T20:41:12.185+01:00
72	scan eta 20.878727229658963 21.17872722965896 ...	61	823832	2020-07-15T20:51:00.835+01:00
73	scan chi 89.35397239546506 90.35397239546506 0...	21	823833	2020-07-15T20:52:31.668+01:00
74	scan eta 21.02372722965796 21.043727229657964 ...	21	823834	2020-07-15T20:53:11.044+01:00
75	scan psi 43.75 44.25 0.05 hkl [0.0002259872630...	11	823835	2020-07-15T20:53:46.822+01:00
76	scan eta 21.022364136827758 21.04236413682776 ...	21	823836	2020-07-15T20:54:05.734+01:00
77	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823837	2020-07-15T20:54:42.601+01:00
78	scan eta 22.133105628121058 22.433105628121055...	61	823838	2020-07-15T21:04:38.593+01:00
79	scan chi 89.35407878805515 90.35407878805515 0...	21	823839	2020-07-15T21:06:08.22+01:00
80	scan eta 22.273105628121055 22.293105628121058...	21	823840	2020-07-15T21:06:47.941+01:00
81	scan psi 43.99999999999997 44.49999999999997 0...	11	823841	2020-07-15T21:07:24.093+01:00
82	scan eta 22.276742064997396 22.2967420649974 0...	21	823842	2020-07-15T21:07:42.996+01:00
83	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823843	2020-07-15T21:08:19.226+01:00
84	scan eta 24.387348721620228 24.687348721620225...	61	823844	2020-07-15T21:18:27.704+01:00
85	scan chi 89.35418795878007 90.35418795878007 0...	21	823845	2020-07-15T21:20:26.632+01:00
86	scan eta 24.527348721620225 24.547348721620228...	21	823846	2020-07-15T21:21:06.207+01:00
87	scan psi 44.24999999999994 44.74999999999994 0...	11	823847	2020-07-15T21:21:42.249+01:00
88	scan eta 24.525984723762956 24.54598472376296 ...	21	823848	2020-07-15T21:22:00.702+01:00
89	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823849	2020-07-15T21:22:36.717+01:00
90	scan eta 20.88127210281195 21.181272102811946 ...	61	823850	2020-07-15T21:32:23.385+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
91	scan chi 89.35441462626818 90.35441462626818 0...	21	823851	2020-07- 15T21:33:53.359+01:00
92	scan eta 21.02127210281294 21.041272102812943 ...	21	823852	2020-07- 15T21:34:32.859+01:00
93	scan psi 44.75 45.25 0.05 hkl [-0.000222144146...	11	823853	2020-07- 15T21:35:08.171+01:00
94	scan eta 21.018907113288893 21.038907113288897...	21	823854	2020-07- 15T21:35:27.938+01:00
95	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823855	2020-07- 15T21:36:04.304+01:00
96	scan eta 22.134378076811025 22.434378076811022...	61	823856	2020-07- 15T21:45:50.172+01:00
97	scan chi 89.3542999055615 90.3542999055615 0.0...	21	823857	2020-07- 15T21:47:19.268+01:00
98	scan eta 22.274378076811022 22.294378076811025...	21	823858	2020-07- 15T21:47:59.028+01:00
99	scan psi 44.5 45.0 0.05 hkl [-0.00022311131573...	11	823859	2020-07- 15T21:48:34.485+01:00
100	scan eta 22.272013593904735 22.292013593904738...	21	823860	2020-07- 15T21:48:52.715+01:00
101	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823861	2020-07- 15T21:49:28.506+01:00
102	scan eta 24.388238960227774 24.68823896022777 ...	61	823862	2020-07- 15T21:59:34.944+01:00
103	scan chi 89.35434546109451 90.35434546109451 0...	21	823863	2020-07- 15T22:01:35.652+01:00
104	scan eta 24.52323896022776 24.543238960227765 ...	21	823864	2020-07- 15T22:02:15.165+01:00
105	scan psi 44.59999999999999 45.09999999999999 0...	11	823865	2020-07- 15T22:02:51.104+01:00
106	scan eta 24.524874285571133 24.544874285571137...	21	823866	2020-07- 15T22:03:09.869+01:00
107	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823867	2020-07- 15T22:03:45.942+01:00
108	scan eta 20.883808870272276 21.183808870272273...	61	823868	2020-07- 15T22:13:31.055+01:00
109	scan chi 89.35490120387247 90.35490120387247 0...	21	823869	2020-07- 15T22:15:00.212+01:00
110	scan eta 21.018808870272277 21.03880887027228 ...	21	823870	2020-07- 15T22:15:39.984+01:00
111	scan psi 45.75 46.25 0.05 hkl [-0.000436466725...	11	823871	2020-07- 15T22:16:15.692+01:00
112	scan eta 21.018441761759664 21.038441761759668...	21	823872	2020-07- 15T22:16:35.374+01:00
113	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823873	2020-07- 15T22:17:10.984+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
114	scan eta 22.137297042945136 22.437297042945133...	61	823874	2020-07- 15T22:26:58.595+01:00
115	scan chi 89.35485055462459 90.35485055462459 0...	21	823875	2020-07- 15T22:28:30.812+01:00
116	scan eta 22.277297042945133 22.297297042945136...	21	823876	2020-07- 15T22:29:10.112+01:00
117	scan psi 45.64999999999999 46.14999999999999 0...	11	823877	2020-07- 15T22:29:45.811+01:00
118	scan eta 22.277930101095496 22.2979301010955 0...	21	823878	2020-07- 15T22:30:33.705+01:00
119	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823879	2020-07- 15T22:31:10.15+01:00
120	scan eta 24.391536729044496 24.691536729044493...	61	823880	2020-07- 15T22:41:22.567+01:00
121	scan chi 89.35497800644022 90.35497800644022 0...	21	823881	2020-07- 15T22:42:57.275+01:00
122	scan eta 24.521536729044872 24.541536729044875...	21	823882	2020-07- 15T22:43:38.407+01:00
123	scan psi 45.899999999999996 46.399999999999996 0...	11	823883	2020-07- 15T22:44:15.959+01:00
124	scan eta 24.52394927411134 24.543949274111345 ...	21	823884	2020-07- 15T22:44:35.788+01:00
125	scan energy 7.21 7.2700000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823885	2020-07- 15T22:45:13.095+01:00
126	scan eta 20.886336759307042 21.18633675930704 ...	61	823886	2020-07- 15T22:55:06.652+01:00
127	scan chi 89.35543198005905 90.35543198005905 0...	21	823887	2020-07- 15T22:56:41.594+01:00
128	scan eta 21.01633675930705 21.03633675930705 0...	21	823888	2020-07- 15T22:57:23.905+01:00
129	scan psi 46.75 47.25 0.05 hkl [-0.000785605709...	11	823889	2020-07- 15T22:58:01.059+01:00
130	scan eta 21.01596735745186 21.035967357451863 ...	21	823890	2020-07-15T22:58:21.2+01:00
131	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823891	2020-07- 15T22:58:58.53+01:00
132	scan eta 22.140330492845983 22.44033049284598 ...	61	823892	2020-07- 15T23:09:10.387+01:00
133	scan chi 89.35548748249121 90.35548748249121 0...	21	823893	2020-07- 15T23:11:11.818+01:00
134	scan eta 22.26533049284598 22.285330492845983 ...	21	823894	2020-07- 15T23:11:54.14+01:00
135	scan psi 46.84999999999999 47.34999999999999 0...	11	823895	2020-07- 15T23:12:31.352+01:00
136	scan eta 22.266960874160322 22.286960874160325...	21	823896	2020-07- 15T23:12:50.46+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
137	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823897	2020-07-15T23:13:28.228+01:00
138	scan eta 24.39456737092155 24.694567370921547 ...	61	823898	2020-07-15T23:23:54.6+01:00
139	scan chi 89.35562816412171 90.35562816412171 0...	21	823899	2020-07-15T23:25:29.228+01:00
140	scan eta 24.514567370921537 24.53456737092154 ...	21	823900	2020-07-15T23:26:12.145+01:00
141	scan psi 47.099999999999996 47.599999999999996 0...	11	823901	2020-07-15T23:26:48.844+01:00
142	scan eta 24.516197178200972 24.536197178200975...	21	823902	2020-07-15T23:27:08.616+01:00
143	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823903	2020-07-15T23:27:45.641+01:00
144	scan eta 20.888854999890277 21.188854999890275...	61	823904	2020-07-15T23:37:30.389+01:00
145	scan chi 89.35600679314452 90.35600679314452 0...	21	823905	2020-07-15T23:39:04.641+01:00
146	scan eta 21.013854999890274 21.033854999890277...	21	823906	2020-07-15T23:39:46.941+01:00
147	scan psi 47.750000000000001 48.250000000000001 0...	11	823907	2020-07-15T23:40:49.575+01:00
148	scan eta 21.01448310291963 21.034483102919634 ...	21	823908	2020-07-15T23:41:10.064+01:00
149	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823909	2020-07-15T23:41:47.335+01:00
150	scan eta 22.141967848908834 22.44196784890883 ...	61	823910	2020-07-15T23:51:38.457+01:00
151	scan chi 89.35585897076074 90.35585897076074 0...	21	823911	2020-07-15T23:53:13.478+01:00
152	scan eta 22.26696784890883 22.286967848908834 ...	21	823912	2020-07-15T23:53:55.588+01:00
153	scan psi 47.500000000000001 48.000000000000001 0...	11	823913	2020-07-15T23:54:32.809+01:00
154	scan eta 22.27059657523368 22.290596575233682 ...	21	823914	2020-07-15T23:54:55.377+01:00
155	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823915	2020-07-15T23:55:32.942+01:00
156	scan eta 24.396203090459274 24.69620309045927 ...	61	823916	2020-07-16T00:05:53.051+01:00
157	scan chi 89.35600679314452 90.35600679314452 0...	21	823917	2020-07-16T00:07:28.909+01:00
158	scan eta 24.516203090459133 24.536203090459136...	21	823918	2020-07-16T00:08:11.839+01:00
159	scan psi 47.749999999999998 48.249999999999998 0...	11	823919	2020-07-16T00:08:49.024+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
160	scan eta 24.522612998554454 24.542612998554457...	21	823920	2020-07-16T00:09:09.5+01:00
161	scan energy 7.21 7.2700000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823921	2020-07-16T00:09:45.964+01:00
162	scan eta 20.891362824931022 21.19136282493102 ...	61	823922	2020-07-16T00:19:41.903+01:00
163	scan chi 89.35662546803253 90.35662546803253 0...	21	823923	2020-07-16T00:21:45.719+01:00
164	scan eta 21.01136282493101 21.031362824931012 ...	21	823924	2020-07-16T00:22:28.053+01:00
165	scan psi 48.75 49.25 0.05 hkl [-0.001236642115...	11	823925	2020-07-16T00:23:05.005+01:00
166	scan eta 21.01398823211103 21.03398823211103 0...	21	823926	2020-07-16T00:23:23.162+01:00
167	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823927	2020-07-16T00:23:59.164+01:00
168	scan eta 22.14572952678823 22.445729526788227 ...	61	823928	2020-07-16T00:33:59.708+01:00
169	scan chi 89.35678696836897 90.35678696836897 0...	21	823929	2020-07-16T00:35:31.333+01:00
170	scan eta 22.260729526788236 22.28072952678824 ...	21	823930	2020-07-16T00:36:10.957+01:00
171	scan psi 48.99999999999997 49.49999999999997 0...	11	823931	2020-07-16T00:36:46.897+01:00
172	scan eta 22.26235427776037 22.282354277760373 ...	21	823932	2020-07-16T00:37:06.305+01:00
173	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823933	2020-07-16T00:37:43.05+01:00
174	scan eta 24.399960683339444 24.69996068333944 ...	61	823934	2020-07-16T00:47:46.928+01:00
175	scan chi 89.35695119527962 90.35695119527962 0...	21	823935	2020-07-16T00:49:17.465+01:00
176	scan eta 24.51496068333928 24.534960683339282 ...	21	823936	2020-07-16T00:50:27.923+01:00
177	scan psi 49.24999999999994 49.74999999999994 0...	11	823937	2020-07-16T00:51:03.483+01:00
178	scan eta 24.515366540960375 24.53536654096038 ...	21	823938	2020-07-16T00:51:21.125+01:00
179	scan energy 7.21 7.2700000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823939	2020-07-16T00:51:56.682+01:00
180	scan eta 20.893859470515494 21.19385947051549 ...	61	823940	2020-07-16T01:01:37.104+01:00
181	scan chi 89.35728781626503 90.35728781626503 0...	21	823941	2020-07-16T01:03:08.961+01:00
182	scan eta 21.01385947051548 21.033859470515484 ...	21	823942	2020-07-16T01:03:48.729+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
183	scan psi 49.75 50.25 0.05 hkl [-0.001615501418...	11	823943	2020-07-16T01:04:24.371+01:00
184	scan eta 21.01048201834853 21.030482018348533 ...	21	823944	2020-07-16T01:04:42.676+01:00
185	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823945	2020-07-16T01:05:18.919+01:00
186	scan eta 22.148223258541044 22.44822325854104 ...	61	823946	2020-07-16T01:15:18.058+01:00
187	scan chi 89.35746020393077 90.35746020393077 0...	21	823947	2020-07-16T01:16:48.797+01:00
188	scan eta 22.263223258541036 22.28322325854104 ...	21	823948	2020-07-16T01:17:28.336+01:00
189	scan psi 49.9999999999997 50.4999999999997 0...	11	823949	2020-07-16T01:18:04.212+01:00
190	scan eta 22.26084508414755 22.280845084147554 ...	21	823950	2020-07-16T01:18:21.913+01:00
191	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823951	2020-07-16T01:18:58.724+01:00
192	scan eta 24.401332086247017 24.701332086247014...	61	823952	2020-07-16T01:29:19.638+01:00
193	scan chi 89.35732207653906 90.35732207653906 0...	21	823953	2020-07-16T01:31:18.95+01:00
194	scan eta 24.511332086246345 24.531332086246348...	21	823954	2020-07-16T01:31:59.047+01:00
195	scan psi 49.7999999999997 50.2999999999997 0...	11	823955	2020-07-16T01:32:34.715+01:00
196	scan eta 24.513736340917287 24.53373634091729 ...	21	823956	2020-07-16T01:32:53.751+01:00
197	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823957	2020-07-16T01:33:29.733+01:00
198	scan eta 20.89634417613304 21.19634417613304 0...	61	823958	2020-07-16T01:43:28.087+01:00
199	scan chi 89.35799363608076 90.35799363608076 0...	21	823959	2020-07-16T01:45:00.702+01:00
200	scan eta 21.006344176133037 21.02634417613304 ...	21	823960	2020-07-16T01:45:40.395+01:00
201	scan psi 50.75 51.25 0.05 hkl [-0.001845263689...	11	823961	2020-07-16T01:46:16.32+01:00
202	scan eta 21.008963656537798 21.0289636565378 0...	21	823962	2020-07-16T01:46:35.767+01:00
203	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823963	2020-07-16T01:47:11.195+01:00
204	scan eta 22.149465623175644 22.44946562317564 ...	61	823964	2020-07-16T01:57:03.358+01:00
205	scan chi 89.35781311719816 90.35781311719816 0...	21	823965	2020-07-16T01:58:36.812+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
206	scan eta 22.25946562317564 22.279465623175643 ...	21	823966	2020-07-16T01:59:16.358+01:00
207	scan psi 50.5 51.0 0.05 hkl [-0.00178893210470...	11	823967	2020-07-16T01:59:52.786+01:00
208	scan eta 22.26308588818456 22.283085888184562 ...	21	823968	2020-07-16T02:00:36.09+01:00
209	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823969	2020-07-16T02:01:12.844+01:00
210	scan eta 24.403692266702038 24.703692266702035...	61	823970	2020-07-16T02:11:25.163+01:00
211	scan chi 89.35799363608076 90.35799363608076 0...	21	823971	2020-07-16T02:12:58.313+01:00
212	scan eta 24.513692266702034 24.533692266702037...	21	823972	2020-07-16T02:13:38.242+01:00
213	scan psi 50.74999999999997 51.2499999999997 0...	11	823973	2020-07-16T02:14:14.131+01:00
214	scan eta 24.515311756025927 24.53531175602593 ...	21	823974	2020-07-16T02:14:34.548+01:00
215	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823975	2020-07-16T02:15:10.043+01:00
216	scan eta 20.89881618491045 21.19881618491045 0...	61	823976	2020-07-16T02:24:48.869+01:00
217	scan chi 89.35874271247627 90.35874271247627 0...	21	823977	2020-07-16T02:26:20.532+01:00
218	scan eta 21.003816184911447 21.02381618491145 ...	21	823978	2020-07-16T02:27:00.123+01:00
219	scan psi 51.75 52.25 0.05 hkl [-0.002385460834...	11	823979	2020-07-16T02:27:36.744+01:00
220	scan eta 21.002432453003895 21.022432453003898...	21	823980	2020-07-16T02:27:56.464+01:00
221	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823981	2020-07-16T02:28:32.604+01:00
222	scan eta 22.15317357751305 22.45317357751305 0...	61	823982	2020-07-16T02:38:25.215+01:00
223	scan chi 89.35893671396413 90.35893671396413 0...	21	823983	2020-07-16T02:40:27.166+01:00
224	scan eta 22.253173577513056 22.27317357751306 ...	21	823984	2020-07-16T02:41:07.031+01:00
225	scan psi 51.99999999999997 52.4999999999997 0...	11	823985	2020-07-16T02:41:42.759+01:00
226	scan eta 22.255789002039446 22.27578900203945 ...	21	823986	2020-07-16T02:42:02.161+01:00
227	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823987	2020-07-16T02:42:38.056+01:00
228	scan eta 24.40702633944977 24.70702633944977 0...	61	823988	2020-07-16T02:52:53.387+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
229	scan chi 89.35901506674882 90.35901506674882 0...	21	823989	2020-07- 16T02:54:27.314+01:00
230	scan eta 24.512026339450355 24.532026339450358...	21	823990	2020-07- 16T02:55:07.828+01:00
231	scan psi 52.09999999999995 52.59999999999995 0...	11	823991	2020-07- 16T02:55:43.949+01:00
232	scan eta 24.511423226328883 24.531423226328886...	21	823992	2020-07- 16T02:56:03.949+01:00
233	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	823993	2020-07- 16T02:56:39.944+01:00
234	scan eta 20.901274743844922 21.20127474384492 ...	61	823994	2020-07- 16T03:06:29.379+01:00
235	scan chi 89.35953481727152 90.35953481727152 0...	21	823995	2020-07- 16T03:08:02.718+01:00
236	scan eta 21.001274743844913 21.021274743844916...	21	823996	2020-07- 16T03:08:42.485+01:00
237	scan psi 52.75 53.25 0.05 hkl [-0.002457854762...	11	823997	2020-07- 16T03:09:18.063+01:00
238	scan eta 21.002887550002068 21.02288755000207 ...	21	823998	2020-07- 16T03:09:38.311+01:00
239	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	823999	2020-07- 16T03:10:39.959+01:00
240	scan eta 22.15562865680358 22.455628656803576 ...	61	824000	2020-07- 16T03:20:03.417+01:00
241	scan chi 89.35973953866888 90.35973953866888 0...	21	824001	2020-07- 16T03:21:52.274+01:00
242	scan eta 22.250628656803574 22.270628656803577...	21	824002	2020-07- 16T03:22:32.054+01:00
243	scan psi 52.99999999999997 53.49999999999997 0...	11	824003	2020-07- 16T03:23:08.037+01:00
244	scan eta 22.252240607274235 22.272240607274238...	21	824004	2020-07- 16T03:23:27.036+01:00
245	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824005	2020-07- 16T03:24:03.155+01:00
246	scan eta 24.409602324133417 24.709602324133414...	61	824006	2020-07- 16T03:34:17.794+01:00
247	scan chi 89.3598636535318 90.3598636535318 0.0...	21	824007	2020-07- 16T03:35:51.673+01:00
248	scan eta 24.504602324132872 24.524602324132875...	21	824008	2020-07- 16T03:36:32.046+01:00
249	scan psi 53.14999999999995 53.64999999999995 0...	11	824009	2020-07- 16T03:37:08.079+01:00
250	scan eta 24.505995560327907 24.52599556032791 ...	21	824010	2020-07- 16T03:37:29.086+01:00
251	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824011	2020-07- 16T03:38:04.626+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
252	scan eta 20.90371910402731 21.203719104027307 ...	61	824012	2020-07-16T03:47:56.03+01:00
253	scan chi 89.36036970917944 90.36036970917944 0...	21	824013	2020-07-16T03:49:28.968+01:00
254	scan eta 21.003719104027315 21.023719104027318...	21	824014	2020-07-16T03:50:38.171+01:00
255	scan psi 53.75 54.25 0.05 hkl [-0.002400556194...	11	824015	2020-07-16T03:51:14.523+01:00
256	scan eta 21.005328244256926 21.02532824425693 ...	21	824016	2020-07-16T03:51:34.22+01:00
257	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824017	2020-07-16T03:52:11.401+01:00
258	scan eta 22.156972866315165 22.456972866315162...	61	824018	2020-07-16T04:02:14.434+01:00
259	scan chi 89.36019931984906 90.36019931984906 0...	21	824019	2020-07-16T04:03:49.742+01:00
260	scan eta 22.25197286631516 22.271972866315163 ...	21	824020	2020-07-16T04:04:31.867+01:00
261	scan psi 53.55 54.05 0.05 hkl [-0.002845011415...	11	824021	2020-07-16T04:05:09.559+01:00
262	scan eta 22.251582815203474 22.271582815203477...	21	824022	2020-07-16T04:05:28.904+01:00
263	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824023	2020-07-16T04:06:05.688+01:00
264	scan eta 24.409969037319165 24.709969037319162...	61	824024	2020-07-16T04:16:27.924+01:00
265	scan chi 89.35998872887485 90.35998872887485 0...	21	824025	2020-07-16T04:18:03.357+01:00
266	scan eta 24.50496903731877 24.524969037318773 ...	21	824026	2020-07-16T04:18:45.498+01:00
267	scan psi 53.3 53.8 0.05 hkl [0.001474188500405...	11	824027	2020-07-16T04:19:22.15+01:00
268	scan eta 24.506361723952796 24.5263617239528 0...	21	824028	2020-07-16T04:19:42.049+01:00
269	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824029	2020-07-16T04:20:47.319+01:00
270	scan eta 20.90614852087817 21.206148520878166 ...	61	824030	2020-07-16T04:30:06.764+01:00
271	scan chi 89.3612471338796 90.3612471338796 0.0...	21	824031	2020-07-16T04:31:54.978+01:00
272	scan eta 20.99614852087817 21.016148520878172 ...	21	824032	2020-07-16T04:32:37.032+01:00
273	scan psi 54.75 55.25 0.05 hkl [-0.002943174055...	11	824033	2020-07-16T04:33:13.416+01:00
274	scan eta 20.997753896224292 21.017753896224296...	21	824034	2020-07-16T04:33:33.972+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
275	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824035	2020-07-16T04:34:11.396+01:00
276	scan eta 22.160494915989176 22.460494915989173...	61	824036	2020-07-16T04:44:25.571+01:00
277	scan chi 89.36147310476525 90.36147310476525 0...	21	824037	2020-07-16T04:46:02.248+01:00
278	scan eta 22.250494915989176 22.27049491598918 ...	21	824038	2020-07-16T04:46:44.505+01:00
279	scan psi 54.9999999999997 55.4999999999997 0...	11	824039	2020-07-16T04:47:21.183+01:00
280	scan eta 22.25109930824672 22.271099308246722 ...	21	824040	2020-07-16T04:47:41.438+01:00
281	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824041	2020-07-16T04:48:18.25+01:00
282	scan eta 24.413859689307287 24.713859689307284...	61	824042	2020-07-16T04:58:40.979+01:00
283	scan chi 89.36138239968622 90.36138239968622 0...	21	824043	2020-07-16T05:00:43.414+01:00
284	scan eta 24.503859689307166 24.52385968930717 ...	21	824044	2020-07-16T05:01:26.521+01:00
285	scan psi 54.8999999999996 55.3999999999996 0...	11	824045	2020-07-16T05:02:03.3+01:00
286	scan eta 24.50224633304322 24.522246333043224 ...	21	824046	2020-07-16T05:02:23.369+01:00
287	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824047	2020-07-16T05:03:00.373+01:00
288	scan eta 20.90856225436618 21.20856225436618 0...	61	824048	2020-07-16T05:12:46.205+01:00
289	scan chi 89.36216682409531 90.36216682409531 0...	21	824049	2020-07-16T05:14:20.614+01:00
290	scan eta 20.993562254366186 21.01356225436619 ...	21	824050	2020-07-16T05:15:03.064+01:00
291	scan psi 55.75 56.25 0.05 hkl [-0.003103602384...	11	824051	2020-07-16T05:15:39.366+01:00
292	scan eta 20.99616362839851 21.016163628398512 ...	21	824052	2020-07-16T05:15:57.313+01:00
293	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824053	2020-07-16T05:16:34.754+01:00
294	scan eta 22.162063070381613 22.46206307038161 ...	61	824054	2020-07-16T05:26:32.21+01:00
295	scan chi 89.36207296100939 90.36207296100939 0...	21	824055	2020-07-16T05:28:05.724+01:00
296	scan eta 22.247063070381618 22.26706307038162 ...	21	824056	2020-07-16T05:28:48.404+01:00
297	scan psi 55.6499999999999 56.1499999999999 0...	11	824057	2020-07-16T05:29:24.998+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
298	scan eta 22.246664881569405 22.266664881569408...	21	824058	2020-07-16T05:29:43.87+01:00
299	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824059	2020-07-16T05:30:46.725+01:00
300	scan eta 24.415067368298587 24.715067368298584...	61	824060	2020-07-16T05:40:55.634+01:00
301	scan chi 89.36184014207362 90.36184014207362 0...	21	824061	2020-07-16T05:42:28.948+01:00
302	scan eta 24.500067368299018 24.52006736829902 ...	21	824062	2020-07-16T05:43:09.603+01:00
303	scan psi 55.39999999999999 55.89999999999999 0...	11	824063	2020-07-16T05:43:45.008+01:00
304	scan eta 24.500452031635636 24.52045203163564 ...	21	824064	2020-07-16T05:44:05.191+01:00
305	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824065	2020-07-16T05:44:41.5+01:00
306	scan eta 20.910959569241193 21.21095956924119 ...	61	824066	2020-07-16T05:54:20.372+01:00
307	scan chi 89.36312849967555 90.36312849967555 0...	21	824067	2020-07-16T05:55:54.212+01:00
308	scan eta 20.990959569241188 21.01095956924119 ...	21	824068	2020-07-16T05:56:33.914+01:00
309	scan psi 56.75000000000001 57.25000000000001 0...	11	824069	2020-07-16T05:57:09.497+01:00
310	scan eta 20.992556775644356 21.01255677564436 ...	21	824070	2020-07-16T05:57:29.829+01:00
311	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824071	2020-07-16T05:58:05.955+01:00
312	scan eta 22.164103282409584 22.46410328240958 ...	61	824072	2020-07-16T06:08:01.194+01:00
313	scan chi 89.36288416045537 90.36288416045537 0...	21	824073	2020-07-16T06:09:35.233+01:00
314	scan eta 22.23410328240959 22.25410328240959 0...	21	824074	2020-07-16T06:10:41.965+01:00
315	scan psi 56.50000000000001 57.00000000000001 0...	11	824075	2020-07-16T06:11:18.053+01:00
316	scan eta 22.233701659702167 22.25370165970217 ...	21	824076	2020-07-16T06:11:36.867+01:00
317	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824077	2020-07-16T06:12:12.736+01:00
318	scan eta 24.417111100459266 24.717111100459263...	61	824078	2020-07-16T06:22:19.959+01:00
319	scan chi 89.36264243172529 90.36264243172529 0...	21	824079	2020-07-16T06:23:54.102+01:00
320	scan eta 24.497111100459247 24.51711110045925 ...	21	824080	2020-07-16T06:24:34.713+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
321	scan psi 56.25000000000001 56.75000000000001 0...	11	824081	2020-07- 16T06:25:10.635+01:00
322	scan eta 24.49949227149713 24.519492271497132 ...	21	824082	2020-07- 16T06:25:28.004+01:00
323	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824083	2020-07- 16T06:26:04.181+01:00
324	scan eta 20.913339735253302 21.2133397352533 0...	61	824084	2020-07- 16T06:35:46.469+01:00
325	scan chi 89.36413186767993 90.36413186767993 0...	21	824085	2020-07- 16T06:37:19.096+01:00
326	scan eta 20.993339735253297 21.0133397352533 0...	21	824086	2020-07- 16T06:37:58.841+01:00
327	scan psi 57.75000000000001 58.25000000000001 0...	11	824087	2020-07- 16T06:38:34.275+01:00
328	scan eta 20.990932575279086 21.01093257527909 ...	21	824088	2020-07- 16T06:38:52.595+01:00
329	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824089	2020-07- 16T06:39:27.904+01:00
330	scan eta 22.166487803816658 22.466487803816655...	61	824090	2020-07- 16T06:49:24.317+01:00
331	scan chi 89.3638771335129 90.3638771335129 0.0...	21	824091	2020-07- 16T06:51:24.12+01:00
332	scan eta 22.246487803817647 22.26648780381765 ...	21	824092	2020-07- 16T06:52:03.837+01:00
333	scan psi 57.50000000000001 58.00000000000001 0...	11	824093	2020-07- 16T06:52:40.298+01:00
334	scan eta 22.245081752408407 22.26508175240841 ...	21	824094	2020-07- 16T06:52:59.912+01:00
335	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824095	2020-07- 16T06:53:35.848+01:00
336	scan eta 24.419737863802084 24.71973786380208 ...	61	824096	2020-07- 16T07:03:47.679+01:00
337	scan chi 89.36372553666486 90.36372553666486 0...	21	824097	2020-07- 16T07:05:21.036+01:00
338	scan eta 24.494737863802182 24.514737863802186...	21	824098	2020-07- 16T07:06:02.049+01:00
339	scan psi 57.35 57.85 0.05 hkl [0.0008858580481...	11	824099	2020-07- 16T07:06:38.006+01:00
340	scan eta 24.497114330863273 24.517114330863276...	21	824100	2020-07- 16T07:06:55.231+01:00
341	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824101	2020-07- 16T07:07:31.546+01:00
342	scan eta 20.91570202737593 21.215702027375926 ...	61	824102	2020-07- 16T07:17:12.505+01:00
343	scan chi 89.36517662246786 90.36517662246786 0...	21	824103	2020-07- 16T07:18:45.627+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
344	scan eta 20.990702027375928 21.01070202737593 ...	21	824104	2020-07-16T07:19:25.359+01:00
345	scan psi 58.75000000000001 59.25000000000001 0...	11	824105	2020-07-16T07:20:26.819+01:00
346	scan eta 20.99129030394874 21.011290303948744 ...	21	824106	2020-07-16T07:20:44.308+01:00
347	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824107	2020-07-16T07:21:20.048+01:00
348	scan eta 22.17003118578343 22.470031185783427 ...	61	824108	2020-07-16T07:31:20.569+01:00
349	scan chi 89.36544424083033 90.36544424083033 0...	21	824109	2020-07-16T07:32:55.518+01:00
350	scan eta 22.240031185783433 22.260031185783436...	21	824110	2020-07-16T07:33:35.383+01:00
351	scan psi 58.99999999999998 59.49999999999998 0...	11	824111	2020-07-16T07:34:11.107+01:00
352	scan eta 22.24061833081475 22.260618330814754 ...	21	824112	2020-07-16T07:34:30.382+01:00
353	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824113	2020-07-16T07:35:07.524+01:00
354	scan eta 24.423755212450935 24.723755212450932...	61	824114	2020-07-16T07:45:23.035+01:00
355	scan chi 89.36549807207675 90.36549807207675 0...	21	824115	2020-07-16T07:46:57.342+01:00
356	scan eta 24.488755212450943 24.508755212450946...	21	824116	2020-07-16T07:47:37.356+01:00
357	scan psi 59.04999999999996 59.54999999999996 0...	11	824117	2020-07-16T07:48:12.874+01:00
358	scan eta 24.48934216259779 24.509342162597793 ...	21	824118	2020-07-16T07:48:32.056+01:00
359	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824119	2020-07-16T07:49:07.582+01:00
360	scan eta 20.918045726030755 21.218045726030752...	61	824120	2020-07-16T07:58:54.88+01:00
361	scan chi 89.36626244579158 90.36626244579158 0...	21	824121	2020-07-16T08:00:55.336+01:00
362	scan eta 20.988045726030744 21.008045726030748...	21	824122	2020-07-16T08:01:35.3+01:00
363	scan psi 59.74999999999999 60.24999999999999 0...	11	824123	2020-07-16T08:02:11.817+01:00
364	scan eta 20.987629293429496 21.0076292934295 0...	21	824124	2020-07-16T08:02:31.253+01:00
365	scan energy 8.350000000000001 8.41 5.0E-4 hkl ...	121	824125	2020-07-16T08:03:07.441+01:00
366	scan eta 22.172253634238963 22.47225363423896 ...	61	824126	2020-07-16T08:13:14.761+01:00

	command	length	scan	start_time
367	scan chi 89.36648450979278 90.36648450979278 0...	21	824127	2020-07-16T08:14:49.145+01:00
368	scan eta 22.237253634238957 22.25725363423896 ...	21	824128	2020-07-16T08:15:28.884+01:00
369	scan psi 59.94999999999997 60.44999999999997 0...	11	824129	2020-07-16T08:16:04.765+01:00
370	scan eta 22.23883625324613 22.258836253246134 ...	21	824130	2020-07-16T08:16:21.779+01:00
371	scan energy 7.899999999999995 7.96 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824131	2020-07-16T08:16:57.742+01:00
372	scan eta 24.426093193587754 24.72609319358775 ...	61	824132	2020-07-16T08:27:08.967+01:00
373	scan chi 89.36659615203028 90.36659615203028 0...	21	824133	2020-07-16T08:28:45.067+01:00
374	scan eta 24.49109319358769 24.511093193587694 ...	21	824134	2020-07-16T08:29:25.535+01:00
375	scan psi 60.049999999999955 60.549999999999955...	11	824135	2020-07-16T08:30:26.481+01:00
376	scan eta 24.49145718792818 24.511457187928183 ...	21	824136	2020-07-16T08:30:45.418+01:00
377	scan energy 7.21 7.270000000000005 5.0E-4 hkl...	121	824137	2020-07-16T08:31:21.327+01:00

```
#schroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schroi', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1;
schroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.)) #scroi_bg =
HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=13; jw=15;
scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.-16)) edic = { 'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh': 7.0},
'l2': {'eres': 7.93, 'ethresh': 6.7}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.24, 'ethresh': 6.5}, } #823760 - 824160 stopped psi ~ 61.75 pos atten 0
for psival in range(40, 71, 1): pos psic psival for ed in edic: print(ed) pos pil3_thresh edic[ed]['ethresh'] pos w 10
#wait for threshol ener = edic[ed]['eres'] pos energy ener pos hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 61 checkbeam pil3 .5
lcroi scroi go maxval scancn chi .05 21 checkbeam pil3 .5 schroi go maxval scancn eta .001 21 checkbeam pil3 .5
lcroi scroi go maxval hh = hkl() scancn psic .05 11 hkl hh pil3 .5 lcroi scroi_bg scroi go minval scancn eta .001 21
checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi go maxval hh = hkl() scan energy ener-.03 ener+.03 .0005 hkl hh checkbeam pil3 1
lcroi scroi_bg scroi
```

In [16]:

```
#energy scans with different psi values (script above)
#Lots of multiple scattering

first = 823760
last = 824137
psi_l1_scans = range(823763, last+1, 18)
psi_l2_scans = range(823769, last+1, 18)
psi_l3_scans = range(823775, last+1, 18)
en_l1_scans = range(823765, last+1, 18)
en_l2_scans = range(823771, last+1, 18)
en_l3_scans = range(823777, last+1, 18)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in en_l1_scans:
    pdnx(p % scan).plt('DCMenergy', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in en_l2_scans:
```

```
pdnx(p % scan).plt('DCMenergy', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in en_l3_scans:
    pdnx(p % scan).plt('DCMenergy', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

#ylim([0,1e7])

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in psi_l1_scans:
    pdnx(p % scan).plt('psi', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in psi_l2_scans:
    pdnx(p % scan).plt('psi', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1)
for scan in psi_l3_scans:
    pdnx(p % scan).plt('psi', 'roi1_sum', ax=ax)

#ylim([0,1e7])
```


In [17]: `showscans(range(824165, 825283+1), metadata = ['entry1/sample/beam/incident_energy'],`

Out[17]:

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
0	scan idgap 6.36085 6.400849999999999 0.002 Bea...	7.24399716251239	21	61.74999999999992	824165	2016T10:48:38.614
1	scan eta 24.374194904580946 24.674194904580943...	7.24399716251239	61	45.00022433636228	824166	2016T10:49:14.018
2	scan chi 89.35441462626818 90.35441462626818 0...	7.244001619177332	21	44.99880169434683	824167	2016T10:50:47.797
3	scan eta 24.60781523218753 24.64781523218753 0...	7.213997701085241	41	44.99971759756888	824168	2016T10:51:35.317
4	scan eta 24.607982027288354 24.647982027288354...	7.2139999102576216	41	45.09977063661253	824169	2016T10:52:41.732
5	scan eta 24.608148756052127 24.648148756052127...	7.2139999102576216	41	45.199840174567896	824170	2016T10:53:48.153
6	scan eta 24.60831541797369 24.648315417973688 ...	7.213997701085241	41	45.29988954247223	824171	2016T10:54:54.982

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
7	scan eta 24.60848201254362 24.64848201254362 0...	7.2139999102576216	41	45.39992768874273	824172	20 16T10:56:01.885
8	scan eta 24.6086485392557 24.6486485392557 0.0...	7.213997701085241	41	45.50000294120815	824173	20 16T10:57:09.18
9	scan eta 24.608814997602064 24.648814997602063...	7.2139999102576216	41	45.60006697870829	824174	20 16T10:58:15.667
10	scan eta 24.608981387075684 24.648981387075683...	7.214004328606605	41	45.70010879392465	824175	20 16T10:59:22.144
11	scan eta 24.609147707168244 24.649147707168243...	7.213997701085241	41	45.80019137883633	824176	20 16T11:00:29.405
12	scan eta 24.609313957376255 24.649313957376254...	7.2139999102576216	41	45.9002313620879	824177	20 16T11:01:36.48
13	scan eta 24.609480137189987 24.649480137189986...	7.21400211943141	41	46.000310298411186	824178	20 16T11:02:44.051
14	scan eta 24.609646246106134 24.649646246106133...	7.213997701085241	41	46.10037616094961	824179	20 16T11:03:51.242
15	scan eta 24.60981228361651 24.64981228361651 0...	7.213997701085241	41	46.20043836657759	824180	20 16T11:04:59.581
16	scan eta 24.60997824921613 24.64997824921613 0...	7.2139999102576216	41	46.299480173429316	824181	20 16T11:06:08.268
17	scan eta 24.61014414239921 24.65014414239921 0...	7.2139999102576216	41	46.3995442120889	824182	20 16T11:07:17.85
18	scan eta 24.610309962661372 24.65030996266137 ...	7.21400211943141	41	46.499610061969534	824183	20 16T11:08:28.225
19	scan eta 24.61047570949572 24.65047570949572 0...	7.213995491914268	41	46.599659669687384	824184	20 16T11:09:38.501
20	scan eta 24.610641382398764 24.650641382398764...	7.213997701085241	41	46.699738163350496	824185	20 16T11:10:49.812
21	scan eta 24.610806980866176 24.650806980866175...	7.214006537783209	41	46.7998040343747	824186	20 16T11:12:00.497

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
22	scan eta 24.610972504392304 24.650972504392303...	7.213997701085241	41	46.89989213788191	824187	20 16T11:13:12.148
23	scan eta 24.61113795247277 24.65113795247277 0...	7.2139999102576216	41	46.99993577924651	824188	20 16T11:14:21.839
24	scan eta 24.611303324604744 24.651303324604743...	7.213997701085241	41	47.10000348580885	824189	20 16T11:15:32.324
25	scan eta 24.61146862028537 24.651468620285367 ...	7.214004328606605	41	47.200071196307526	824190	20 16T11:16:44.122
26	scan eta 24.61163383900715 24.65163383900715 0...	7.213997701085241	41	47.30013890584552	824191	20 16T11:17:55.254
27	scan eta 24.61179898027203 24.65179898027203 0...	7.21400211943141	41	47.400206615758165	824192	20 16T11:19:06.402
28	scan eta 24.611964043572055 24.651964043572054...	7.2139999102576216	41	47.50027615785685	824193	20 16T11:20:16.856
29	scan eta 24.612129028407796 24.652129028407796...	7.2139999102576216	41	47.60034386218229	824194	20 16T11:21:26.041
30	scan eta 24.612293934275765 24.652293934275765...	7.21400211943141	41	47.70043564078862	824195	20 16T11:22:33.764
31	scan eta 24.61245876067313 24.65245876067313 0...	7.213997701085241	41	47.79948294993318	824196	20 16T11:23:40.431
32	scan eta 24.612623507097627 24.652623507097626...	7.2139999102576216	41	47.89953254882811	824197	20 16T11:24:48.34
33	scan eta 24.612788173048262 24.65278817304826 ...	7.213997701085241	41	47.99962387427574	824198	20 16T11:25:55.441
34	scan eta 24.604178478032534 24.644178478032533...	7.215000810150979	41	44.999712092410576	824199	20 16T11:27:07.345
35	scan eta 24.604345273133358 24.644345273133357...	7.215000810150979	41	45.09977247154727	824200	20 16T11:28:14.746
36	scan eta 24.604512001897117 24.644512001897116...	7.215000810150979	41	45.19982550439328	824201	20 16T11:29:21.887

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
37	scan eta 24.604678663818692 24.64467866381869 ...	7.2150030199627215	41	45.29989870055302	824202	20 16T11:30:29.762
38	scan eta 24.604845258388625 24.644845258388624...	7.215005229775872	41	45.399927687167136	824203	20 16T11:31:36.345
39	scan eta 24.605011785100704 24.645011785100703...	7.215000810150979	41	45.50001027412195	824204	20 16T11:32:43.767
40	scan eta 24.605178243447067 24.645178243447067...	7.214996390531721	41	45.60007431384849	824205	20 16T11:33:51.05
41	scan eta 24.605344632920687 24.645344632920686...	7.2150030199627215	41	45.70012551120868	824206	20 16T11:34:59.602
42	scan eta 24.605510953013248 24.645510953013247...	7.2150030199627215	41	45.80016915712358	824207	20 16T11:36:06.989
43	scan eta 24.60567720322126 24.645677203221258 ...	7.215000810150979	41	45.900231365214	824208	20 16T11:37:14.459
44	scan eta 24.60584338303499 24.64584338303499 0...	7.215000810150979	41	46.00029356334321	824209	20 16T11:38:22.293
45	scan eta 24.606009491951138 24.646009491951137...	7.214996390531721	41	46.10038165771162	824210	20 16T11:39:28.809
46	scan eta 24.606175529461513 24.646175529461512...	7.214998600340644	41	46.20041794802641	824211	20 16T11:40:36.524
47	scan eta 24.606341495061134 24.646341495061133...	7.2150030199627215	41	46.29948200927915	824212	20 16T11:41:44.303
48	scan eta 24.606507388244214 24.646507388244213...	7.214998600340644	41	46.399570111888686	824213	20 16T11:42:51.665
49	scan eta 24.606673208506376 24.646673208506375...	7.215000810150979	41	46.49962681012936	824214	20 16T11:43:59.016
50	scan eta 24.606838955340724 24.646838955340723...	7.214998600340644	41	46.59967412154202	824215	20 16T11:45:06.632
51	scan eta 24.607004628243768 24.647004628243767...	7.215000810150979	41	46.69973813930795	824216	20 16T11:46:14.528
52	scan eta 24.60717022671118 24.64717022671118 0...	7.215000810150979	41	46.79980403140701	824217	20 16T11:47:22.287

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
53	scan eta 24.607335750237308 24.647335750237307...	7.2149941807242035	41	46.89986988465854	824218	20 16T11:48:29.711
54	scan eta 24.60750119831776 24.64750119831776 0...	7.215000810150979	41	46.99993577936886	824219	20 16T11:49:37.452
55	scan eta 24.607666570449748 24.647666570449747...	7.215007439590432	41	47.10002205370933	824220	20 16T11:50:44.668
56	scan eta 24.607831866129363 24.647831866129362...	7.215000810150979	41	47.20008793144333	824221	20 16T11:51:52.085
57	scan eta 24.607997084852155 24.647997084852154...	7.2150030199627215	41	47.30013890148707	824222	20 16T11:52:59.129
58	scan eta 24.608162226116026 24.648162226116025...	7.2150030199627215	41	47.40020661273416	824223	20 16T11:54:07.216
59	scan eta 24.60832728941706 24.648327289417058 ...	7.214996390531721	41	47.50027431985427	824224	20 16T11:55:14.45
60	scan eta 24.6084922742528 24.6484922742528 0.0...	7.215000810150979	41	47.60036792911532	824225	20 16T11:56:21.746
61	scan eta 24.608657180119774 24.648657180119773...	7.215000810150979	41	47.700448474980895	824226	20 16T11:57:29.921
62	scan eta 24.608822006518135 24.648822006518134...	7.2150030199627215	41	47.799505188479124	824227	20 16T11:58:37.909
63	scan eta 24.60898675294263 24.64898675294263 0...	7.214996390531721	41	47.899576571161475	824228	20 16T11:59:45.617
64	scan eta 24.609151418893266 24.649151418893265...	7.215005229775872	41	47.999623868452666	824229	20 16T12:00:53.879
65	scan eta 24.600542837498534 24.640542837498533...	7.215999788650632	41	44.999721266730525	824230	20 16T12:02:05.422
66	scan eta 24.600709632598363 24.640709632598362...	7.215999788650632	41	45.0997724735901	824231	20 16T12:03:12.684
67	scan eta 24.600876361363117 24.640876361363116...	7.215999788650632	41	45.1998087837955	824232	20 16T12:04:20.39

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
68	scan eta 24.601043023284692 24.64104302328469 ...	7.215999788650632	41	45.29986915326251	824233	16T12:05:27.635
69	scan eta 24.601209617854625 24.641209617854624...	7.21599757820348	41	45.39995174092376	824234	16T12:06:35.251
70	scan eta 24.601376144566704 24.641376144566703...	7.216001999099193	41	45.499988051689634	824235	16T12:07:42.109
71	scan eta 24.60154260291206 24.641542602912057 ...	7.216001999099193	41	45.60004842134403	824236	16T12:08:48.842
72	scan eta 24.601708992385692 24.64170899238569 ...	7.215999788650632	41	45.7001310072575	824237	16T12:09:56.585
73	scan eta 24.601875312479248 24.641875312479247...	7.21599757820348	41	45.800195045019535	824238	16T12:11:03.871
74	scan eta 24.60204156268625 24.64204156268625 0...	7.21600420954916	41	45.90023136508141	824239	16T12:12:11.955
75	scan eta 24.60220774249998 24.64220774249998 0...	7.215999788650632	41	46.00031579234314	824240	16T12:13:19.31
76	scan eta 24.602373851416143 24.642373851416142...	7.216001999099193	41	46.10037981595058	824241	16T12:14:27.372
77	scan eta 24.60253988892652 24.642539888926517 ...	7.215999788650632	41	46.20044019697684	824242	16T12:15:34.795
78	scan eta 24.60270585452614 24.642705854526138 ...	7.215999788650632	41	46.29948201218925	824243	16T12:16:42.694
79	scan eta 24.602871747709205 24.642871747709204...	7.215999788650632	41	46.39957377210815	824244	16T12:17:50.548
80	scan eta 24.603037567971366 24.643037567971366...	7.216001999099193	41	46.499637813726004	824245	16T12:18:58
81	scan eta 24.603203314806724 24.643203314806723...	7.21599757820348	41	46.59967433242971	824246	16T12:20:08.388
82	scan eta 24.603368987708773 24.643368987708772...	7.215999788650632	41	46.6997585564074	824247	16T12:21:15.703

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
83	scan eta 24.60353458617617 24.64353458617617 0...	7.21599757820348	41	46.79980403745094	824248	20 16T12:22:23.395
84	scan eta 24.6037001097023 24.643700109702298 0...	7.21599757820348	41	46.899892140162216	824249	20 16T12:23:30.529
85	scan eta 24.60386555778376 24.64386555778376 0...	7.21599757820348	41	46.99993761548816	824250	20 16T12:24:38.515
86	scan eta 24.604030929915748 24.644030929915747...	7.215999788650632	41	47.100023901504365	824251	20 16T12:25:46.999
87	scan eta 24.604196225595363 24.644196225595362...	7.215999788650632	41	47.20009893298182	824252	20 16T12:26:54.107
88	scan eta 24.604361444318155 24.644361444318154...	7.215999788650632	41	47.3001389000049	824253	20 16T12:28:01.696
89	scan eta 24.604526585582025 24.644526585582025...	7.21599757820348	41	47.40022701632049	824254	20 16T12:29:10.55
90	scan eta 24.60469164888205 24.64469164888205 0...	7.216001999099193	41	47.500274321518724	824255	20 16T12:30:19.338
91	scan eta 24.6048566337188 24.6448566337188 0.0...	7.216001999099193	41	47.60036427248053	824256	20 16T12:31:26.92
92	scan eta 24.605021539585774 24.645021539585773...	7.215999788650632	41	47.700413403630506	824257	20 16T12:32:34.392
93	scan eta 24.605186365983126 24.645186365983125...	7.21600420954916	41	47.799482949008436	824258	20 16T12:33:41.498
94	scan eta 24.60535111240762 24.64535111240762 0...	7.215999788650632	41	47.899582064400995	824259	20 16T12:34:48.618
95	scan eta 24.60551577835827 24.64551577835827 0...	7.21600420954916	41	47.99964611001969	824260	20 16T12:35:56.679
96	scan eta 24.596908310053532 24.63690831005353 ...	7.21700126613868	41	44.99971577147202	824261	20 16T12:37:08.041
97	scan eta 24.597075105153362 24.63707510515336 ...	7.216999055053031	41	45.09977246797807	824262	20 16T12:38:15.622

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
98	scan eta 24.597241833918115 24.637241833918115...	7.21700126613868	41	45.19981061986508	824263	20 16T12:39:23.346
99	scan eta 24.59740849583969 24.63740849583969 0...	7.21700126613868	41	45.29986915330793	824264	20 16T12:40:30.852
100	scan eta 24.597575090409624 24.637575090409623...	7.216999055053031	41	45.39992768877433	824265	20 16T12:41:38.562
101	scan eta 24.597741617121702 24.6377416171217 0...	7.216996843968793	41	45.500013944174896	824266	20 16T12:42:46.018
102	scan eta 24.597908075467057 24.637908075467056...	7.216996843968793	41	45.60004841968808	824267	20 16T12:43:54.002
103	scan eta 24.59807446494069 24.63807446494069 0...	7.21700126613868	41	45.70013101661061	824268	20 16T12:45:01.883
104	scan eta 24.598240785034246 24.638240785034245...	7.216999055053031	41	45.80019321419007	824269	20 16T12:46:09.457
105	scan eta 24.598407035241248 24.638407035241247...	7.216996843968793	41	45.90023133854209	824270	20 16T12:47:17.323
106	scan eta 24.59857321505599 24.638573215055988 ...	7.21700126613868	41	46.00029172756155	824271	20 16T12:48:24.84
107	scan eta 24.59873932397114 24.63873932397114 0...	7.216999055053031	41	46.100355768185864	824272	20 16T12:49:32.499
108	scan eta 24.598905361481517 24.638905361481516...	7.216999055053031	41	46.200445700864606	824273	20 16T12:50:39.7
109	scan eta 24.599071327081138 24.639071327081137...	7.21700126613868	41	46.299500571636244	824274	20 16T12:51:46.676
110	scan eta 24.599237220264204 24.639237220264203...	7.217003477225739	41	46.399562773884846	824275	20 16T12:52:54.167
111	scan eta 24.59940304052638 24.63940304052638 0...	7.216999055053031	41	46.49961008645596	824276	20 16T12:54:01.585
112	scan eta 24.599568787361722 24.63956878736172 ...	7.216994632885961	41	46.59967412759814	824277	20 16T12:55:09.261

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
113	scan eta 24.599734460264767 24.639734460264766...	7.216999055053031	41	46.69976406224221	824278	20 16T12:56:16.88
114	scan eta 24.59990005873117 24.63990005873117 0...	7.216999055053031	41	46.79980403175962	824279	20 16T12:57:23.757
115	scan eta 24.60006558225731 24.64006558225731 0...	7.217003477225739	41	46.899869911981796	824280	20 16T12:58:31.728
116	scan eta 24.600231030338772 24.64023103033877 ...	7.216999055053031	41	46.99995984622478	824281	20 16T12:59:39.248
117	scan eta 24.600396402470746 24.640396402470746...	7.216999055053031	41	47.10000348762369	824282	20 16T13:00:46.942
118	scan eta 24.60056169815036 24.64056169815036 0...	7.216999055053031	41	47.20009526858511	824283	20 16T13:01:54.73
119	scan eta 24.600726916873153 24.640726916873152...	7.216999055053031	41	47.30012445393615	824284	20 16T13:03:02.289
120	scan eta 24.600892058137024 24.640892058137023...	7.216996843968793	41	47.40020661579177	824285	20 16T13:04:09.826
121	scan eta 24.601057121438057 24.641057121438056...	7.217003477225739	41	47.500274318411414	824286	20 16T13:05:17.943
122	scan eta 24.6012221062738 24.641222106273798 0...	7.216999055053031	41	47.600343863572746	824287	20 16T13:06:26.282
123	scan eta 24.601387012140773 24.641387012140772...	7.216999055053031	41	47.7004134064005	824288	20 16T13:07:35.169
124	scan eta 24.601551838538125 24.641551838538124...	7.217003477225739	41	47.799482949967164	824289	20 16T13:08:43.779
125	scan eta 24.60171658496262 24.64171658496262 0...	7.216999055053031	41	47.899578403297376	824290	20 16T13:09:51.586
126	scan eta 24.601881250914264 24.641881250914263...	7.217003477225739	41	47.99964978164529	824291	20 16T13:11:00.961
127	scan eta 24.59327489516853 24.63327489516853 0...	7.217998609480908	41	44.9996935550311	824292	20 16T13:12:14.052

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
128	scan eta 24.59344169026836 24.63344169026836 0...	7.218003032928338	41	45.09975025347606	824293	20 16T13:13:22.307
129	scan eta 24.593608419033128 24.633608419033127...	7.218003032928338	41	45.19980878784388	824294	20 16T13:14:30.348
130	scan eta 24.59377508095368 24.63377508095368 0...	7.218000821203918	41	45.299867296877764	824295	20 16T13:15:38.496
131	scan eta 24.593941675524622 24.63394167552462 ...	7.218000821203918	41	45.39995174691517	824296	20 16T13:16:47.717
132	scan eta 24.5941082022367 24.6341082022367 0.0...	7.218003032928338	41	45.49998805068554	824297	20 16T13:17:56.399
133	scan eta 24.59427466058207 24.63427466058207 0...	7.218003032928338	41	45.60007064162146	824298	20 16T13:19:05.699
134	scan eta 24.59444105005569 24.63444105005569 0...	7.217998609480908	41	45.70010878820344	824299	20 16T13:20:15.273
135	scan eta 24.594607370149244 24.634607370149244...	7.218000821203918	41	45.80020054592996	824300	20 16T13:21:22.999
136	scan eta 24.594773620356246 24.634773620356246...	7.218003032928338	41	45.900231358051	824301	20 16T13:22:32.429
137	scan eta 24.59493980016998 24.634939800169978 ...	7.218000821203918	41	46.00032679663269	824302	20 16T13:23:42.986
138	scan eta 24.59510590908614 24.63510590908614 0...	7.218000821203918	41	46.10035576538758	824303	20 16T13:24:53.321
139	scan eta 24.595271946596515 24.635271946596514...	7.217998609480908	41	46.20039618187619	824304	20 16T13:26:04.268
140	scan eta 24.595437912196136 24.635437912196135...	7.218000821203918	41	46.29948017890737	824305	20 16T13:27:14.831
141	scan eta 24.595603805379216 24.635603805379215...	7.218000821203918	41	46.399575605967044	824306	20 16T13:28:25.862
142	scan eta 24.595769625641378 24.635769625641377...	7.218000821203918	41	46.49960822910092	824307	20 16T13:29:36.433

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
143	24.59593537247672 24.63593537247672 0...	7.217998609480908	41	46.59967412168391	824308	20 16T13:30:46.984
	scan eta					
144	24.59610104537877 24.63610104537877 0...	7.217998609480908	41	46.699738164934985	824309	20 16T13:31:58.18
	scan eta					
145	24.596266643846167 24.636266643846167...	7.218003032928338	41	46.799804032873546	824310	20 16T13:33:08.798
	scan eta					
146	24.59643216737231 24.63643216737231 0...	7.218000821203918	41	46.899869884360086	824311	20 16T13:34:20.254
	scan eta					
147	24.59659761545377 24.63659761545377 0...	7.218000821203918	41	46.999935757792834	824312	20 16T13:35:31.052
	scan eta					
148	24.596762987585745 24.636762987585744...	7.218000821203918	41	47.100031223748175	824313	20 16T13:36:41.226
	scan eta					
149	24.596928283265374 24.636928283265373...	7.218003032928338	41	47.20009709641809	824314	20 16T13:37:52.571
	scan eta					
150	24.59709350198815 24.63709350198815 0...	7.218000821203918	41	47.30011712156251	824315	20 16T13:39:04.165
	scan eta					
151	24.597258643252022 24.63725864325202 ...	7.218000821203918	41	47.400232516554155	824316	20 16T13:40:15.287
	scan eta					
152	24.59742370655206 24.63742370655206 0...	7.218003032928338	41	47.50030022437323	824317	20 16T13:41:25.596
	scan eta					
153	24.597588691388797 24.637588691388796...	7.218000821203918	41	47.60032758185366	824318	20 16T13:42:36.404
	scan eta					
154	24.59775359725577 24.63775359725577 0...	7.218000821203918	41	47.70041340981457	824319	20 16T13:43:48.525
	scan eta					
155	24.597918423653123 24.637918423653122...	7.218000821203918	41	47.79950335121911	824320	20 16T13:45:00.726
	scan eta					
156	24.59808317007762 24.638083170077618 ...	7.218000821203918	41	47.899554330145435	824321	20 16T13:46:14.044

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
157	scan eta 24.598247836028268 24.638247836028267...	7.218003032928338	41	47.9996442795084	824322	20 16T13:47:26.094
158	scan eta 24.589642592312526 24.629642592312525...	7.219000664417707	41	44.99969355667808	824323	20 16T13:48:42.472
159	scan eta 24.589809387412355 24.629809387412354...	7.2190028767797605	41	45.09976696721913	824324	20 16T13:49:54.048
160	scan eta 24.589976116177123 24.629976116177122...	7.2189984520570665	41	45.19983467819454	824325	20 16T13:51:03.649
161	scan eta 24.590142778098684 24.630142778098683...	7.219000664417707	41	45.29986915350413	824326	20 16T13:52:13.493
162	scan eta 24.59030937266863 24.63030937266863 0...	7.219000664417707	41	45.39994989974967	824327	20 16T13:53:20.568
163	scan eta 24.59047589938071 24.63047589938071 0...	7.219000664417707	41	45.50000844203151	824328	20 16T13:54:28.053
164	scan eta 24.590642357726065 24.630642357726064...	7.218996239697836	41	45.60007248087393	824329	20 16T13:55:34.795
165	scan eta 24.590808747199684 24.630808747199683...	7.2189984520570665	41	45.70013468478125	824330	20 16T13:56:42.106
166	scan eta 24.59097506729324 24.63097506729324 0...	7.219000664417707	41	45.8001691598057	824331	20 16T13:57:49.297
167	scan eta 24.591141317500256 24.631141317500255...	7.2190028767797605	41	45.90026825203478	824332	20 16T13:58:57.218
168	scan eta 24.591307497313988 24.631307497313987...	7.219000664417707	41	46.00029010410427	824333	20 16T14:00:07.108
169	scan eta 24.591473606230135 24.631473606230134...	7.219000664417707	41	46.100355766658296	824334	20 16T14:01:16.305
170	scan eta 24.59163964374051 24.63163964374051 0...	7.2190028767797605	41	46.20043653325729	824335	20 16T14:02:23.855
171	scan eta 24.59180560934013 24.63180560934013 0...	7.219000664417707	41	46.29950423943398	824336	20 16T14:03:31.755

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
172	scan eta 24.59197150252321 24.63197150252321 0...	7.219000664417707	41	46.39954421494107	824337	20 16T14:04:38.616
173	scan eta 24.592137322785373 24.632137322785372...	7.218996239697836	41	46.4996304755912	824338	20 16T14:05:45.846
174	scan eta 24.592303069620716 24.632303069620715...	7.2189984520570665	41	46.599690854473295	824339	20 16T14:06:52.927
175	scan eta 24.592468742523774 24.632468742523773...	7.2190028767797605	41	46.69975855758145	824340	20 16T14:08:01.4
176	scan eta 24.592634340990177 24.632634340990176...	7.218996239697836	41	46.79980403593759	824341	20 16T14:09:09.132
177	scan eta 24.592799864516305 24.632799864516304...	7.219000664417707	41	46.89986990731556	824342	20 16T14:10:16.719
178	scan eta 24.592965312597766 24.632965312597765...	7.2190028767797605	41	46.99995618245601	824343	20 16T14:11:24.061
179	scan eta 24.59313068472974 24.63313068472974 0...	7.219000664417707	41	47.100023887439804	824344	20 16T14:12:32.028
180	scan eta 24.59329598040937 24.63329598040937 0...	7.219000664417707	41	47.20007119967792	824345	20 16T14:13:39.25
181	scan eta 24.593461199132147 24.633461199132146...	7.2189984520570665	41	47.30015930495323	824346	20 16T14:14:46.592
182	scan eta 24.593626340396032 24.63362634039603 ...	7.219000664417707	41	47.400230678244625	824347	20 16T14:15:54.031
183	scan eta 24.59379140369705 24.63379140369705 0...	7.219000664417707	41	47.50025620607142	824348	20 16T14:17:02.368
184	scan eta 24.593956388532792 24.63395638853279 ...	7.2189984520570665	41	47.600378931978334	824349	20 16T14:18:10.914
185	scan eta 24.594121294399766 24.634121294399765...	7.218996239697836	41	47.70044298264826	824350	20 16T14:19:20.113
186	scan eta 24.594286120797133 24.63428612079713 ...	7.2190028767797605	41	47.799482950178835	824351	20 16T14:20:27.74

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
187	scan eta 24.594450867221628 24.634450867221627...	7.219000664417707	41	47.89957656230759	824352	20 16T14:21:35.584
188	scan eta 24.594615533173258 24.634615533173257...	7.219000664417707	41	47.99962570724973	824353	20 16T14:22:43.416
189	scan eta 24.586011400956533 24.626011400956532...	7.220000795902924	41	44.999693549726764	824354	20 16T14:23:54.745
190	scan eta 24.586178196057357 24.626178196057356...	7.219996369907242	41	45.0997520850044	824355	20 16T14:25:01.628
191	scan eta 24.586344924821116 24.626344924821115...	7.220000795902924	41	45.199831005206526	824356	20 16T14:26:08.965
192	scan eta 24.58651158674269 24.62651158674269 0...	7.219996369907242	41	45.29988953498323	824357	20 16T14:27:17.025
193	scan eta 24.586678181312625 24.626678181312624...	7.219998582904377	41	45.39992769208536	824358	20 16T14:28:24.713
194	scan eta 24.586844708024703 24.626844708024702...	7.219998582904377	41	45.50000476940809	824359	20 16T14:29:32.946
195	scan eta 24.587011166370058 24.627011166370057...	7.219998582904377	41	45.60002296328165	824360	20 16T14:30:40.445
196	scan eta 24.58717755584369 24.62717755584369 0...	7.220000795902924	41	45.700134671204346	824361	20 16T14:31:47.846
197	scan eta 24.587343875937247 24.627343875937246...	7.219998582904377	41	45.80016915696207	824362	20 16T14:32:56.489
198	scan eta 24.58751012614425 24.627510126144248 ...	7.22000522190425	41	45.900231360755626	824363	20 16T14:34:03.991
199	scan eta 24.58767630595899 24.62767630595899 0...	7.220000795902924	41	46.00031945226448	824364	20 16T14:35:11.763
200	scan eta 24.587842414874142 24.62784241487414 ...	7.220000795902924	41	46.100348643205976	824365	20 16T14:36:20.308
201	scan eta 24.588008452384518 24.628008452384517...	7.219998582904377	41	46.20043653476856	824366	20 16T14:37:27.674

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
202	24.58817441798414 24.628174417984138 ...	7.220000795902924	41	46.2994987357328	824367	20 16T14:38:35.152
	scan eta					
203	24.588340311167205 24.628340311167204...	7.220000795902924	41	46.39956644502394	824368	20 16T14:39:42.504
	scan eta					
204	24.58850613142938 24.62850613142938 0...	7.220000795902924	41	46.49960825456243	824369	20 16T14:40:50.558
	scan eta					
205	24.588671878264723 24.628671878264722...	7.220000795902924	41	46.599674126203496	824370	20 16T14:41:59.682
	scan eta					
206	24.588837551167767 24.628837551167766...	7.220000795902924	41	46.69973815934513	824371	20 16T14:43:07.835
	scan eta					
207	24.58900314963518 24.629003149635178 ...	7.220000795902924	41	46.79983726596541	824372	20 16T14:44:15.945
	scan eta					
208	24.589168673160312 24.62916867316031 ...	7.220000795902924	41	46.89989029919007	824373	20 16T14:45:23.44
	scan eta					
209	24.589334121241773 24.629334121241772...	7.220003008902882	41	46.99993575792521	824374	20 16T14:46:30.469
	scan eta					
210	24.589499493373747 24.629499493373746...	7.220000795902924	41	47.10000348932708	824375	20 16T14:47:37.723
	scan eta					
211	24.589664789053362 24.62966478905336 ...	7.220003008902882	41	47.20009526711282	824376	20 16T14:48:45.019
	scan eta					
212	24.589830007776154 24.629830007776153...	7.219998582904377	41	47.30016664238199	824377	20 16T14:49:51.92
	scan eta					
213	24.589995149040025 24.629995149040024...	7.220000795902924	41	47.400234352648006	824378	20 16T14:50:59.632
	scan eta					
214	24.590160212341058 24.630160212341057...	7.220000795902924	41	47.5003002291872	824379	20 16T14:52:06.547
	scan eta					
215	24.5903251971768 24.6303251971768 0.0...	7.220000795902924	41	47.60038076624846	824380	20 16T14:53:14.04
	scan eta					
216	24.590490103043773 24.630490103043773...	7.220000795902924	41	47.70041340677405	824381	20 16T14:54:21.672

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
217	scan eta 24.590654929441126 24.630654929441125...	7.220003008902882	41	47.79950885370467	824382	20 16T14:55:28.763
218	scan eta 24.59081967586663 24.63081967586663 0...	7.219996369907242	41	47.89955432845633	824383	20 16T14:56:36.577
219	scan eta 24.590984341817265 24.630984341817264...	7.220000795902924	41	47.99962387285577	824384	20 16T14:57:43.946
220	scan eta 24.582381320571525 24.622381320571524...	7.220999002145784	41	44.99968460824091	824385	20 16T14:58:56.278
221	scan eta 24.582548115671354 24.622548115671353...	7.220999002145784	41	45.09975045093401	824386	20 16T15:00:07.879
222	scan eta 24.582714844436122 24.62271484443612 ...	7.220999002145784	41	45.19983282989544	824387	20 16T15:01:16.891
223	scan eta 24.582881506357683 24.622881506357682...	7.2209967885104716	41	45.299885866972936	824388	20 16T15:02:23.296
224	scan eta 24.58304810092763 24.62304810092763 0...	7.2209967885104716	41	45.39990955967374	824389	20 16T15:03:30.31
225	scan eta 24.58321462763971 24.623214627639708 ...	7.22100342942064	41	45.50000477591446	824390	20 16T15:04:37.99
226	scan eta 24.583381085985064 24.623381085985063...	7.220999002145784	41	45.600046588122474	824391	20 16T15:05:45.411
227	scan eta 24.583547475458683 24.623547475458682...	7.221005643060187	41	45.70012734713912	824392	20 16T15:06:52.903
228	scan eta 24.583713795552253 24.623713795552252...	7.221001215782505	41	45.80016915686597	824393	20 16T15:08:00.348
229	scan eta 24.583880045759255 24.623880045759254...	7.221001215782505	41	45.90020957055107	824394	20 16T15:09:08.306
230	scan eta 24.584046225572987 24.624046225572986...	7.2209967885104716	41	46.00030844816589	824395	20 16T15:10:16.72
231	scan eta 24.584212334489134 24.624212334489133...	7.221001215782505	41	46.100355768012506	824396	20 16T15:11:24.431

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
232	scan eta 24.58437837199951 24.62437837199951 0...	7.221001215782505	41	46.20041797156279	824397	20 16T15:12:32.184
233	scan eta 24.58454433759913 24.62454433759913 0...	7.2209967885104716	41	46.299480178939874	824398	20 16T15:13:39.322
234	scan eta 24.58471023078221 24.62471023078221 0...	7.220999002145784	41	46.399570108448174	824399	20 16T15:14:46.547
235	scan eta 24.584876051044372 24.62487605104437 ...	7.2209967885104716	41	46.49962865205692	824400	20 16T15:15:53.865
236	scan eta 24.585041797879715 24.625041797879714...	7.220999002145784	41	46.59969636302816	824401	20 16T15:17:02.074
237	scan eta 24.585207470781764 24.625207470781763...	7.221001215782505	41	46.69975672633634	824402	20 16T15:18:09.917
238	scan eta 24.585373069249176 24.625373069249175...	7.221001215782505	41	46.79982076077893	824403	20 16T15:19:17.321
239	scan eta 24.585538592775304 24.625538592775303...	7.220994574876574	41	46.8998939722484	824404	20 16T15:20:25.238
240	scan eta 24.585704040856765 24.625704040856764...	7.2209967885104716	41	46.999959842357875	824405	20 16T15:21:32.751
241	scan eta 24.58586941298874 24.625869412988738 ...	7.220992361244088	41	47.100029389712184	824406	20 16T15:22:41.05
242	scan eta 24.586034708668368 24.626034708668367...	7.221001215782505	41	47.20007119973768	824407	20 16T15:23:49.035
243	scan eta 24.586199927391146 24.626199927391145...	7.220999002145784	41	47.30013887974888	824408	20 16T15:24:56.823
244	scan eta 24.58636506865503 24.62636506865503 0...	7.220999002145784	41	47.40023067784119	824409	20 16T15:26:04.878
245	scan eta 24.58653013195605 24.62653013195605 0...	7.2209967885104716	41	47.50027432454379	824410	20 16T15:27:13.633
246	scan eta 24.58669511679179 24.62669511679179 0...	7.2209967885104716	41	47.60034386248691	824411	20 16T15:28:22.258

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
247	scan eta 24.586860022658765 24.626860022658764...	7.2209967885104716	41	47.700437480853104	824412	20 16T15:29:33.375
248	scan eta 24.58702484905613 24.62702484905613 0...	7.220999002145784	41	47.799482953424814	824413	20 16T15:30:44.42
249	scan eta 24.587189595480627 24.627189595480626...	7.220999002145784	41	47.899554326984976	824414	20 16T15:31:55.774
250	scan eta 24.587354261431262 24.62735426143126 ...	7.220999002145784	41	47.999640601342406	824415	20 16T15:33:07.328
251	scan eta 24.578752350627536 24.618752350627535...	7.221999709904296	41	44.99969355096611	824416	20 16T15:34:23.225
252	scan eta 24.57891914572836 24.61891914572836 0...	7.221999709904296	41	45.099752083734586	824417	20 16T15:35:33.967
253	scan eta 24.57908587449212 24.619085874492118 ...	7.222001924179467	41	45.19981061809648	824418	20 16T15:36:44.348
254	scan eta 24.57925253641368 24.61925253641368 0...	7.22200413845605	41	45.299867318869374	824419	20 16T15:37:55.216
255	scan eta 24.579419130983627 24.619419130983626...	7.222006352734048	41	45.399927681921	824420	20 16T15:39:05.928
256	scan eta 24.579585657695706 24.619585657695705...	7.221999709904296	41	45.50000843733113	824421	20 16T15:40:17.773
257	scan eta 24.57975211604207 24.61975211604207 0...	7.221997495630536	41	45.60006330804817	824422	20 16T15:41:28.756
258	scan eta 24.57991850551569 24.619918505515688 ...	7.221997495630536	41	45.70013101518822	824423	20 16T15:42:39.453
259	scan eta 24.58008482560825 24.62008482560825 0...	7.221999709904296	41	45.80018588036915	824424	20 16T15:43:49.663
260	scan eta 24.580251075816246 24.620251075816245...	7.22199528135819	41	45.90023136074214	824425	20 16T15:45:00.325

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
261	scan eta 24.58041725562998 24.62041725562997 ...	7.221999709904296	41	46.00031945537963	824426	20 16T15:46:10.098
262	scan eta 24.58058336454614 24.62058336454614 0...	7.221999709904296	41	46.10037798996387	824427	20 16T15:47:20.664
263	scan eta 24.580749402056515 24.620749402056514...	7.221999709904296	41	46.20044019918104	824428	20 16T15:48:31.004
264	scan eta 24.580915367656136 24.620915367656135...	7.221999709904296	41	46.29950423642289	824429	20 16T15:49:42.22
265	scan eta 24.581081260839216 24.621081260839215...	7.221997495630536	41	46.399581108617376	824430	20 16T15:50:53.411
266	scan eta 24.581247081101377 24.621247081101377...	7.221997495630536	41	46.49963232066402	824431	20 16T15:52:04.359
267	scan eta 24.581412827935726 24.621412827935725...	7.221999709904296	41	46.599674123117566	824432	20 16T15:53:14.624
268	scan eta 24.58157850083877 24.62157850083877 0...	7.221997495630536	41	46.69973816197138	824433	20 16T15:54:25.936
269	scan eta 24.581744099306167 24.621744099306166...	7.221999709904296	41	46.799828090208365	824434	20 16T15:55:37.297
270	scan eta 24.58190962283231 24.62190962283231 0...	7.221997495630536	41	46.89986990878874	824435	20 16T15:56:47.801
271	scan eta 24.58207507091276 24.62207507091276 0...	7.222001924179467	41	46.99995801206542	824436	20 16T15:57:59.142
272	scan eta 24.582240443044736 24.622240443044735...	7.221999709904296	41	47.10000348886754	824437	20 16T15:59:09.297
273	scan eta 24.582405738724365 24.622405738724364...	7.221999709904296	41	47.20007120161281	824438	20 16T16:00:19.501
274	scan eta 24.582570957447157 24.622570957447156...	7.221999709904296	41	47.30013890309631	824439	20 16T16:01:30.281
275	scan eta 24.582736098711027 24.622736098711027...	7.221999709904296	41	47.40022884384201	824440	20 16T16:02:41.262

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
276	scan eta 24.58290116201206 24.62290116201206 0...	7.222001924179467	41	47.50027614877992	824441	20 16T16:03:52.404
277	scan eta 24.583066146847788 24.623066146847787...	7.221999709904296	41	47.60037160134422	824442	20 16T16:05:03.107
278	scan eta 24.583231052714762 24.62323105271476 ...	7.221999709904296	41	47.700437476243984	824443	20 16T16:06:14.052
279	scan eta 24.583395879113123 24.623395879113122...	7.221999709904296	41	47.799482954878286	824444	20 16T16:07:25.203
280	scan eta 24.58356062553762 24.623560625537618 ...	7.221999709904296	41	47.89955433209386	824445	20 16T16:08:36.829
281	scan eta 24.583725291488268 24.623725291488267...	7.221999709904296	41	47.99964794315259	824446	20 16T16:09:48.097
282	scan eta 24.575124490597528 24.615124490597527...	7.223000706302995	41	44.999706601957215	824447	20 16T16:11:03.38
283	scan eta 24.575291285697357 24.615291285697356...	7.223002921216889	41	45.099750254682604	824448	20 16T16:12:13.708
284	scan eta 24.575458014462125 24.615458014462124...	7.223005136132193	41	45.199808782749756	824449	20 16T16:13:25.461
285	scan eta 24.575624676383686 24.615624676383685...	7.223002921216889	41	45.29985835712298	824450	20 16T16:14:36.301
286	scan eta 24.57579127095362 24.61579127095362 0...	7.223007351048913	41	45.39995724523536	824451	20 16T16:15:46.858
287	scan eta 24.575957797665698 24.615957797665697...	7.222998491390517	41	45.499988050634165	824452	20 16T16:16:57.86
288	scan eta 24.576124256011067 24.616124256011066...	7.222996276479451	41	45.60004842411507	824453	20 16T16:18:09.028
289	scan eta 24.576290645484686 24.616290645484685...	7.223000706302995	41	45.700127350599175	824454	20 16T16:19:20.71
290	scan eta 24.57645696557824 24.61645696557824 0...	7.223000706302995	41	45.800184045320385	824455	20 16T16:20:31.157

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
291	scan eta 24.576623215785258 24.616623215785257...	7.223002921216889	41	45.90024808520469	824456	20 16T16:21:41.59
292	scan eta 24.576789395599985 24.616789395599984...	7.223002921216889	41	46.00031212680711	824457	20 16T16:22:51.328
293	scan eta 24.576955504515137 24.616955504515136...	7.223002921216889	41	46.10038165600916	824458	20 16T16:23:59.597
294	scan eta 24.577121542025512 24.61712154202551 ...	7.223000706302995	41	46.20044203301931	824459	20 16T16:25:06.688
295	scan eta 24.577287507625133 24.617287507625132...	7.223002921216889	41	46.29948201241147	824460	20 16T16:26:14.382
296	scan eta 24.577453400808214 24.617453400808213...	7.222996276479451	41	46.399544214913945	824461	20 16T16:27:22.369
297	scan eta 24.577619221070375 24.617619221070374...	7.223002921216889	41	46.49963598174115	824462	20 16T16:28:29.375
298	scan eta 24.577784967905718 24.617784967905717...	7.223000706302995	41	46.5996741242633	824463	20 16T16:29:36.395
299	scan eta 24.577950640808762 24.61795064080876 ...	7.223000706302995	41	46.699762220167145	824464	20 16T16:30:43.282
300	scan eta 24.57811623927518 24.618116239275178 ...	7.223000706302995	41	46.79980401167305	824465	20 16T16:31:50.388
301	scan eta 24.578281762801307 24.618281762801306...	7.223000706302995	41	46.89986990861648	824466	20 16T16:32:57.595
302	scan eta 24.578447210882768 24.618447210882767...	7.223000706302995	41	46.99996168461982	824467	20 16T16:34:05.708
303	scan eta 24.578612583014742 24.61861258301474 ...	7.223002921216889	41	47.10002205888373	824468	20 16T16:35:13.407
304	scan eta 24.57877787869437 24.61877787869437 0...	7.223000706302995	41	47.20007119518049	824469	20 16T16:36:21.256
305	scan eta 24.57894309741715 24.618943097417148 ...	7.222996276479451	41	47.30013887966144	824470	20 16T16:37:29.215
306	scan eta 24.579108238681034 24.619108238681033...	7.223002921216889	41	47.40020661597309	824471	20 16T16:38:36.335

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
307	scan eta 24.579273301982052 24.61927330198205 ...	7.223000706302995	41	47.50027432310211	824472	20 16T16:39:43.715
308	scan eta 24.579438286817794 24.619438286817793...	7.223002921216889	41	47.60036427131342	824473	20 16T16:40:51.616
309	scan eta 24.57960319268477 24.619603192684767 ...	7.223000706302995	41	47.70041340386211	824474	20 16T16:42:00.445
310	scan eta 24.579768019082135 24.619768019082134...	7.223000706302995	41	47.79951436292447	824475	20 16T16:43:08.056
311	scan eta 24.579932765507625 24.619932765507624...	7.223000706302995	41	47.89953071634811	824476	20 16T16:44:16.325
312	scan eta 24.58009743145826 24.62009743145826 0...	7.223000706302995	41	47.99962570951067	824477	20 16T16:45:23.735
313	scan eta 24.571497739951536 24.611497739951535...	7.223999775913565	41	44.99969355541055	824478	20 16T16:46:35.776
314	scan eta 24.57166453505236 24.61166453505236 0...	7.224001991465036	41	45.09977614215036	824479	20 16T16:47:44.549
315	scan eta 24.57183126381612 24.611831263816118 ...	7.224001991465036	41	45.1998383364716	824480	20 16T16:48:52.846
316	scan eta 24.57199792573768 24.61199792573768 0...	7.224006422572222	41	45.299900544684974	824481	20 16T16:50:00.769
317	scan eta 24.572164520308622 24.61216452030862 ...	7.223999775913565	41	45.39990589255572	824482	20 16T16:51:08.394
318	scan eta 24.5723310470207 24.6123310470207 0.0...	7.223999775913565	41	45.499988059557204	824483	20 16T16:52:16.228
319	scan eta 24.57249750536607 24.61249750536607 0...	7.224001991465036	41	45.60006697583932	824484	20 16T16:53:23.434
320	scan eta 24.57266389483969 24.612663894839688 ...	7.223997560363506	41	45.70010879243288	824485	20 16T16:54:31.332

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
321	scan eta 24.57283021493225 24.61283021493225 0...	7.224001991465036	41	45.800169158078866	824486	20 16T16:55:38.995
322	scan eta 24.572996465140246 24.612996465140245...	7.223999775913565	41	45.90025724493822	824487	20 16T16:56:47.47
323	scan eta 24.573162644953978 24.613162644953977...	7.223997560363506	41	46.00029173162436	824488	20 16T16:57:56.055
324	scan eta 24.57332875387014 24.61332875387014 0...	7.224001991465036	41	46.10035577139913	824489	20 16T16:59:03.96
325	scan eta 24.573494791380515 24.613494791380514...	7.223999775913565	41	46.200416345635574	824490	20 16T17:00:11.775
326	scan eta 24.573660756980136 24.613660756980135...	7.223999775913565	41	46.29948017886737	824491	20 16T17:01:19.855
327	scan eta 24.573826650163216 24.613826650163215...	7.224001991465036	41	46.39956460539185	824492	20 16T17:02:27.916
328	scan eta 24.573992470425377 24.613992470425377...	7.223999775913565	41	46.499608252640904	824493	20 16T17:03:35.535
329	scan eta 24.57415821726072 24.61415821726072 0...	7.223999775913565	41	46.59969085081762	824494	20 16T17:04:43.551
330	scan eta 24.57432389016277 24.61432389016277 0...	7.223997560363506	41	46.69976405787438	824495	20 16T17:05:51.482
331	scan eta 24.574489488630167 24.614489488630166...	7.224001991465036	41	46.7998317672957	824496	20 16T17:06:58.567
332	scan eta 24.57465501215631 24.61465501215631 0...	7.223999775913565	41	46.89986991040114	824497	20 16T17:08:07.104
333	scan eta 24.57482046023676 24.61482046023676 0...	7.223999775913565	41	46.99995802111309	824498	20 16T17:09:15.171
334	scan eta 24.574985832369745 24.614985832369744...	7.223997560363506	41	47.100020214208385	824499	20 16T17:10:23.792
335	scan eta 24.575151128049374 24.615151128049373...	7.224001991465036	41	47.20009709730189	824500	20 16T17:11:31.092

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
336	scan eta 24.57531634677215 24.61531634677215 0...	7.223999775913565	41	47.300138904727916	824501	20 16T17:12:39.179
337	scan eta 24.575481488036022 24.61548148803602 ...	7.223997560363506	41	47.40018666383508	824502	20 16T17:13:46.348
338	scan eta 24.57564655133606 24.61564655133606 0...	7.223997560363506	41	47.500296559876574	824503	20 16T17:14:53.725
339	scan eta 24.575811536172797 24.615811536172796...	7.224001991465036	41	47.60037343106149	824504	20 16T17:16:01.637
340	scan eta 24.57597644203977 24.61597644203977 0...	7.223999775913565	41	47.70043564102678	824505	20 16T17:17:09.189
341	scan eta 24.576141268437137 24.616141268437136...	7.223999775913565	41	47.799482953348985	824506	20 16T17:18:16.942
342	scan eta 24.57630601486162 24.616306014861618 ...	7.223999775913565	41	47.89957840350178	824507	20 16T17:19:23.944
343	scan eta 24.576470680812267 24.616470680812267...	7.223993129267633	41	47.99964244249338	824508	20 16T17:20:31.731
344	scan eta 24.56787209816353 24.60787209816353 0...	7.2250035655136395	41	44.99969355100284	824509	20 16T17:21:43.582
345	scan eta 24.568038893264355 24.608038893264354...	7.225001349322904	41	45.099777973676545	824510	20 16T17:22:50.659
346	scan eta 24.568205622028128 24.608205622028127...	7.224999133133579	41	45.19980878967558	824511	20 16T17:23:58.032
347	scan eta 24.56837228394969 24.608372283949688 ...	7.2249969169456705	41	45.299869157897575	824512	20 16T17:25:05.229
348	scan eta 24.56853887851962 24.60853887851962 0...	7.224999133133579	41	45.39992768872358	824513	20 16T17:26:12.723
349	scan eta 24.5687054052317 24.6087054052317 0.0...	7.224999133133579	41	45.50001394059718	824514	20 16T17:27:19.906

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
350	scan eta 24.568871863578064 24.608871863578063...	7.225001349322904	41	45.600081648283734	824515	20 16T17:28:27
351	scan eta 24.569038253051684 24.609038253051683...	7.224999133133579	41	45.70013101079531	824516	20 16T17:29:34.691
352	scan eta 24.569204573144244 24.609204573144243...	7.2249969169456705	41	45.80019320880627	824517	20 16T17:30:42.06
353	scan eta 24.569370823352255 24.609370823352254...	7.2250035655136395	41	45.90025541827292	824518	20 16T17:31:49.986
354	scan eta 24.569537003165987 24.609537003165986...	7.225001349322904	41	46.000291733110096	824519	20 16T17:32:58.051
355	scan eta 24.569703112082134 24.609703112082133...	7.225001349322904	41	46.10035576943078	824520	20 16T17:34:06.519
356	scan eta 24.56986914959251 24.60986914959251 0...	7.225001349322904	41	46.20044202648759	824521	20 16T17:35:13.969
357	scan eta 24.57003511519213 24.61003511519213 0...	7.225001349322904	41	46.29950607454366	824522	20 16T17:36:23.101
358	scan eta 24.57020100837521 24.61020100837521 0...	7.224999133133579	41	46.399562772925904	824523	20 16T17:37:30.784
359	scan eta 24.570366828637372 24.61036682863737 ...	7.224999133133579	41	46.4996082545872	824524	20 16T17:38:38.946
360	scan eta 24.57053257547172 24.61053257547172 0...	7.224999133133579	41	46.59970002713328	824525	20 16T17:39:46.634
361	scan eta 24.570698248374764 24.610698248374764...	7.2249969169456705	41	46.69973815937003	824526	20 16T17:40:54.324
362	scan eta 24.570863846842176 24.610863846842175...	7.224999133133579	41	46.799804039212404	824527	20 16T17:42:02.189
363	scan eta 24.571029370368304 24.611029370368303...	7.224999133133579	41	46.89986991015648	824528	20 16T17:43:10.966
364	scan eta 24.57119481844877 24.61119481844877 0...	7.225001349322904	41	46.999961684839576	824529	20 16T17:44:18.807

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
365	scan eta 24.571360190580744 24.611360190580744...	7.224999133133579	41	47.1000202227237	824530	20 16T17:45:26.859
366	scan eta 24.571525486260374 24.611525486260373...	7.2249969169456705	41	47.200071194946794	824531	20 16T17:46:35.049
367	scan eta 24.57169070498315 24.61169070498315 0...	7.224999133133579	41	47.300161129944144	824532	20 16T17:47:43.347
368	scan eta 24.571855846247022 24.61185584624702 ...	7.2249969169456705	41	47.40023067471326	824533	20 16T17:48:51.061
369	scan eta 24.572020909548055 24.612020909548054...	7.224999133133579	41	47.50029838670684	824534	20 16T17:49:58.753
370	scan eta 24.572185894383797 24.612185894383796...	7.225001349322904	41	47.60036792896513	824535	20 16T17:51:07.958
371	scan eta 24.57235080025077 24.61235080025077 0...	7.224999133133579	41	47.700446639782236	824536	20 16T17:52:16.562
372	scan eta 24.572515626649132 24.61251562664913 ...	7.2249969169456705	41	47.79948295309762	824537	20 16T17:53:25.049
373	scan eta 24.572680373073627 24.612680373073626...	7.225001349322904	41	47.89955432848215	824538	20 16T17:54:33.034
374	scan eta 24.572845039024262 24.61284503902426 ...	7.225001349322904	41	47.99962387425501	824539	20 16T17:55:40.272
375	scan eta 24.564247564704527 24.604247564704526...	7.22600099491296	41	44.99971944271289	824540	20 16T17:56:51.644
376	scan eta 24.56441435980535 24.60441435980535 0...	7.226003211741823	41	45.09977429615753	824541	20 16T17:57:59.641
377	scan eta 24.564581088569124 24.604581088569123...	7.226003211741823	41	45.199825504631505	824542	20 16T17:59:08.855
378	scan eta 24.564747750490685 24.604747750490684...	7.226003211741823	41	45.29986731885015	824543	20 16T18:00:20.141
379	scan eta 24.564914345060618 24.604914345060617...	7.2259987780855175	41	45.39992768697497	824544	20 16T18:01:32.01
380	scan eta 24.565080871773706 24.605080871773705...	7.226005428572098	41	45.500010276565156	824545	20 16T18:02:43.221

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
381	scan eta 24.56524733011906 24.60524733011906 0...	7.22600099491296	41	45.60003579533031	824546	20 16T18:03:54.515
382	scan eta 24.565413719592694 24.605413719592693...	7.226003211741823	41	45.70013651179419	824547	20 16T18:05:05.738
383	scan eta 24.56558003968524 24.60558003968524 0...	7.226003211741823	41	45.800169162924654	824548	20 16T18:06:17.067
384	scan eta 24.56574628989325 24.60574628989325 0...	7.22600099491296	41	45.90023136372956	824549	20 16T18:07:28.168
385	scan eta 24.565912469706984 24.605912469706983...	7.226005428572098	41	46.00029173305254	824550	20 16T18:08:38.776
386	scan eta 24.566078578623145 24.606078578623144...	7.22600099491296	41	46.10035577110253	824551	20 16T18:09:50.175
387	scan eta 24.56624461613352 24.60624461613352 0...	7.22600099491296	41	46.20044018926965	824552	20 16T18:11:00.575
388	scan eta 24.566410581733127 24.606410581733126...	7.225996561259485	41	46.299480179004036	824553	20 16T18:12:11.451
389	scan eta 24.566576474916207 24.606576474916206...	7.2259987780855175	41	46.399544215063706	824554	20 16T18:13:22.444
390	scan eta 24.56674229517837 24.606742295178368 ...	7.226003211741823	41	46.49960824884183	824555	20 16T18:14:34.356
391	scan eta 24.566908042013726 24.606908042013725...	7.2259987780855175	41	46.59970369059507	824556	20 16T18:15:46.136
392	scan eta 24.567073714915775 24.607073714915774...	7.2259987780855175	41	46.69973816503281	824557	20 16T18:16:57.466
393	scan eta 24.567239313383173 24.60723931338317 ...	7.22600099491296	41	46.79980403915339	824558	20 16T18:18:08.638
394	scan eta 24.5674048369093 24.6074048369093 0.0...	7.22600099491296	41	46.89988846647416	824559	20 16T18:19:19.402
395	scan eta 24.567570284989767 24.607570284989766...	7.226003211741823	41	46.999959847489414	824560	20 16T18:20:30.665

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
396	scan eta 24.56773565712174 24.60773565712174 0...	7.2259987780855175	41	47.099989036571706	824561	20 16T18:21:40.358
397	scan eta 24.567900952802365 24.607900952802364...	7.22600099491296	41	47.2000711966745	824562	20 16T18:22:51.52
398	scan eta 24.568066171525157 24.608066171525156...	7.22600099491296	41	47.30015747239433	824563	20 16T18:24:03.839
399	scan eta 24.568231312789027 24.608231312789027...	7.22600099491296	41	47.40020660803565	824564	20 16T18:25:15.45
400	scan eta 24.56839637608905 24.60839637608905 0...	7.2259987780855175	41	47.500274296698855	824565	20 16T18:26:28.179
401	scan eta 24.568561360925788 24.608561360925787...	7.2259987780855175	41	47.60034386526739	824566	20 16T18:27:40.272
402	scan eta 24.568726266792762 24.60872626679276 ...	7.22600099491296	41	47.70041340084439	824567	20 16T18:28:51.806
403	scan eta 24.56889109319013 24.608891093190127 ...	7.226003211741823	41	47.79948316525896	824568	20 16T18:30:06.1
404	scan eta 24.569055839614624 24.609055839614623...	7.22600099491296	41	47.899572901757	824569	20 16T18:31:16.693
405	scan eta 24.56922050556526 24.609220505565258 ...	7.225996561259485	41	47.99962570280188	824570	20 16T18:32:28.176
406	scan eta 24.560624139048524 24.600624139048524...	7.227000928357758	41	44.99969355357207	824571	20 16T18:33:44.603
407	scan eta 24.560790934149363 24.600790934149362...	7.227003145825012	41	45.099752085091716	824572	20 16T18:34:55.709
408	scan eta 24.560957662913122 24.60095766291312 ...	7.226998710891918	41	45.19981062282184	824573	20 16T18:36:07.417
409	scan eta 24.561124324834683 24.601124324834682...	7.227003145825012	41	45.299887698056054	824574	20 16T18:37:18.222
410	scan eta 24.56129091940463 24.60129091940463 0...	7.227000928357758	41	45.39992769175028	824575	20 16T18:38:28.742

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
411	24.56145744611671 24.601457446116708 ...	7.227000928357758	41	45.50001945139071	824576	20 16T18:39:40.645
	scan eta					
412	24.561623904462063 24.601623904462063...	7.226996493427493	41	45.6000412947314	824577	20 16T18:40:52.285
	scan eta					
413	24.561790293935683 24.601790293935682...	7.227000928357758	41	45.70010879567901	824578	20 16T18:42:03.661
	scan eta					
414	24.561956614029253 24.601956614029252...	7.227000928357758	41	45.80016916133327	824579	20 16T18:43:15.259
	scan eta					
415	24.56212286423725 24.60212286423725 0...	7.227000928357758	41	45.90025725590256	824580	20 16T18:44:26.802
	scan eta					
416	24.56228904405098 24.60228904405098 0...	7.227003145825012	41	46.000291733175565	824581	20 16T18:45:37.492
	scan eta					
417	24.562455152967143 24.602455152967142...	7.227007580763772	41	46.10035393811135	824582	20 16T18:46:49.428
	scan eta					
418	24.56262119047752 24.602621190477517 ...	7.227000928357758	41	46.20043652946358	824583	20 16T18:48:00.763
	scan eta					
419	24.56278715607613 24.60278715607613 0...	7.226996493427493	41	46.29950057210189	824584	20 16T18:49:12.392
	scan eta					
420	24.562953049260205 24.602953049260204...	7.226998710891918	41	46.3995627752565	824585	20 16T18:50:25.038
	scan eta					
421	24.56311886952137 24.60311886952137 0...	7.226998710891918	41	46.49963780154826	824586	20 16T18:51:37.372
	scan eta					
422	24.563284616356714 24.603284616356714...	7.227000928357758	41	46.59969818451265	824587	20 16T18:52:49.542
	scan eta					
423	24.563450289259773 24.603450289259772...	7.227000928357758	41	46.69975855784002	824588	20 16T18:53:59.162
	scan eta					
424	24.56361588772717 24.60361588772717 0...	7.226998710891918	41	46.799831765738816	824589	20 16T18:55:08.598
	scan eta					
425	24.563781411252304 24.603781411252303...	7.226996493427493	41	46.89986990579552	824590	20 16T18:56:16.633

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
426	scan eta 24.563946859333765 24.603946859333764...	7.227000928357758	41	46.99993578195855	824591	20 16T18:57:23.652
427	scan eta 24.56411223146574 24.604112231465738 ...	7.227003145825012	41	47.1000034889744	824592	20 16T18:58:31.192
428	scan eta 24.564277527145368 24.604277527145367...	7.227000928357758	41	47.20007119099479	824593	20 16T18:59:39.311
429	scan eta 24.564442745868146 24.604442745868145...	7.227000928357758	41	47.30016297013115	824594	20 16T19:00:47.339
430	scan eta 24.56460788713203 24.60460788713203 0...	7.227000928357758	41	47.400232511666296	824595	20 16T19:01:55.542
431	scan eta 24.56477295043305 24.60477295043305 0...	7.227000928357758	41	47.50027432293468	824596	20 16T19:03:04.242
432	scan eta 24.56493793526879 24.60493793526879 0...	7.226998710891918	41	47.60036610008648	824597	20 16T19:04:11.719
433	scan eta 24.565102841135765 24.605102841135764...	7.227003145825012	41	47.70044114410444	824598	20 16T19:05:19.592
434	scan eta 24.565267667534126 24.605267667534125...	7.227000928357758	41	47.79950517945276	824599	20 16T19:06:27.002
435	scan eta 24.56543241395862 24.60543241395862 0...	7.227000928357758	41	47.899554328551474	824600	20 16T19:07:35.202
436	scan eta 24.56559707990927 24.60559707990927 0...	7.227000928357758	41	47.999647944687815	824601	20 16T19:08:43.191
437	scan eta 24.557001820667534 24.597001820667533...	7.228001149779908	41	44.99969355094299	824602	20 16T19:09:55.29
438	scan eta 24.557168615768358 24.597168615768357...	7.227998931675402	41	45.0997724704746	824603	20 16T19:11:02.99
439	scan eta 24.557335344532117 24.597335344532116...	7.2279944954706385	41	45.199808784990694	824604	20 16T19:12:10.768
440	scan eta 24.557502006453692 24.59750200645369 ...	7.228001149779908	41	45.29986915193206	824605	20 16T19:13:18.328

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
441	scan eta 24.557668601023625 24.597668601023624...	7.227998931675402	41	45.39995173339203	824606	20 16T19:14:26.079
442	scan eta 24.557835127735704 24.597835127735703...	7.227998931675402	41	45.50000661523428	824607	20 16T19:15:34.17
443	scan eta 24.558001586082067 24.598001586082066...	7.228005585993171	41	45.60004842255445	824608	20 16T19:16:42.814
444	scan eta 24.558167975555687 24.598167975555686...	7.227998931675402	41	45.700108790854955	824609	20 16T19:17:50.736
445	scan eta 24.558334295648248 24.598334295648247...	7.228001149779908	41	45.80019871781495	824610	20 16T19:18:57.862
446	scan eta 24.55850054585626 24.598500545856258 ...	7.228007804101925	41	45.90022973429674	824611	20 16T19:20:06.805
447	scan eta 24.55866672566999 24.59866672566999 0...	7.228005585993171	41	46.00029356228183	824612	20 16T19:21:14.512
448	scan eta 24.558832834586138 24.598832834586137...	7.227998931675402	41	46.100355768072035	824613	20 16T19:22:22.793
449	scan eta 24.558998872096513 24.598998872096512...	7.227998931675402	41	46.200438359297166	824614	20 16T19:23:31.016
450	scan eta 24.559164837696134 24.599164837696133...	7.227998931675402	41	46.2994820073385	824615	20 16T19:24:39.412
451	scan eta 24.559330730879214 24.599330730879213...	7.228001149779908	41	46.39954421505945	824616	20 16T19:25:47.253
452	scan eta 24.559496551141375 24.599496551141375...	7.227996713572313	41	46.49960825146162	824617	20 16T19:26:55.699
453	scan eta 24.559662297975724 24.599662297975723...	7.227996713572313	41	46.5996741217771	824618	20 16T19:28:03.518
454	scan eta 24.559827970878768 24.599827970878767...	7.227998931675402	41	46.69976590347851	824619	20 16T19:29:11.519
455	scan eta 24.55999356934618 24.59999356934618 0...	7.228001149779908	41	46.799802413493815	824620	20 16T19:30:18.891
456	scan eta 24.560159092872308 24.600159092872307...	7.227996713572313	41	46.8998699074357	824621	20 16T19:31:26.321

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
457	scan eta 24.56032454095276 24.60032454095276 0...	7.227998931675402	41	46.999952515374254	824622	20 16T19:32:33.855
458	scan eta 24.560489913084748 24.600489913084747...	7.227998931675402	41	47.100018392745	824623	20 16T19:33:41.863
459	scan eta 24.560655208765372 24.60065520876537 ...	7.227998931675402	41	47.200095268463045	824624	20 16T19:34:50.017
460	scan eta 24.560820427487155 24.600820427487154...	7.227998931675402	41	47.30011345488942	824625	20 16T19:35:58.326
461	scan eta 24.56098556875202 24.60098556875202 0...	7.227996713572313	41	47.40020658829426	824626	20 16T19:37:06.514
462	scan eta 24.56115063205206 24.601150632052057 ...	7.227998931675402	41	47.50027432144854	824627	20 16T19:38:14.811
463	scan eta 24.5613156168878 24.6013156168878 0.0...	7.228003367885831	41	47.60036609385997	824628	20 16T19:39:22.554
464	scan eta 24.56148052275577 24.601480522755768 ...	7.227998931675402	41	47.700435636943574	824629	20 16T19:40:30.734
465	scan eta 24.561645349153135 24.601645349153134...	7.227996713572313	41	47.79950885177966	824630	20 16T19:41:39.427
466	scan eta 24.56181009557763 24.60181009557763 0...	7.228001149779908	41	47.89957106763052	824631	20 16T19:42:47.24
467	scan eta 24.561974761528266 24.601974761528265...	7.227998931675402	41	47.99962387464722	824632	20 16T19:43:54.709
468	scan eta 24.553380609035525 24.593380609035524...	7.229001659302097	41	44.99971393443626	824633	20 16T19:45:07.588
469	scan eta 24.553547404136363 24.593547404136363...	7.228999440558651	41	45.09977063484387	824634	20 16T19:46:15.205
470	scan eta 24.553714132900122 24.59371413290012 ...	7.228999440558651	41	45.1998087636516	824635	20 16T19:47:22.818
471	scan eta 24.553880794821684 24.593880794821683...	7.229003878046959	41	45.29986915071988	824636	20 16T19:48:30.515

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
472	scan eta 24.554047389392625 24.594047389392625...	7.228999440558651	41	45.39994991353927	824637	20 16T19:49:38.836
473	scan eta 24.554213916104704 24.594213916104703...	7.229001659302097	41	45.4999862177351	824638	20 16T19:50:46.601
474	scan eta 24.55438037445006 24.594380374450058 ...	7.228999440558651	41	45.6000465924907	824639	20 16T19:51:54.334
475	scan eta 24.554546763923693 24.59454676392369 ...	7.229001659302097	41	45.70013284166746	824640	20 16T19:53:01.997
476	scan eta 24.554713084016253 24.594713084016252...	7.228997221816624	41	45.80018954570889	824641	20 16T19:54:09.975
477	scan eta 24.55487933422425 24.59487933422425 0...	7.229001659302097	41	45.90023135905416	824642	20 16T19:55:18.339
478	scan eta 24.55504551403798 24.59504551403798 0...	7.228995003076014	41	46.00026260813308	824643	20 16T19:56:26.285
479	scan eta 24.555211622954143 24.595211622954142...	7.228999440558651	41	46.10035576812577	824644	20 16T19:57:34.396
480	scan eta 24.55537766046452 24.595377660464518 ...	7.229001659302097	41	46.20040901427041	824645	20 16T19:58:42.286
481	scan eta 24.555543626064125 24.595543626064124...	7.228999440558651	41	46.29950423419882	824646	20 16T19:59:50.743
482	scan eta 24.555709519247205 24.595709519247205...	7.228999440558651	41	46.39957011128217	824647	20 16T20:00:59.243
483	scan eta 24.555875339509367 24.595875339509366...	7.228999440558651	41	46.49960825020381	824648	20 16T20:02:07.149
484	scan eta 24.556041086344724 24.596041086344723...	7.228999440558651	41	46.59970551831232	824649	20 16T20:03:14.615
485	scan eta 24.556206759246773 24.596206759246773...	7.229001659302097	41	46.69977688816771	824650	20 16T20:04:22.929
486	scan eta 24.55637235771417 24.59637235771417 0...	7.228999440558651	41	46.799804034346316	824651	20 16T20:05:31.027

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
487	24.5565378812403 24.596537881240298 0...	7.228999440558651	41	46.899869910591036	824652	20 16T20:06:39.183
	scan eta					
488	24.556703329320765 24.596703329320764...	7.228997221816624	41	46.99993578099428	824653	20 16T20:07:47.484
	scan eta					
489	24.556868701453748 24.596868701453747...	7.229001659302097	41	47.1000016504028	824654	20 16T20:08:54.466
	scan eta					
490	24.557033997133363 24.597033997133362...	7.228997221816624	41	47.20007140842226	824655	20 16T20:10:02.085
	scan eta					
491	24.557199215856155 24.597199215856154...	7.228999440558651	41	47.30013890447181	824656	20 16T20:11:09.82
	scan eta					
492	24.557364357120026 24.597364357120025...	7.229001659302097	41	47.400232512518095	824657	20 16T20:12:18.168
	scan eta					
493	24.55752942042005 24.59752942042005 0...	7.228997221816624	41	47.50027615963273	824658	20 16T20:13:25.957
	scan eta					
494	24.5576944052568 24.5976944052568 0.0...	7.228999440558651	41	47.6003438621532	824659	20 16T20:14:33.304
	scan eta					
495	24.557859311123774 24.597859311123774...	7.228999440558651	41	47.70043381181788	824660	20 16T20:15:41.789
	scan eta					
496	24.558024137521127 24.598024137521126...	7.228999440558651	41	47.799503353261684	824661	20 16T20:16:49.702
	scan eta					
497	24.558188883945622 24.59818888394562 ...	7.229003878046959	41	47.899574720349854	824662	20 16T20:17:57.358
	scan eta					
498	24.55835354989627 24.59835354989627 0...	7.228999440558651	41	47.99965344035797	824663	20 16T20:19:05.168
	scan eta					
499	24.549760503627535 24.589760503627534...	7.2299957989033645	41	44.99971026766451	824664	20 16T20:20:19.781
	scan eta					
500	24.54992729872735 24.58992729872735 0...	7.230000237664421	41	45.09977063334042	824665	20 16T20:21:27.983
	scan eta					
501	24.55009402749212 24.590094027492118 ...	7.230002457047077	41	45.1998291671455	824666	20 16T20:22:36.245

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
502	scan eta 24.55026068941368 24.59026068941368 0...	7.230000237664421	41	45.29988770960183	824667	20 16T20:23:44.695
503	scan eta 24.550427283983627 24.590427283983626...	7.230002457047077	41	45.39995540512178	824668	20 16T20:24:52.565
504	scan eta 24.550593810695705 24.590593810695704...	7.230000237664421	41	45.5000102799409	824669	20 16T20:26:00.596
505	scan eta 24.55076026904106 24.59076026904106 0...	7.229998018283182	41	45.60004842283897	824670	20 16T20:27:08.262
506	scan eta 24.550926658514694 24.590926658514693...	7.2299957989033645	41	45.70008883080956	824671	20 16T20:28:16.276
507	scan eta 24.55109297860825 24.59109297860825 0...	7.23000689581664	41	45.800169161493166	824672	20 16T20:29:23.807
508	scan eta 24.55125922881525 24.59125922881525 0...	7.230000237664421	41	45.90025175765436	824673	20 16T20:30:31.562
509	scan eta 24.551425408628983 24.591425408628982...	7.230000237664421	41	46.00029356343124	824674	20 16T20:31:40.075
510	scan eta 24.551591517545145 24.591591517545144...	7.2299957989033645	41	46.1003468103562	824675	20 16T20:32:50.235
511	scan eta 24.55175755505552 24.59175755505552 0...	7.230000237664421	41	46.20044020530901	824676	20 16T20:33:59.913
512	scan eta 24.551923520655127 24.591923520655126...	7.230000237664421	41	46.29950606620856	824677	20 16T20:35:09.623
513	scan eta 24.552089413838207 24.592089413838206...	7.230000237664421	41	46.39956826845631	824678	20 16T20:36:21.042
514	scan eta 24.552255234100368 24.592255234100367...	7.229998018283182	41	46.49963414952556	824679	20 16T20:37:32.033
515	scan eta 24.552420980935725 24.592420980935724...	7.230000237664421	41	46.59969451842634	824680	20 16T20:38:43.187
516	scan eta 24.552586653837775 24.592586653837774...	7.230000237664421	41	46.699756726704386	824681	20 16T20:39:54.508

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
517	scan eta 24.552752252305172 24.59275225230517 ...	7.230000237664421	41	46.79982809826551	824682	20 16T20:41:05.959
518	scan eta 24.5529177758313 24.5929177758313 0.0...	7.230000237664421	41	46.89988846402468	824683	20 16T20:42:17.119
519	scan eta 24.55308322391276 24.59308322391276 0...	7.230002457047077	41	46.99996900384394	824684	20 16T20:43:27.28
520	scan eta 24.55324859604475 24.59324859604475 0...	7.230000237664421	41	47.10000348780415	824685	20 16T20:44:39.256
521	scan eta 24.553413891724365 24.593413891724364...	7.230000237664421	41	47.20009526089718	824686	20 16T20:45:49.618
522	scan eta 24.553579110447156 24.593579110447156...	7.230000237664421	41	47.30013890292291	824687	20 16T20:47:01.362
523	scan eta 24.553744251711027 24.593744251711026...	7.230002457047077	41	47.40022151056502	824688	20 16T20:48:11.865
524	scan eta 24.55390931501206 24.59390931501206 0...	7.230000237664421	41	47.50027615040791	824689	20 16T20:49:23.491
525	scan eta 24.554074299847787 24.594074299847787...	7.230000237664421	41	47.60034383892809	824690	20 16T20:50:33.056
526	scan eta 24.55423920571476 24.59423920571476 0...	7.230002457047077	41	47.700413405223536	824691	20 16T20:51:43.09
527	scan eta 24.554404032112128 24.594404032112127...	7.230000237664421	41	47.79948295015148	824692	20 16T20:52:53.966
528	scan eta 24.554568778536623 24.594568778536622...	7.230000237664421	41	47.89957839970751	824693	20 16T20:54:04.751
529	scan eta 24.55473344448726 24.594733444487257 ...	7.2299957989033645	41	47.99962387266433	824694	20 16T20:55:15.87
530	scan eta 24.546141503915532 24.58614150391553 ...	7.230999103094814	41	44.99969355245999	824695	20 16T20:56:31.109
531	scan eta 24.546308299016356 24.586308299016356...	7.230996883075512	41	45.09975206349066	824696	20 16T20:57:42.436

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
532	scan eta 24.546475027780115 24.586475027780114...	7.231003543137673	41	45.19980878819924	824697	20 16T20:58:53.855
533	scan eta 24.54664168970169 24.58664168970169 0...	7.230999103094814	41	45.29999407482549	824698	20 16T21:00:07.297
534	scan eta 24.546808284271624 24.586808284271623...	7.230996883075512	41	45.39992769020011	824699	20 16T21:01:18.571
535	scan eta 24.546974810983702 24.5869748109837 0...	7.230999103094814	41	45.49997176043085	824700	20 16T21:02:28.357
536	scan eta 24.54714126932907 24.58714126932907 0...	7.231001323115534	41	45.60004658547242	824701	20 16T21:03:40.32
537	scan eta 24.54730765880269 24.58730765880269 0...	7.231003543137673	41	45.70010695375705	824702	20 16T21:04:53.08
538	scan eta 24.547473978896246 24.587473978896245...	7.230999103094814	41	45.800169162763126	824703	20 16T21:06:04.972
539	scan eta 24.547640229103248 24.587640229103247...	7.230999103094814	41	45.900231362278696	824704	20 16T21:07:16.775
540	scan eta 24.54780640891799 24.587806408917988 ...	7.230996883075512	41	46.00027727320913	824705	20 16T21:08:28.216
541	scan eta 24.547972517834136 24.587972517834135...	7.230999103094814	41	46.10035576791333	824706	20 16T21:09:39.645
542	scan eta 24.54813855534451 24.58813855534451 0...	7.230999103094814	41	46.20043653411417	824707	20 16T21:10:50.816
543	scan eta 24.548304520943137 24.588304520943137...	7.230999103094814	41	46.29950790111318	824708	20 16T21:12:02.577
544	scan eta 24.548470414127213 24.58847041412721 ...	7.231001323115534	41	46.39953709183786	824709	20 16T21:13:14.484
545	scan eta 24.54863623438838 24.588636234388378 ...	7.230999103094814	41	46.499630481445124	824710	20 16T21:14:25.877
546	scan eta 24.548801981223722 24.58880198122372 ...	7.230996883075512	41	46.59967228979933	824711	20 16T21:15:39.975

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
547	scan eta 24.548967654126766 24.588967654126765...	7.230999103094814	41	46.69976772639137	824712	20 16T21:16:51.174
548	scan eta 24.549133252594178 24.589133252594177...	7.230999103094814	41	46.79980403766169	824713	20 16T21:18:03.322
549	scan eta 24.54929877611931 24.58929877611931 0...	7.231001323115534	41	46.8998994697246	824714	20 16T21:19:15.693
550	scan eta 24.549464224200772 24.58946422420077 ...	7.231001323115534	41	46.99996718541503	824715	20 16T21:20:27.101
551	scan eta 24.549629596332746 24.589629596332745...	7.230999103094814	41	47.100029391916166	824716	20 16T21:21:38.012
552	scan eta 24.549794892012375 24.589794892012375...	7.230999103094814	41	47.200071195165464	824717	20 16T21:22:49.253
553	scan eta 24.549960110735153 24.589960110735152...	7.231003543137673	41	47.30015930490871	824718	20 16T21:24:00.985
554	scan eta 24.550125251999024 24.590125251999023...	7.231001323115534	41	47.400225185249425	824719	20 16T21:25:12.506
555	scan eta 24.550290315300057 24.590290315300056...	7.230999103094814	41	47.50030572238403	824720	20 16T21:26:23.384
556	scan eta 24.5504553001358 24.590455300135798 0...	7.230999103094814	41	47.60037526982022	824721	20 16T21:27:31.174
557	scan eta 24.550620206002773 24.59062020600277 ...	7.23100576316123	41	47.700439317676235	824722	20 16T21:28:38.797
558	scan eta 24.550785032400125 24.590785032400124...	7.230996883075512	41	47.799507017021114	824723	20 16T21:29:46.562
559	scan eta 24.55094977882563 24.590949778825628 ...	7.2310079831862035	41	47.89955432688027	824724	20 16T21:30:54.843
560	scan eta 24.551114444776264 24.591114444776263...	7.230999103094814	41	47.99962387127496	824725	20 16T21:32:02.346
561	scan eta 24.542523609375532 24.58252360937553 ...	7.2320004763744095	41	44.99967908915897	824726	20 16T21:33:13.975
562	scan eta 24.542690404476357 24.582690404476356...	7.231998255715353	41	45.099779804518114	824727	20 16T21:34:21.758

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
563	scan eta 24.542857133240116 24.582857133240115...	7.2320004763744095	41	45.19980879088455	824728	20 16T21:35:29.395
564	scan eta 24.54302379516169 24.58302379516169 0...	7.2320026970348845	41	45.299893197177504	824729	20 16T21:36:37.303
565	scan eta 24.543190389731624 24.583190389731623...	7.231998255715353	41	45.399951737788825	824730	20 16T21:37:45.139
566	scan eta 24.543356916443702 24.5833569164437 0...	7.231998255715353	41	45.499988053327534	824731	20 16T21:38:53.164
567	scan eta 24.543523374789057 24.583523374789056...	7.231998255715353	41	45.60004679036087	824732	20 16T21:40:01.324
568	scan eta 24.54368976426269 24.58368976426269 0...	7.2320004763744095	41	45.70010695648155	824733	20 16T21:41:09.724
569	scan eta 24.543856084356246 24.583856084356245...	7.2320026970348845	41	45.8001691569324	824734	20 16T21:42:18.333
570	scan eta 24.544022334564257 24.584022334564256...	7.2320004763744095	41	45.90025909200442	824735	20 16T21:43:26.084
571	scan eta 24.54418851437799 24.58418851437799 0...	7.2319960350577155	41	46.00031578870331	824736	20 16T21:44:33.996
572	scan eta 24.544354623294137 24.584354623294136...	7.2319960350577155	41	46.100355768079595	824737	20 16T21:45:41.682
573	scan eta 24.544520660804512 24.58452066080451 ...	7.23200491769678	41	46.20044203047791	824738	20 16T21:46:49.885
574	scan eta 24.544686626403138 24.584686626403137...	7.231998255715353	41	46.29948015339707	824739	20 16T21:47:58.381
575	scan eta 24.544852519587213 24.584852519587212...	7.231998255715353	41	46.399571940281874	824740	20 16T21:49:06.588
576	scan eta 24.54501833984838 24.58501833984838 0...	7.2320004763744095	41	46.499610085035854	824741	20 16T21:50:15.856
577	scan eta 24.545184086683722 24.58518408668372 ...	7.2320004763744095	41	46.59970369333176	824742	20 16T21:51:24.594

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
578	scan eta 24.545349759586767 24.585349759586766...	7.2320004763744095	41	46.69973817164466	824743	20 16T21:52:32.564
579	scan eta 24.54551535805418 24.585515358054177 ...	7.2320004763744095	41	46.79980403738993	824744	20 16T21:53:41.585
580	scan eta 24.54568088157931 24.58568088157931 0...	7.231998255715353	41	46.899895804081694	824745	20 16T21:54:49.371
581	scan eta 24.545846329660773 24.58584632966077 ...	7.2320004763744095	41	46.999961682478045	824746	20 16T21:55:57.742
582	scan eta 24.546011701792747 24.586011701792746...	7.231998255715353	41	47.10002388480313	824747	20 16T21:57:05.894
583	scan eta 24.54617699747236 24.58617699747236 0...	7.2320026970348845	41	47.200047579263895	824748	20 16T21:58:13.879
584	scan eta 24.546342216195153 24.586342216195153...	7.23200491769678	41	47.30013890621715	824749	20 16T21:59:23.265
585	scan eta 24.546507357459024 24.586507357459023...	7.2320004763744095	41	47.40022884941381	824750	20 16T22:00:30.935
586	scan eta 24.546672420760057 24.586672420760056...	7.2320004763744095	41	47.50027432145642	824751	20 16T22:01:38.526
587	scan eta 24.5468374055958 24.586837405595798 0...	7.231998255715353	41	47.60034386527086	824752	20 16T22:02:46.637
588	scan eta 24.547002311462773 24.587002311462772...	7.2320026970348845	41	47.70043198094898	824753	20 16T22:03:54.695
589	scan eta 24.547167137860125 24.587167137860124...	7.2320004763744095	41	47.79948292669701	824754	20 16T22:05:02.207
590	scan eta 24.54733188428563 24.58733188428563 0...	7.2320004763744095	41	47.89958023446684	824755	20 16T22:06:09.884
591	scan eta 24.547496550236264 24.587496550236263...	7.2319960350577155	41	47.999646114219836	824756	20 16T22:07:17.623
592	scan eta 24.53890681948253 24.57890681948253 0...	7.232999916945849	41	44.999715769110956	824757	20 16T22:08:29.857

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
593	scan eta 24.53907361458236 24.57907361458236 0...	7.232999916945849	41	45.09977064516411	824758	20 16T22:09:37.965
594	scan eta 24.539240343347128 24.579240343347127...	7.232999916945849	41	45.199832846033	824759	20 16T22:10:45.854
595	scan eta 24.53940700526869 24.57940700526869 0...	7.232999916945849	41	45.29988587834191	824760	20 16T22:11:53.968
596	scan eta 24.539573599838622 24.57957359983862 ...	7.232995474351941	41	45.399948066267754	824761	20 16T22:13:02.57
597	scan eta 24.5397401265507 24.5797401265507 0.0...	7.232999916945849	41	45.499988056214995	824762	20 16T22:14:10.695
598	scan eta 24.53990658489607 24.57990658489607 0...	7.232999916945849	41	45.60006331457383	824763	20 16T22:15:19.335
599	scan eta 24.54007297436969 24.58007297436969 0...	7.232999916945849	41	45.70012918243331	824764	20 16T22:16:27.758
600	scan eta 24.540239294463245 24.580239294463244...	7.232999916945849	41	45.80019321977402	824765	20 16T22:17:36.506
601	scan eta 24.540405544670246 24.580405544670246...	7.232999916945849	41	45.90023136364922	824766	20 16T22:18:43.907
602	scan eta 24.54057172448398 24.580571724483978 ...	7.233002138244934	41	46.00029356780714	824767	20 16T22:19:52.352
603	scan eta 24.54073783340014 24.58073783340014 0...	7.232999916945849	41	46.100376160337	824768	20 16T22:21:00.549
604	scan eta 24.540903870910515 24.580903870910515...	7.232997695648185	41	46.200417970245255	824769	20 16T22:22:08.793
605	scan eta 24.541069836510136 24.581069836510135...	7.232999916945849	41	46.29950790164992	824770	20 16T22:23:17.18
606	scan eta 24.541235729693216 24.581235729693216...	7.232999916945849	41	46.39957744000844	824771	20 16T22:24:25.139
607	scan eta 24.541401549955378 24.581401549955377...	7.233002138244934	41	46.499608251384124	824772	20 16T22:25:33.203

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
608	scan eta 24.54156729679072 24.58156729679072 0...	7.232999916945849	41	46.59969268491352	824773	20 16T22:26:41.117
609	scan eta 24.54173296969277 24.58173296969277 0...	7.233002138244934	41	46.69973816054888	824774	20 16T22:27:48.573
610	scan eta 24.541898568160168 24.581898568160167...	7.232997695648185	41	46.7998040328891	824775	20 16T22:28:56.293
611	scan eta 24.54206409168631 24.58206409168631 0...	7.233002138244934	41	46.89986990868574	824776	20 16T22:30:06.636
612	scan eta 24.54222953976777 24.58222953976777 0...	7.233006580847359	41	46.999924996075244	824777	20 16T22:31:14.473
613	scan eta 24.542394911899745 24.582394911899744...	7.232999916945849	41	47.10002021842008	824778	20 16T22:32:23.031
614	scan eta 24.542560207579374 24.582560207579373...	7.232999916945849	41	47.20008792558964	824779	20 16T22:33:31.336
615	scan eta 24.54272542630215 24.58272542630215 0...	7.232999916945849	41	47.300170304850276	824780	20 16T22:34:39.699
616	scan eta 24.542890567566022 24.58289056756602 ...	7.233004359545438	41	47.40022701849573	824781	20 16T22:35:47.973
617	scan eta 24.543055630866046 24.583055630866046...	7.232999916945849	41	47.50027431686086	824782	20 16T22:36:55.992
618	scan eta 24.543220615702797 24.583220615702796...	7.232999916945849	41	47.600377101199804	824783	20 16T22:38:03.758
619	scan eta 24.54338552156977 24.58338552156977 0...	7.232997695648185	41	47.70041340347962	824784	20 16T22:39:12.086
620	scan eta 24.543550347967123 24.583550347967122...	7.233004359545438	41	47.79950335217763	824785	20 16T22:40:20.535
621	scan eta 24.54371509439162 24.583715094391618 ...	7.232999916945849	41	47.89954356186812	824786	20 16T22:41:28.437
622	scan eta 24.543879760342268 24.583879760342267...	7.232999916945849	41	47.9996534544379	824787	20 16T22:42:36.194

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
623	scan eta 24.535291133710526 24.575291133710525...	7.23399964495207	41	44.999721271891524	824788	20 16T22:43:49.695
624	scan eta 24.53545792881135 24.57545792881135 0...	7.234001866890036	41	45.099768799997264	824789	20 16T22:44:57.455
625	scan eta 24.535624657575124 24.575624657575123...	7.234004088829418	41	45.19980878123044	824790	20 16T22:46:05.936
626	scan eta 24.535791319496685 24.575791319496684...	7.23399964495207	41	45.29989688218691	824791	20 16T22:47:13.707
627	scan eta 24.535957914066632 24.57595791406663 ...	7.234004088829418	41	45.399957239251734	824792	20 16T22:48:22.065
628	scan eta 24.53612444077871 24.57612444077871 0...	7.23399964495207	41	45.499986218975394	824793	20 16T22:49:30.338
629	scan eta 24.53629089912506 24.57629089912506 0...	7.234001866890036	41	45.600048425555315	824794	20 16T22:50:38.493
630	scan eta 24.536457288597685 24.576457288597684...	7.23399964495207	41	45.70010879087594	824795	20 16T22:51:47.573
631	scan eta 24.53662360869124 24.57662360869124 0...	7.23399964495207	41	45.80019138321842	824796	20 16T22:52:55.472
632	scan eta 24.53678985889925 24.57678985889925 0...	7.233997423015529	41	45.90024624603473	824797	20 16T22:54:03.663
633	scan eta 24.536956038712983 24.576956038712982...	7.23399964495207	41	46.00029173177666	824798	20 16T22:55:11.641
634	scan eta 24.537122147629145 24.577122147629144...	7.234001866890036	41	46.10035576809329	824799	20 16T22:56:20.159
635	scan eta 24.53728818513952 24.57728818513952 0...	7.23399964495207	41	46.20039801465845	824800	20 16T22:57:28.366
636	scan eta 24.537454150739126 24.577454150739126...	7.234001866890036	41	46.29950607630718	824801	20 16T22:58:36.7
637	scan eta 24.537620043922207 24.577620043922206...	7.23399964495207	41	46.39957744508882	824802	20 16T22:59:45.458

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
638	scan eta 24.537785864184368 24.577785864184367...	7.234001866890036	41	46.499639649979315	824803	20 16T23:00:53.476
639	scan eta 24.537951611018716 24.577951611018715...	7.234006310770224	41	46.59969818895217	824804	20 16T23:02:01.493
640	scan eta 24.538117283921775 24.578117283921774...	7.23399964495207	41	46.6997640584921	824805	20 16T23:03:11.242
641	scan eta 24.538282882389172 24.57828288238917 ...	7.23399964495207	41	46.79982810118679	824806	20 16T23:04:23.169
642	scan eta 24.5384484059153 24.5784484059153 0.0...	7.23399964495207	41	46.899888473835134	824807	20 16T23:05:35.186
643	scan eta 24.538613853995766 24.578613853995765...	7.23399964495207	41	46.99995801298333	824808	20 16T23:06:46.732
644	scan eta 24.53877922612774 24.57877922612774 0...	7.23399964495207	41	47.10002389035898	824809	20 16T23:07:59.705
645	scan eta 24.53894452180737 24.57894452180737 0...	7.23399964495207	41	47.200071199821245	824810	20 16T23:09:12.425
646	scan eta 24.539109740530147 24.579109740530146...	7.234001866890036	41	47.300168475053745	824811	20 16T23:10:25.165
647	scan eta 24.539274881794032 24.57927488179403 ...	7.23399964495207	41	47.40020661614525	824812	20 16T23:11:36.776
648	scan eta 24.53943994509505 24.57943994509505 0...	7.23399964495207	41	47.50030205345304	824813	20 16T23:12:48.652
649	scan eta 24.539604929930793 24.57960492993079 ...	7.234004088829418	41	47.600371596188296	824814	20 16T23:14:00.225
650	scan eta 24.539769835797767 24.579769835797766...	7.23399964495207	41	47.7004374767109	824815	20 16T23:15:11.54
651	scan eta 24.539934662196128 24.579934662196127...	7.23399964495207	41	47.799505193939986	824816	20 16T23:16:23.107
652	scan eta 24.540099408620623 24.580099408620622...	7.234001866890036	41	47.89955433346096	824817	20 16T23:17:35.342

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
653	scan eta 24.540264074571258 24.580264074571257...	7.234001866890036	41	47.9996257128925	824818	20 16T23:18:47.338
654	scan eta 24.53167655153653 24.57167655153653 0...	7.234999660515361	41	44.99969355666473	824819	20 16T23:20:03.486
655	scan eta 24.531843346637356 24.571843346637355...	7.234997437939666	41	45.0997520865169	824820	20 16T23:21:16.704
656	scan eta 24.53201007540113 24.572010075401128 ...	7.234999660515361	41	45.199836498594685	824821	20 16T23:22:29.39
657	scan eta 24.53217673732269 24.57217673732269 0...	7.234999660515361	41	45.299869158131095	824822	20 16T23:23:41.944
658	scan eta 24.532343331892623 24.572343331892622...	7.235001883092477	41	45.39995541612241	824823	20 16T23:24:53.678
659	scan eta 24.5325098586047 24.5725098586047 0.0...	7.234999660515361	41	45.50001760437476	824824	20 16T23:26:05.02
660	scan eta 24.532676316951065 24.572676316951064...	7.234999660515361	41	45.60007064025634	824825	20 16T23:27:16.64
661	scan eta 24.53284270642369 24.57284270642369 0...	7.235006328250972	41	45.70013284679455	824826	20 16T23:28:28.648
662	scan eta 24.533009026517245 24.573009026517244...	7.235004105671013	41	45.800169136286605	824827	20 16T23:29:40.387
663	scan eta 24.533175276725256 24.573175276725255...	7.234997437939666	41	45.9002590793774	824828	20 16T23:30:52.389
664	scan eta 24.533341456538988 24.573341456538987...	7.234999660515361	41	46.0003231250094	824829	20 16T23:32:04.582
665	scan eta 24.533507565455135 24.573507565455134...	7.234997437939666	41	46.10038349720571	824830	20 16T23:33:17.022
666	scan eta 24.53367360296551 24.57367360296551 0...	7.234999660515361	41	46.20041797322537	824831	20 16T23:34:29.257
667	scan eta 24.533839568564137 24.573839568564136...	7.234999660515361	41	46.2994712198819	824832	20 16T23:35:42.319

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
668	scan eta 24.53400546174821 24.57400546174821 0...	7.234995215365391	41	46.399537091415496	824833	20 16T23:36:54.393
669	scan eta 24.53417128200938 24.574171282009377 ...	7.234999660515361	41	46.49963048011271	824834	20 16T23:38:05.82
670	scan eta 24.53433702884472 24.57433702884472 0...	7.235004105671013	41	46.59967412603225	824835	20 16T23:39:17.631
671	scan eta 24.534502701747765 24.574502701747765...	7.234999660515361	41	46.69973816181352	824836	20 16T23:40:28.363
672	scan eta 24.534668300215177 24.574668300215176...	7.235001883092477	41	46.79980403592347	824837	20 16T23:41:40.74
673	scan eta 24.53483382374031 24.57483382374031 0...	7.234999660515361	41	46.89986991217385	824838	20 16T23:42:52.792
674	scan eta 24.53499927182177 24.57499927182177 0...	7.235004105671013	41	46.99993761395179	824839	20 16T23:44:06.14
675	scan eta 24.535164643953745 24.575164643953745...	7.234999660515361	41	47.09998903734856	824840	20 16T23:45:18.277
676	scan eta 24.535329939633375 24.575329939633374...	7.234997437939666	41	47.20007119966366	824841	20 16T23:46:30.306
677	scan eta 24.535495158356152 24.57549515835615 ...	7.235004105671013	41	47.30013890293557	824842	20 16T23:47:42.7
678	scan eta 24.535660299620023 24.575660299620022...	7.234999660515361	41	47.4002306800927	824843	20 16T23:48:53.889
679	scan eta 24.535825362921056 24.575825362921055...	7.234999660515361	41	47.500274537207595	824844	20 16T23:50:08.342
680	scan eta 24.535990347756798 24.575990347756797...	7.235001883092477	41	47.60037161149337	824845	20 16T23:51:21.497
681	scan eta 24.53615525362377 24.57615525362377 0...	7.235004105671013	41	47.70043931582501	824846	20 16T23:52:32.907
682	scan eta 24.536320080022133 24.576320080022132...	7.234999660515361	41	47.799482953349454	824847	20 16T23:53:46.51

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
683	scan eta 24.536484826446628 24.576484826446627...	7.234997437939666	41	47.89957656276479	824848	20 16T23:54:59.419
684	scan eta 24.536649492397263 24.576649492397262...	7.234999660515361	41	47.99964794914463	824849	20 16T23:56:11.373
685	scan eta 24.528063072435526 24.568063072435525...	7.2360044101925745	41	44.99972310787807	824850	20 16T23:57:28.762
686	scan eta 24.528229867536364 24.568229867536363...	7.235999963758075	41	45.09975025807848	824851	20 16T23:58:40.307
687	scan eta 24.528396596300123 24.568396596300122...	7.2360021869746145	41	45.19980878951676	824852	20 16T23:59:51.867
688	scan eta 24.528563258221684 24.568563258221683...	7.235997740542955	41	45.299867521698225	824853	20 17T00:01:00.602
689	scan eta 24.52872985279163 24.56872985279163 0...	7.2360021869746145	41	45.3999554020913	824854	20 17T00:02:08.965
690	scan eta 24.528896379504705 24.568896379504704...	7.2360021869746145	41	45.49998805661519	824855	20 17T00:03:17.242
691	scan eta 24.52906283785006 24.56906283785006 0...	7.235997740542955	41	45.60001746430601	824856	20 17T00:04:26.315
692	scan eta 24.529229227323693 24.569229227323692...	7.235999963758075	41	45.70012735685508	824857	20 17T00:05:34.773
693	scan eta 24.52939554741624 24.56939554741624 0...	7.235997740542955	41	45.800191379537004	824858	20 17T00:06:44.043
694	scan eta 24.52956179762425 24.56956179762425 0...	7.235997740542955	41	45.90025908832269	824859	20 17T00:07:53.969
695	scan eta 24.529727977437982 24.56972797743798 ...	7.2360021869746145	41	46.00029173337833	824860	20 17T00:09:02.901
696	scan eta 24.529894086354144 24.569894086354143...	7.235997740542955	41	46.10035576797078	824861	20 17T00:10:13.264
697	scan eta 24.53006012386452 24.57006012386452 0...	7.235999963758075	41	46.20041797022052	824862	20 17T00:11:21.264

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
698	scan eta 24.530226089464126 24.570226089464125...	7.236006633411958	41	46.29948201375988	824863	20 17T00:12:29.085
699	scan eta 24.530391982647206 24.570391982647205...	7.235999963758075	41	46.39954421321265	824864	20 17T00:13:37.59
700	scan eta 24.530557802909367 24.570557802909367...	7.2360021869746145	41	46.49963415365665	824865	20 17T00:14:46.708
701	scan eta 24.530723549743715 24.570723549743715...	7.235997740542955	41	46.59967412299046	824866	20 17T00:15:54.986
702	scan eta 24.530889222646774 24.570889222646773...	7.2360021869746145	41	46.69973999806181	824867	20 17T00:17:04.377
703	scan eta 24.53105482111417 24.57105482111417 0...	7.235997740542955	41	46.79983726581843	824868	20 17T00:18:13.148
704	scan eta 24.5312203446403 24.5712203446403 0.0...	7.235997740542955	41	46.89990130705645	824869	20 17T00:19:21.318
705	scan eta 24.531385792720766 24.571385792720765...	7.235999963758075	41	46.99993761265024	824870	20 17T00:20:29.866
706	scan eta 24.53155116485274 24.57155116485274 0...	7.235999963758075	41	47.10000348918403	824871	20 17T00:21:37.601
707	scan eta 24.531716460533364 24.571716460533363...	7.235999963758075	41	47.200060412124216	824872	20 17T00:22:46.285
708	scan eta 24.531881679256156 24.571881679256155...	7.235999963758075	41	47.3001389029665	824873	20 17T00:23:54.378
709	scan eta 24.532046820520026 24.572046820520026...	7.2360044101925745	41	47.40020658818933	824874	20 17T00:25:02.422
710	scan eta 24.53221188382005 24.57221188382005 0...	7.2360021869746145	41	47.500300225297565	824875	20 17T00:26:10.569
711	scan eta 24.5323768686568 24.5723768686568 0.0...	7.235999963758075	41	47.600371602614494	824876	20 17T00:27:18.999
712	scan eta 24.53254177452376 24.57254177452376 0...	7.235999963758075	41	47.70041348420339	824877	20 17T00:28:27.417

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
713	scan eta 24.532706600921127 24.572706600921126...	7.235999963758075	41	47.79948294746679	824878	17T00:29:36.468
714	scan eta 24.532871347345623 24.57287134734562 ...	7.235999963758075	41	47.89957473056546	824879	17T00:30:44.896
715	scan eta 24.53303601329627 24.57303601329627 0...	7.2360044101925745	41	47.99962387270883	824880	17T00:31:53.714
716	scan eta 24.524450695884536 24.564450695884535...	7.236996107094429	41	44.99967175698165	824881	17T00:33:06.438
717	scan eta 24.52461749098536 24.56461749098536 0...	7.237002778658873	41	45.09975208381883	824882	17T00:34:15.268
718	scan eta 24.52478421974912 24.564784219749118 ...	7.236996107094429	41	45.19980878509852	824883	17T00:35:23.797
719	scan eta 24.52495088167068 24.56495088167068 0...	7.237005002516529	41	45.29988404194548	824884	17T00:36:32.568
720	scan eta 24.525117476240627 24.565117476240626...	7.237000554802635	41	45.39992768707933	824885	17T00:37:40.569
721	scan eta 24.525284002952706 24.565284002952705...	7.237000554802635	41	45.499988050460395	824886	17T00:38:49.63
722	scan eta 24.52545046129907 24.56545046129907 0...	7.236996107094429	41	45.600077971545794	824887	17T00:39:57.45
723	scan eta 24.52561685077269 24.565616850772688 ...	7.237000554802635	41	45.7001087926724	824888	17T00:41:07.357
724	scan eta 24.52578317086525 24.56578317086525 0...	7.237000554802635	41	45.800169161745075	824889	17T00:42:16.111
725	scan eta 24.525949421073246 24.565949421073245...	7.237000554802635	41	45.90023136082855	824890	17T00:43:24.698
726	scan eta 24.52611560088698 24.566115600886977 ...	7.237000554802635	41	46.000319459047766	824891	17T00:44:33.062

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
727	24.52628170980314 24.56628170980314 0...	7.237000554802635	41	46.100388995888565	824892	20 17T00:45:41.324
	scan eta					
728	24.526447747313515 24.566447747313514...	7.236998330947823	41	46.2004179686997	824893	20 17T00:46:50.325
	scan eta					
729	24.526613712913136 24.566613712913135...	7.237000554802635	41	46.29948201527898	824894	20 17T00:47:58.805
	scan eta					
730	24.526779606096216 24.566779606096215...	7.237002778658873	41	46.39954421997183	824895	20 17T00:49:07.044
	scan eta					
731	24.526945426358377 24.566945426358377...	7.237000554802635	41	46.49960824763811	824896	20 17T00:50:16.428
	scan eta					
732	24.527111173192726 24.567111173192725...	7.237002778658873	41	46.59967412452228	824897	20 17T00:51:25.315
	scan eta					
733	24.52727684609577 24.56727684609577 0...	7.236998330947823	41	46.69974183273534	824898	20 17T00:52:33.978
	scan eta					
734	24.527442444563167 24.567442444563167...	7.237000554802635	41	46.79982259638236	824899	20 17T00:53:42.995
	scan eta					
735	24.52760796808931 24.56760796808931 0...	7.237000554802635	41	46.89986991020661	824900	20 17T00:54:51.061
	scan eta					
736	24.52777341616976 24.56777341616976 0...	7.237000554802635	41	46.99996351849528	824901	20 17T00:56:00.137
	scan eta					
737	24.527938788301736 24.567938788301735...	7.236996107094429	41	47.100003484948516	824902	20 17T00:57:08.87
	scan eta					
738	24.528104083982374 24.568104083982373...	7.237000554802635	41	47.20009342292762	824903	20 17T00:58:17.28
	scan eta					
739	24.52826930270515 24.56826930270515 0...	7.236998330947823	41	47.30013707271754	824904	20 17T00:59:25.326
	scan eta					
740	24.528434443969022 24.56843444396902 ...	7.237000554802635	41	47.40023251351126	824905	20 17T01:00:35.685
	scan eta					
741	24.52859950726906 24.56859950726906 0...	7.237000554802635	41	47.500305730153734	824906	20 17T01:01:44.025

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
742	scan eta 24.528764492104788 24.568764492104787...	7.237000554802635	41	47.60036243608094	824907	17T01:02:52.795
743	scan eta 24.52892939797277 24.56892939797277 0...	7.236996107094429	41	47.70044481089433	824908	17T01:04:01.306
744	scan eta 24.529094224370123 24.569094224370122...	7.237000554802635	41	47.799508855669316	824909	17T01:05:09.682
745	scan eta 24.52925897079462 24.569258970794618 ...	7.237002778658873	41	47.89955430348172	824910	17T01:06:18.31
746	scan eta 24.529423636745268 24.569423636745267...	7.237000554802635	41	47.999625706118074	824911	17T01:07:26.211
747	scan eta 24.52083942136053 24.56083942136053 0...	7.2379969847834005	41	44.99971027048504	824912	17T01:08:38.697
748	scan eta 24.52100621646036 24.56100621646036 0...	7.23799920927676	41	45.0997743027515	824913	17T01:09:47.518
749	scan eta 24.52117294522513 24.561172945225128 ...	7.238001433771541	41	45.19983650098233	824914	17T01:10:55.929
750	scan eta 24.52133960714568 24.56133960714568 0...	7.2379969847834005	41	45.29986915453346	824915	17T01:12:04.539
751	scan eta 24.521506201716623 24.56150620171662 ...	7.238003658267745	41	45.39994991311938	824916	17T01:13:13.932
752	scan eta 24.5216727284287 24.5616727284287 0.0...	7.23799920927676	41	45.5000047773717	824917	17T01:14:21.998
753	scan eta 24.52183918677407 24.56183918677407 0...	7.238005882765372	41	45.60004842262655	824918	17T01:15:29.549
754	scan eta 24.52200557624769 24.56200557624769 0...	7.2379969847834005	41	45.700132849220715	824919	17T01:16:39.128
755	scan eta 24.522171896341245 24.562171896341244...	7.238001433771541	41	45.80020420918815	824920	17T01:17:47.31

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
756	scan eta 24.522338146548247 24.562338146548246...	7.2379969847834005	41	45.900231360791125	824921	17T01:18:56.349
757	scan eta 24.52250432636198 24.562504326361978 ...	7.2379969847834005	41	46.000293770959246	824922	17T01:20:07.053
758	scan eta 24.52267043527814 24.56267043527814 0...	7.238003658267745	41	46.10035393200578	824923	17T01:21:16.015
759	scan eta 24.522836472788516 24.562836472788515...	7.2379969847834005	41	46.200440189341364	824924	17T01:22:24.918
760	scan eta 24.523002438388136 24.563002438388136...	7.238001433771541	41	46.29948017733367	824925	17T01:23:33.334
761	scan eta 24.523168331571203 24.5631683315712 0...	7.2379969847834005	41	46.39954421644218	824926	17T01:24:42.107
762	scan eta 24.523334151833378 24.563334151833377...	7.2379969847834005	41	46.49960825153573	824927	17T01:25:51.247
763	scan eta 24.52349989866872 24.56349989866872 0...	7.23799920927676	41	46.599652336712225	824928	17T01:27:00.434
764	scan eta 24.52366557157077 24.56366557157077 0...	7.23799920927676	41	46.69973816202156	824929	17T01:28:09.051
765	scan eta 24.523831170038168 24.563831170038167...	7.23799920927676	41	46.79978958207833	824930	17T01:29:18.281
766	scan eta 24.52399669356431 24.56399669356431 0...	7.238001433771541	41	46.89989029555985	824931	17T01:30:27.216
767	scan eta 24.52416214164577 24.56416214164577 0...	7.23799920927676	41	46.99995984249922	824932	17T01:31:35.781
768	scan eta 24.524327513777745 24.564327513777744...	7.238001433771541	41	47.1000034893639	824933	17T01:32:44.416
769	scan eta 24.524492809457374 24.564492809457374...	7.238001433771541	41	47.20007119361821	824934	17T01:33:53.831
770	scan eta 24.524658028180152 24.56465802818015 ...	7.23799920927676	41	47.30013890449202	824935	17T01:35:02.604

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
771	scan eta 24.524823169444023 24.564823169444022...	7.23799920927676	41	47.40022518876345	824936	17T01:36:11.994
772	scan eta 24.524988232744047 24.564988232744046...	7.2379969847834005	41	47.500302053509195	824937	17T01:37:21.957
773	scan eta 24.525153217580797 24.565153217580797...	7.2379969847834005	41	47.60037159015958	824938	17T01:38:33.307
774	scan eta 24.52531812344777 24.56531812344777 0...	7.2379969847834005	41	47.700413405450725	824939	17T01:39:44.525
775	scan eta 24.525482949845124 24.565482949845123...	7.238003658267745	41	47.79951069115755	824940	17T01:40:55.665
776	scan eta 24.52564769626962 24.565647696269618 ...	7.23799920927676	41	47.89958573076085	824941	17T01:42:07.948
777	scan eta 24.525812362220268 24.565812362220267...	7.238001433771541	41	47.99962384776605	824942	17T01:43:20.087
778	scan eta 24.517229248338534 24.557229248338533...	7.239004825923798	41	44.99971943901923	824943	17T01:44:36.926
779	scan eta 24.51739604343936 24.557396043439358 ...	7.2390026007873525	41	45.099752089370476	824944	17T01:45:48.448
780	scan eta 24.517562772203117 24.557562772203116...	7.239000375652332	41	45.19983833900792	824945	17T01:47:01.002
781	scan eta 24.517729434124693 24.557729434124692...	7.239000375652332	41	45.29989687449553	824946	17T01:48:13.675
782	scan eta 24.517896028694626 24.557896028694625...	7.238998150518732	41	45.39992766396857	824947	17T01:49:26.436
783	scan eta 24.518062555406704 24.558062555406703...	7.2390026007873525	41	45.49998805947606	824948	17T01:50:38.056
784	scan eta 24.518229013753068 24.558229013753067...	7.239000375652332	41	45.60004842617511	824949	17T01:51:50.555
785	scan eta 24.518395403225693 24.558395403225692...	7.239004825923798	41	45.70010878978973	824950	17T01:53:02.762
786	scan eta 24.518561723319248 24.558561723319247...	7.2390026007873525	41	45.80015470057851	824951	17T01:54:14.4

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
787	24.51872797352726 24.558727973527258 ...	7.2390026007873525	41	45.90025542155536	824952	20 17T01:55:25.382
	scan eta					
788	24.51889415334099 24.55889415334099 0...	7.2390026007873525	41	46.00029356637683	824953	20 17T01:56:36.919
	scan eta					
789	24.51906026225714 24.559060262257137 ...	7.239000375652332	41	46.10035393344676	824954	20 17T01:57:49.136
	scan eta					
790	24.519226299767514 24.559226299767513...	7.2390026007873525	41	46.20044569917312	824955	20 17T01:59:01.061
	scan eta					
791	24.519392265367134 24.559392265367133...	7.238998150518732	41	46.29948038493185	824956	20 17T02:00:14.262
	scan eta					
792	24.519558158550215 24.559558158550214...	7.238995925386555	41	46.399571945480375	824957	20 17T02:01:26.571
	scan eta					
793	24.519723978812376 24.559723978812375...	7.239000375652332	41	46.499610086123965	824958	20 17T02:02:37.975
	scan eta					
794	24.519889725646724 24.559889725646723...	7.238995925386555	41	46.59970185632621	824959	20 17T02:03:49.408
	scan eta					
795	24.52005539854977 24.560055398549768 ...	7.238995925386555	41	46.69973816040886	824960	20 17T02:05:00.456
	scan eta					
796	24.52022099701718 24.56022099701718 0...	7.239000375652332	41	46.79979508163805	824961	20 17T02:06:12.433
	scan eta					
797	24.5203865205423 24.5603865205423 0.0...	7.238998150518732	41	46.899869905888195	824962	20 17T02:07:23.926
	scan eta					
798	24.52055196862376 24.56055196862376 0...	7.239000375652332	41	46.999935776723255	824963	20 17T02:08:36.549
	scan eta					
799	24.52071734075575 24.560717340755748 ...	7.238998150518732	41	47.10002022658675	824964	20 17T02:09:47.901
	scan eta					
800	24.520882636435363 24.560882636435363...	7.239000375652332	41	47.20009893685173	824965	20 17T02:10:59.676

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
801	scan eta 24.521047855158155 24.561047855158154...	7.2390026007873525	41	47.300159309960385	824966	17T02:12:11.666
802	scan eta 24.521212996422026 24.561212996422025...	7.238995925386555	41	47.40020660960594	824967	17T02:13:22.277
803	scan eta 24.52137805972306 24.561378059723058 ...	7.238995925386555	41	47.50029289019333	824968	17T02:14:33.04
804	scan eta 24.5215430445588 24.5615430445588 0.0...	7.239000375652332	41	47.60036426046267	824969	17T02:15:45.259
805	scan eta 24.521707950425775 24.561707950425774...	7.2390026007873525	41	47.70043930398828	824970	17T02:16:56.766
806	scan eta 24.521872776824136 24.561872776824135...	7.239000375652332	41	47.79951435483351	824971	17T02:18:09.289
807	scan eta 24.52203752324863 24.56203752324863 0...	7.2390026007873525	41	47.899571074489096	824972	17T02:19:23.066
808	scan eta 24.522202189199266 24.562202189199265...	7.2390026007873525	41	47.9996238479189	824973	17T02:20:36.309
809	scan eta 24.513620176297533 24.55362017629753 ...	7.240004055972707	41	44.999693559827826	824974	17T02:21:54.399
810	scan eta 24.513786971398357 24.553786971398356...	7.23999960442306	41	45.099752086753945	824975	17T02:23:07.619
811	scan eta 24.513953700162116 24.553953700162115...	7.23999960442306	41	45.19983650058655	824976	17T02:24:20.102
812	scan eta 24.51412036208369 24.55412036208369 0...	7.23999960442306	41	45.29988586977375	824977	17T02:25:33.364
813	scan eta 24.514286956653624 24.554286956653623...	7.240001830197173	41	45.39992768877394	824978	17T02:26:46.307
814	scan eta 24.514453483365703 24.5544534833657 0...	7.23999960442306	41	45.499988054704154	824979	17T02:27:59.436
815	scan eta 24.514619941712066 24.554619941712065...	7.240001830197173	41	45.600066979624884	824980	17T02:29:12.769

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
816	scan eta 24.514786331185686 24.554786331185685...	7.23999960442306	41	45.70012918218482	824981	20 17T02:30:25.941
817	scan eta 24.514952651278247 24.554952651278246...	7.23999960442306	41	45.800169161319204	824982	20 17T02:31:38.5
818	scan eta 24.515118901486257 24.555118901486257...	7.240001830197173	41	45.900260922538855	824983	20 17T02:32:49.785
819	scan eta 24.51528508129999 24.55528508129999 0...	7.23999960442306	41	46.000319458603	824984	20 17T02:33:59.15
820	scan eta 24.515451190216137 24.555451190216136...	7.23999960442306	41	46.100332144401214	824985	20 17T02:35:08.26
821	scan eta 24.515617227726512 24.55561722772651 ...	7.23999960442306	41	46.200417970435765	824986	20 17T02:36:17.793
822	scan eta 24.515783193326133 24.555783193326132...	7.23999960442306	41	46.29950423516306	824987	20 17T02:37:27.703
823	scan eta 24.515949086509213 24.555949086509212...	7.239997378650371	41	46.39957010139358	824988	20 17T02:38:36.652
824	scan eta 24.516114906771374 24.556114906771374...	7.23999960442306	41	46.49961008951926	824989	20 17T02:39:45.607
825	scan eta 24.516280653605723 24.55628065360572 ...	7.240001830197173	41	46.59970552156132	824990	20 17T02:40:54.838
826	scan eta 24.516446326508767 24.556446326508766...	7.240001830197173	41	46.69976222271973	824991	20 17T02:42:03.391
827	scan eta 24.51661192497618 24.556611924976178 ...	7.239997378650371	41	46.799824430893324	824992	20 17T02:43:12.773
828	scan eta 24.516777448502307 24.556777448502306...	7.23999960442306	41	46.899892145264076	824993	20 17T02:44:22.712
829	scan eta 24.516942896582773 24.556942896582772...	7.240004055972707	41	46.999935782388164	824994	20 17T02:45:31.909
830	scan eta 24.517108268714747 24.557108268714746...	7.240001830197173	41	47.100003493862694	824995	20 17T02:46:39.891
831	scan eta 24.51727356439537 24.55727356439537 0...	7.23999960442306	41	47.20007117225475	824996	20 17T02:47:48.262

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
832	scan eta 24.517438783117154 24.557438783117153...	7.23999960442306	41	47.30016113928425	824997	20 17T02:48:56.558
833	scan eta 24.517603924382033 24.557603924382033...	7.23999960442306	41	47.400228837888186	824998	20 17T02:50:07.417
834	scan eta 24.517768987682057 24.557768987682056...	7.23999960442306	41	47.500296566220435	824999	20 17T02:51:16.976
835	scan eta 24.5179339725178 24.557933972517798 0...	7.240001830197173	41	47.60036793417343	825000	20 17T02:52:25.23
836	scan eta 24.518098878385768 24.558098878385767...	7.240004055972707	41	47.70041338195052	825001	20 17T02:53:34.49
837	scan eta 24.518263704783134 24.558263704783133...	7.23999960442306	41	47.79948295178657	825002	20 17T02:54:44.325
838	scan eta 24.51842845120763 24.55842845120763 0...	7.239997378650371	41	47.89957656681158	825003	20 17T02:55:52.503
839	scan eta 24.518593117158265 24.558593117158264...	7.240001830197173	41	47.99964427878547	825004	20 17T02:57:01.873
840	scan eta 24.510012204715533 24.550012204715532...	7.241001346619088	41	44.99971759594522	825005	20 17T02:58:14.862
841	scan eta 24.510178999815363 24.550178999815362...	7.240999120205616	41	45.09975209102194	825006	20 17T02:59:24.058
842	scan eta 24.510345728580116 24.550345728580115...	7.241001346619088	41	45.19982916791977	825007	20 17T03:00:34.535
843	scan eta 24.510512390500683 24.550512390500682...	7.241003573033985	41	45.29988954916004	825008	20 17T03:01:43.29
844	scan eta 24.510678985071625 24.550678985071624...	7.240996893793569	41	45.3999276875812	825009	20 17T03:02:51.924
845	scan eta 24.510845511783703 24.550845511783702...	7.240996893793569	41	45.499969927259414	825010	20 17T03:04:00.511
846	scan eta 24.511011970129058 24.551011970129057...	7.240996893793569	41	45.600022962997976	825011	20 17T03:05:08.458
847	scan eta 24.51117835960269 24.55117835960269 0...	7.241005799450305	41	45.70010695794384	825012	20 17T03:06:16.549

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
848	scan eta 24.511344679696247 24.551344679696246...	7.241001346619088	41	45.80016916139659	825013	20 17T03:07:26.495
849	scan eta 24.51151092990325 24.551510929903248 ...	7.240996893793569	41	45.90025725106323	825014	20 17T03:08:35.185
850	scan eta 24.51167710971698 24.55167710971698 0...	7.240999120205616	41	46.00029172763892	825015	20 17T03:09:45.128
851	scan eta 24.511843218633143 24.55184321863314 ...	7.240999120205616	41	46.10035577128987	825016	20 17T03:10:54.472
852	scan eta 24.512009256143518 24.552009256143517...	7.241001346619088	41	46.20044569509716	825017	20 17T03:12:03.395
853	scan eta 24.51217522174314 24.552175221743138 ...	7.241001346619088	41	46.29950239987273	825018	20 17T03:13:12.886
854	scan eta 24.512341114926205 24.552341114926204...	7.241003573033985	41	46.39956277125249	825019	20 17T03:14:21.249
855	scan eta 24.51250693518838 24.55250693518838 0...	7.241003573033985	41	46.499608245971224	825020	20 17T03:15:29.733
856	scan eta 24.512672682023723 24.552672682023722...	7.241001346619088	41	46.59969085024777	825021	20 17T03:16:38.977
857	scan eta 24.512838354925773 24.552838354925772...	7.240999120205616	41	46.69973816346249	825022	20 17T03:17:48.135
858	scan eta 24.51300395339317 24.55300395339317 0...	7.241001346619088	41	46.79982260196111	825023	20 17T03:18:57.813
859	scan eta 24.513169476919312 24.55316947691931 ...	7.241001346619088	41	46.89987011741279	825024	20 17T03:20:10.158
860	scan eta 24.51333492500076 24.553334925000758 ...	7.240999120205616	41	46.99993578691245	825025	20 17T03:21:19.675
861	scan eta 24.513500297132747 24.553500297132747...	7.240999120205616	41	47.10000348770374	825026	20 17T03:22:29.049
862	scan eta 24.513665592812362 24.55366559281236 ...	7.240999120205616	41	47.200091597270834	825027	20 17T03:23:37.635

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
863	scan eta 24.513830811535154 24.553830811535153...	7.241003573033985	41	47.30016296648559	825028	17T03:24:46.597
864	scan eta 24.513995952799025 24.553995952799024...	7.240996893793569	41	47.40020661272467	825029	17T03:25:54.335
865	scan eta 24.51416101609905 24.554161016099048 ...	7.240999120205616	41	47.50030205036889	825030	17T03:27:02.951
866	scan eta 24.5143260009358 24.5543260009358 0.0...	7.240996893793569	41	47.60036793988351	825031	17T03:28:12.902
867	scan eta 24.514490906802774 24.554490906802773...	7.240996893793569	41	47.70041340648203	825032	17T03:29:21.681
868	scan eta 24.514655733200126 24.554655733200125...	7.240999120205616	41	47.799468503366704	825033	17T03:30:30.479
869	scan eta 24.51482047962462 24.55482047962462 0...	7.240994667382945	41	47.89957473513832	825034	17T03:31:38.738
870	scan eta 24.51498514557527 24.55498514557527 0...	7.240996893793569	41	47.99965344429903	825035	17T03:32:47.243
871	scan eta 24.506405333068525 24.546405333068524...	7.242001150175058	41	44.99969355388604	825036	17T03:34:00.089
872	scan eta 24.506572128169363 24.546572128169363...	7.2419989231219555	41	45.09975023058395	825037	17T03:35:08.473
873	scan eta 24.506738856933122 24.54673885693312 ...	7.241996696070274	41	45.199834668724336	825038	17T03:36:16.898
874	scan eta 24.506905518854683 24.546905518854683...	7.2419989231219555	41	45.2998877110824	825039	17T03:37:25.06
875	scan eta 24.50707211342463 24.54707211342463 0...	7.242005604285542	41	45.39995173736264	825040	17T03:38:33.185
876	scan eta 24.50723864013671 24.547238640136708 ...	7.242001150175058	41	45.49998805333998	825041	17T03:39:42.509
877	scan eta 24.50740509848306 24.547405098483058 ...	7.241996696070274	41	45.60005597346994	825042	17T03:40:51.123

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
878	scan eta 24.507571487955683 24.547571487955683...	7.2419989231219555	41	45.70011062141444	825043	20 17T03:42:00.298
879	scan eta 24.507737808049253 24.547737808049252...	7.242003377229588	41	45.80019321453826	825044	20 17T03:43:09.09
880	scan eta 24.50790405825725 24.54790405825725 0...	7.2419989231219555	41	45.900231360738466	825045	20 17T03:44:17.398
881	scan eta 24.50807023807098 24.54807023807098 0...	7.241996696070274	41	46.00032312606085	825046	20 17T03:45:25.689
882	scan eta 24.508236346987143 24.548236346987142...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.10035576809227	825047	20 17T03:46:34.916
883	scan eta 24.50840238449752 24.548402384497518 ...	7.241996696070274	41	46.200442028242506	825048	20 17T03:47:43.138
884	scan eta 24.50856835009714 24.54856835009714 0...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.29948201040218	825049	20 17T03:48:51.523
885	scan eta 24.508734243280205 24.548734243280204...	7.241996696070274	41	46.39954442089977	825050	20 17T03:50:00.047
886	scan eta 24.508900063541372 24.54890006354137 ...	7.242001150175058	41	46.49963597646931	825051	20 17T03:51:08.998
887	scan eta 24.509065810376715 24.549065810376714...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.59967412311379	825052	20 17T03:52:18.267
888	scan eta 24.509231483279773 24.549231483279772...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.69973816064744	825053	20 17T03:53:27.327
889	scan eta 24.50939708174717 24.54939708174717 0...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.79982992837076	825054	20 17T03:54:36.962
890	scan eta 24.509562605272304 24.549562605272303...	7.2419989231219555	41	46.899869906128224	825055	20 17T03:55:46.639
891	scan eta 24.509728053353765 24.549728053353764...	7.241996696070274	41	46.99993761677264	825056	20 17T03:56:55.594
892	scan eta 24.50989342548574 24.549893425485738 ...	7.242001150175058	41	47.100003486191035	825057	20 17T03:58:04.51

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
893	scan eta 24.510058721165368 24.550058721165367...	7.2419989231219555	41	47.200071198478945	825058	20 17T03:59:13.69
894	scan eta 24.510223939888146 24.550223939888145...	7.2419989231219555	41	47.300170303096536	825059	20 17T04:00:23.339
895	scan eta 24.51038908115203 24.55038908115203 0...	7.241996696070274	41	47.40020661119794	825060	20 17T04:01:33.228
896	scan eta 24.51055414445305 24.55055414445305 0...	7.2419989231219555	41	47.50026537156204	825061	20 17T04:02:42.509
897	scan eta 24.51071912928879 24.55071912928879 0...	7.242003377229588	41	47.60037526064523	825062	20 17T04:03:52.097
898	scan eta 24.510884035155765 24.550884035155764...	7.242003377229588	41	47.700442982327644	825063	20 17T04:05:01.497
899	scan eta 24.511048861554126 24.551048861554126...	7.2419989231219555	41	47.79948295487438	825064	20 17T04:06:09.757
900	scan eta 24.511213607978622 24.55121360797862 ...	7.2419989231219555	41	47.89957840083148	825065	20 17T04:07:19.75
901	scan eta 24.51137827392927 24.55137827392927 0...	7.242001150175058	41	47.999646105705075	825066	20 17T04:08:28.951
902	scan eta 24.502799560836532 24.54279956083653 ...	7.2429990132941	41	44.99966809162806	825067	20 17T04:09:42.168
903	scan eta 24.502966355937357 24.542966355937356...	7.243003468681541	41	45.099750253596106	825068	20 17T04:10:52.712
904	scan eta 24.503133084701116 24.543133084701115...	7.2429990132941	41	45.19980878964644	825069	20 17T04:12:04.272
905	scan eta 24.50329974662269 24.54329974662269 0...	7.2429990132941	41	45.29986915154173	825070	20 17T04:13:15.539
906	scan eta 24.503466341192624 24.543466341192623...	7.2429990132941	41	45.399951738252746	825071	20 17T04:14:28.753
907	scan eta 24.503632867904702 24.5436328679047 0...	7.243001240987107	41	45.50006610417614	825072	20 17T04:15:41.246

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
908	scan eta 24.503799326251066 24.543799326251065...	7.2429990132941	41	45.60004842556592	825073	17T04:16:54.866
909	scan eta 24.503965715724686 24.543965715724685...	7.243001240987107	41	45.70010879131348	825074	17T04:18:06.478
910	scan eta 24.504132035817246 24.544132035817245...	7.2429990132941	41	45.800169161238536	825075	17T04:19:19.1
911	scan eta 24.504298286025257 24.544298286025256...	7.243001240987107	41	45.90023133846111	825076	17T04:20:32.35
912	scan eta 24.50446446583899 24.54446446583899 0...	7.2429990132941	41	46.00031578068545	825077	17T04:21:43.989
913	scan eta 24.504630574755137 24.544630574755136...	7.243001240987107	41	46.10035393498935	825078	17T04:22:56.02
914	scan eta 24.504796612265512 24.54479661226551 ...	7.2429990132941	41	46.200417967320824	825079	17T04:24:08.361
915	scan eta 24.504962577865133 24.54496257786513 ...	7.2429990132941	41	46.29948015342157	825080	17T04:25:20.254
916	scan eta 24.505128471048213 24.545128471048212...	7.243001240987107	41	46.39957377297584	825081	17T04:26:33.382
917	scan eta 24.505294291310374 24.545294291310373...	7.243003468681541	41	46.49963964817485	825082	17T04:27:44.843
918	scan eta 24.505460038144722 24.54546003814472 ...	7.243001240987107	41	46.599674123125745	825083	17T04:28:57.228
919	scan eta 24.505625711047767 24.545625711047766...	7.242996785602517	41	46.69976222126524	825084	17T04:30:11.057
920	scan eta 24.50579130951518 24.545791309515177 ...	7.243001240987107	41	46.79983176380666	825085	17T04:31:22.827
921	scan eta 24.505956833041306 24.545956833041306...	7.243001240987107	41	46.89986991411383	825086	17T04:32:34.785
922	scan eta 24.506122281121772 24.54612228112177 ...	7.243001240987107	41	46.99993577963968	825087	17T04:33:47.274
923	scan eta 24.506287653253747 24.546287653253746...	7.2429990132941	41	47.10002388759929	825088	17T04:35:00.749

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
924	scan eta 24.50645294893336 24.54645294893336 0...	7.242996785602517	41	47.20007119670321	825089	17T04:36:13.444
925	scan eta 24.506618167656153 24.546618167656153...	7.243001240987107	41	47.30013890265654	825090	17T04:37:25.016
926	scan eta 24.506783308920024 24.546783308920023...	7.243003468681541	41	47.40023984698919	825091	17T04:38:38.438
927	scan eta 24.506948372221057 24.546948372221056...	7.243003468681541	41	47.500296553979865	825092	17T04:39:50.824
928	scan eta 24.5071133570568 24.547113357056798 0...	7.2429990132941	41	47.60034386077412	825093	17T04:41:02.756
929	scan eta 24.507278262923773 24.547278262923772...	7.2429990132941	41	47.700437474843376	825094	17T04:42:15.629
930	scan eta 24.507443089322134 24.547443089322133...	7.2429990132941	41	47.799503353237995	825095	17T04:43:27.714
931	scan eta 24.50760783574663 24.54760783574663 0...	7.243001240987107	41	47.89955432845052	825096	17T04:44:40.102
932	scan eta 24.507772501697264 24.547772501697263...	7.243003468681541	41	47.99964428296304	825097	17T04:45:53.239
933	scan eta 24.49919488749853 24.539194887498528 ...	7.244003847511943	41	44.99969355366801	825098	17T04:47:09.646
934	scan eta 24.49936168259836 24.539361682598358 ...	7.243999390844148	41	45.09975023036614	825099	17T04:48:22.315
935	scan eta 24.499528411363126 24.539528411363126...	7.244006075847979	41	45.19983100103282	825100	17T04:49:33.543
936	scan eta 24.499695073283693 24.539695073283692...	7.243999390844148	41	45.29989320133681	825101	17T04:50:47.194
937	scan eta 24.49986166785462 24.53986166785462 0...	7.244001619177332	41	45.399927687192864	825102	17T04:52:00.391
938	scan eta 24.5000281945667 24.5400281945667 0.0...	7.24399716251239	41	45.5000047770877	825103	17T04:53:12.619

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
939	scan eta 24.500194652912068 24.540194652912067...	7.243999390844148	41	45.600046566319975	825104	20 17T04:54:26.394
940	scan eta 24.500361042385688 24.540361042385687...	7.243999390844148	41	45.70013285425782	825105	20 17T04:55:38.916
941	scan eta 24.500527362479243 24.540527362479242...	7.244001619177332	41	45.800167531394244	825106	20 17T04:56:51.36
942	scan eta 24.50069361268626 24.54069361268626 0...	7.243999390844148	41	45.900231338654	825107	20 17T04:58:04.356
943	scan eta 24.50085979249999 24.54085979249999 0...	7.24399716251239	41	46.000293567678725	825108	20 17T04:59:17.142
944	scan eta 24.50102590141614 24.541025901416138 ...	7.244003847511943	41	46.100344977182104	825109	20 17T05:00:30.326
945	scan eta 24.501191938926514 24.541191938926513...	7.243999390844148	41	46.200436535866025	825110	20 17T05:01:43.693
946	scan eta 24.501357904526134 24.541357904526134...	7.244001619177332	41	46.29950240532252	825111	20 17T05:02:56.847
947	scan eta 24.501523797709215 24.541523797709214...	7.244001619177332	41	46.399537091338004	825112	20 17T05:04:10.347
948	scan eta 24.501689617971376 24.541689617971375...	7.244001619177332	41	46.49960825169125	825113	20 17T05:05:22.447
949	scan eta 24.50185536480672 24.541855364806718 ...	7.243999390844148	41	46.59970552122559	825114	20 17T05:06:33.002
950	scan eta 24.50202103770877 24.542021037708768 ...	7.24399716251239	41	46.6997603979254	825115	20 17T05:07:44.038
951	scan eta 24.50218663617618 24.54218663617618 0...	7.243999390844148	41	46.799822595132554	825116	20 17T05:08:52.796
952	scan eta 24.50235215970231 24.542352159702308 ...	7.244001619177332	41	46.89989396245987	825117	20 17T05:10:01.056

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
953	scan eta 24.50251760778377 24.54251760778377 0...	7.24399716251239	41	46.99993578072808	825118	20 17T05:11:09.986
954	scan eta 24.502682979915743 24.542682979915742...	7.243999390844148	41	47.10000348907675	825119	20 17T05:12:19.587
955	scan eta 24.502848275595372 24.54284827559537 ...	7.24399716251239	41	47.20007119243706	825120	20 17T05:13:28.539
956	scan eta 24.50301349431815 24.54301349431815 0...	7.243999390844148	41	47.30016847992401	825121	20 17T05:14:37.964
957	scan eta 24.50317863558202 24.54317863558202 0...	7.243999390844148	41	47.400232513636276	825122	20 17T05:15:47.346
958	scan eta 24.50334369888206 24.543343698882058 ...	7.244001619177332	41	47.50026906003918	825123	20 17T05:16:56.264
959	scan eta 24.503508683718795 24.543508683718795...	7.243999390844148	41	47.60036427265374	825124	20 17T05:18:05.127
960	scan eta 24.50367358958577 24.54367358958577 0...	7.243999390844148	41	47.700435645175176	825125	20 17T05:19:13.443
961	scan eta 24.503838415983136 24.543838415983135...	7.24399716251239	41	47.7994829532713	825126	20 17T05:20:22.349
962	scan eta 24.50400316240763 24.54400316240763 0...	7.243999390844148	41	47.899576575447355	825127	20 17T05:21:31.843
963	scan eta 24.504167828358266 24.544167828358265...	7.243999390844148	41	47.999647950960245	825128	20 17T05:22:40.663
964	scan eta 24.495591312531527 24.535591312531526...	7.245000055894261	41	44.99971210105186	825129	20 17T05:23:55.258
965	scan eta 24.49575810763235 24.53575810763235 0...	7.245000055894261	41	45.09975206339344	825130	20 17T05:25:04.269
966	scan eta 24.495924836396124 24.535924836396124...	7.244997826922054	41	45.19983467673961	825131	20 17T05:26:13.467
967	scan eta 24.496091498317686 24.536091498317685...	7.245000055894261	41	45.29986915336547	825132	20 17T05:27:22.458

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
968	24.49625809288762 24.536258092887618 ...	7.245000055894261	41	45.39992768587115	825133	20 17T05:28:32.156
	scan eta					
969	24.49642461959971 24.53642461959971 0...	7.244997826922054	41	45.50000661144259	825134	20 17T05:29:42.156
	scan eta					
970	24.49659107794606 24.53659107794606 0...	7.244997826922054	41	45.600068807475196	825135	20 17T05:30:51.132
	scan eta					
971	24.496757467419695 24.536757467419694...	7.244997826922054	41	45.70012551827287	825136	20 17T05:32:00.001
	scan eta					
972	24.49692378751224 24.53692378751224 0...	7.244995597951275	41	45.800169158380335	825137	20 17T05:33:08.286
	scan eta					
973	24.497090037720252 24.53709003772025 ...	7.244997826922054	41	45.90025725505708	825138	20 17T05:34:17.799
	scan eta					
974	24.497256217533984 24.537256217533983...	7.245000055894261	41	46.00029172891222	825139	20 17T05:35:27.079
	scan eta					
975	24.497422326450145 24.537422326450145...	7.245002284867894	41	46.10038899505548	825140	20 17T05:36:35.804
	scan eta					
976	24.49758836396052 24.53758836396052 0...	7.245002284867894	41	46.200417947998645	825141	20 17T05:37:46.334
	scan eta					
977	24.497754329560127 24.537754329560126...	7.245000055894261	41	46.299460221045486	825142	20 17T05:38:56.329
	scan eta					
978	24.497920222743208 24.537920222743207...	7.2449933689819215	41	46.39954259019307	825143	20 17T05:40:07.599
	scan eta					
979	24.49808604300537 24.538086043005368 ...	7.245002284867894	41	46.49960825163651	825144	20 17T05:41:17.079
	scan eta					
980	24.498251789839717 24.538251789839716...	7.245000055894261	41	46.599674120197996	825145	20 17T05:42:25.009
	scan eta					
981	24.498417462742776 24.538417462742775...	7.245002284867894	41	46.69973816520456	825146	20 17T05:43:33.468
	scan eta					
982	24.498583061210173 24.538583061210172...	7.245002284867894	41	46.79980401155579	825147	20 17T05:44:42.329

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
983	scan eta 24.4987485847363 24.5387485847363 0.0...	7.245000055894261	41	46.89986990584181	825148	20 17T05:45:50.991
984	scan eta 24.498914032816767 24.538914032816766...	7.245002284867894	41	46.99992132913586	825149	20 17T05:47:00.432
985	scan eta 24.49907940494874 24.53907940494874 0...	7.245000055894261	41	47.100003487239036	825150	20 17T05:48:10.333
986	scan eta 24.49924470062837 24.53924470062837 0...	7.245000055894261	41	47.2000711964019	825151	20 17T05:49:19.431
987	scan eta 24.499409919351148 24.539409919351147...	7.245002284867894	41	47.30013890594022	825152	20 17T05:50:29.412
988	scan eta 24.499575060615033 24.539575060615032...	7.245004513842955	41	47.40023251590745	825153	20 17T05:51:38.039
989	scan eta 24.49974012391605 24.53974012391605 0...	7.245004513842955	41	47.50027432162884	825154	20 17T05:52:46.32
990	scan eta 24.499905108751793 24.539905108751793...	7.245004513842955	41	47.600364268375984	825155	20 17T05:53:54.143
991	scan eta 24.500070014619762 24.54007001461976 ...	7.245000055894261	41	47.70041340238106	825156	20 17T05:55:02.785
992	scan eta 24.50023484101713 24.540234841017128 ...	7.245000055894261	41	47.79948295685633	825157	20 17T05:56:12.696
993	scan eta 24.500399587441624 24.540399587441623...	7.245000055894261	41	47.899572907142904	825158	20 17T05:57:21.716
994	scan eta 24.50056425339226 24.540564253392258 ...	7.244997826922054	41	47.99964978550427	825159	20 17T05:58:31.018
995	scan eta 24.49198883541653 24.53198883541653 0...	7.246003238181028	41	44.99969355499406	825160	20 17T05:59:44.293
996	scan eta 24.492155630517356 24.532155630517355...	7.246001008566673	41	45.09977613300988	825161	20 17T06:00:53.326

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
997	24.49232235928113 24.532322359281128 ...	7.246001008566673	41	45.19983101290179	825162	20 17T06:02:02.91
	scan eta					
998	24.49248902120269 24.53248902120269 0...	7.246001008566673	41	45.29989137271009	825163	20 17T06:03:12.019
	scan eta					
999	24.492655615773632 24.53265561577363 ...	7.246003238181028	41	45.39995174291994	825164	20 17T06:04:20.901
	scan eta					
1000	24.49282214248571 24.53282214248571 0...	7.246003238181028	41	45.49998805319242	825165	20 17T06:05:29.452
	scan eta					
1001	24.492988600831065 24.532988600831064...	7.246003238181028	41	45.60004658805297	825166	20 17T06:06:38.094
	scan eta					
1002	24.493154990304685 24.533154990304684...	7.246001008566673	41	45.700108792434285	825167	20 17T06:07:46.637
	scan eta					
1003	24.493321310397246 24.533321310397245...	7.246001008566673	41	45.80016916107786	825168	20 17T06:08:56.066
	scan eta					
1004	24.493487560605256 24.533487560605256...	7.2459943197321754	41	45.900229734607386	825169	20 17T06:10:06.452
	scan eta					
1005	24.49365374041899 24.533653740418988 ...	7.246001008566673	41	46.00029356344436	825170	20 17T06:11:16.471
	scan eta					
1006	24.493819849335136 24.533819849335135...	7.246001008566673	41	46.10035576967097	825171	20 17T06:12:26.2
	scan eta					
1007	24.49398588684551 24.53398588684551 0...	7.246003238181028	41	46.200417970191545	825172	20 17T06:13:35.475
	scan eta					
1008	24.494151852445132 24.53415185244513 ...	7.246001008566673	41	46.29948015369224	825173	20 17T06:14:44.338
	scan eta					
1009	24.494317745628212 24.53431774562821 ...	7.246001008566673	41	46.39956827163483	825174	20 17T06:15:53.18
	scan eta					
1010	24.494483565890373 24.534483565890373...	7.246001008566673	41	46.49963231323806	825175	20 17T06:17:02.533
	scan eta					
1011	24.494649312725716 24.534649312725715...	7.245996549342248	41	46.59967412471644	825176	20 17T06:18:11.124

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1012	scan eta 24.494814985627766 24.534814985627765...	7.246003238181028	41	46.69976222337515	825177	17T06:19:19.534
1013	scan eta 24.494980584095178 24.534980584095177...	7.246003238181028	41	46.79980403283442	825178	17T06:20:29.059
1014	scan eta 24.495146107621306 24.535146107621305...	7.245998778953747	41	46.89986991040258	825179	17T06:21:38.694
1015	scan eta 24.49531155570177 24.53531155570177 0...	7.245996549342248	41	46.999959847346275	825180	17T06:22:49.053
1016	scan eta 24.49547692783474 24.53547692783474 0...	7.246001008566673	41	47.10003305777775	825181	17T06:23:58.192
1017	scan eta 24.49564222351437 24.53564222351437 0...	7.246001008566673	41	47.20007119698249	825182	17T06:25:07.769
1018	scan eta 24.495807442237147 24.535807442237147...	7.245998778953747	41	47.30015746992767	825183	17T06:26:16.388
1019	scan eta 24.495972583501032 24.53597258350103 ...	7.246001008566673	41	47.40022884553864	825184	17T06:27:24.891
1020	scan eta 24.496137646801056 24.536137646801055...	7.246003238181028	41	47.5003057210137	825185	17T06:28:33.668
1021	scan eta 24.496302631637793 24.536302631637792...	7.245998778953747	41	47.600371597897635	825186	17T06:29:43.499
1022	scan eta 24.496467537504767 24.536467537504766...	7.246001008566673	41	47.7004134065981	825187	17T06:30:52.888
1023	scan eta 24.496632363902133 24.536632363902132...	7.245992090123532	41	47.799482947436424	825188	17T06:32:02.741
1024	scan eta 24.49679711032663 24.536797110326628 ...	7.246001008566673	41	47.899552495554865	825189	17T06:33:11.644
1025	scan eta 24.496961776277264 24.536961776277263...	7.246001008566673	41	47.99964978232602	825190	17T06:34:20.665
1026	scan eta 24.488387455633525 24.528387455633524...	7.247000018729767	41	44.99971944158905	825191	17T06:35:33.033

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1027	scan eta 24.488554250734364 24.528554250734363...	7.247000018729767	41	45.099777972056216	825192	17T06:36:41.986
1028	scan eta 24.488720979498122 24.52872097949812 ...	7.247000018729767	41	45.19980878979302	825193	17T06:37:50.295
1029	scan eta 24.488887641419684 24.528887641419683...	7.246997788477277	41	45.29990237545459	825194	17T06:38:58.693
1030	scan eta 24.48905423598963 24.52905423598963 0...	7.247000018729767	41	45.39992788769972	825195	17T06:40:08.534
1031	scan eta 24.48922076270171 24.52922076270171 0...	7.247000018729767	41	45.50001944262766	825196	17T06:41:18.05
1032	scan eta 24.48938722104806 24.529387221048058 ...	7.247002248983686	41	45.600048421032106	825197	17T06:42:27.483
1033	scan eta 24.489553610520684 24.529553610520683...	7.247002248983686	41	45.700103294296945	825198	17T06:43:36.603
1034	scan eta 24.489719930614253 24.529719930614252...	7.246995558226215	41	45.800196871133515	825199	17T06:44:47.495
1035	scan eta 24.48988618082225 24.52988618082225 0...	7.247000018729767	41	45.900231360470386	825200	17T06:45:58.853
1036	scan eta 24.490052360635982 24.53005236063598 ...	7.246997788477277	41	46.000317621990526	825201	17T06:47:12.757
1037	scan eta 24.490218469552143 24.530218469552143...	7.247000018729767	41	46.10035393211511	825202	17T06:48:26.321
1038	scan eta 24.49038450706252 24.530384507062518 ...	7.246997788477277	41	46.20039618126388	825203	17T06:49:38.274
1039	scan eta 24.490550472662125 24.530550472662124...	7.247000018729767	41	46.29950973954938	825204	17T06:50:51.245
1040	scan eta 24.490716365845206 24.530716365845205...	7.247000018729767	41	46.39956827965477	825205	17T06:52:03.804
1041	scan eta 24.490882186107367 24.530882186107366...	7.247000018729767	41	46.49960825602255	825206	17T06:53:16.071

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1042	scan eta 24.491047932941715 24.531047932941714...	7.247002248983686	41	46.59970368850621	825207	17T06:54:27.654
1043	scan eta 24.491213605844774 24.531213605844773...	7.247000018729767	41	46.69976956399365	825208	17T06:55:40.685
1044	scan eta 24.49137920431217 24.53137920431217 0...	7.246997788477277	41	46.79983726566131	825209	17T06:56:52.875
1045	scan eta 24.491544727837304 24.531544727837304...	7.247002248983686	41	46.89989213477691	825210	17T06:58:05.874
1046	scan eta 24.491710175918765 24.531710175918764...	7.246997788477277	41	46.9999357820151	825211	17T06:59:18.582
1047	scan eta 24.49187554805074 24.53187554805074 0...	7.246997788477277	41	47.100003485913035	825212	17T07:00:30.435
1048	scan eta 24.49204084373037 24.532040843730368 ...	7.247000018729767	41	47.20007117188087	825213	17T07:01:42.344
1049	scan eta 24.492206062453146 24.532206062453145...	7.247002248983686	41	47.300138904157244	825214	17T07:02:54.831
1050	scan eta 24.49237120371703 24.53237120371703 0...	7.247002248983686	41	47.40020661946291	825215	17T07:04:06.861
1051	scan eta 24.49253626701805 24.53253626701805 0...	7.247002248983686	41	47.50029838543647	825216	17T07:05:18.768
1052	scan eta 24.49270125185379 24.53270125185379 0...	7.247000018729767	41	47.6003697706947	825217	17T07:06:31.234
1053	scan eta 24.492866157720766 24.532866157720765...	7.247000018729767	41	47.7004429796833	825218	17T07:07:43.562
1054	scan eta 24.493030984119127 24.533030984119126...	7.246997788477277	41	47.799482953224675	825219	17T07:08:55.652
1055	scan eta 24.493195730543622 24.53319573054362 ...	7.246997788477277	41	47.899552712939936	825220	17T07:10:10.448
1056	scan eta 24.49336039649427 24.53336039649427 0...	7.247000018729767	41	47.999623874382834	825221	17T07:11:23.201

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1057	scan eta 24.484787172661537 24.524787172661537...	7.248003777267671	41	44.99971577421057	825222	17T07:12:39.841
1058	scan eta 24.48495396776236 24.52495396776236 0...	7.247999315478731	41	45.099750256319425	825223	17T07:13:52.167
1059	scan eta 24.48512069652612 24.52512069652612 0...	7.248001546372486	41	45.199808791117405	825224	17T07:15:04.085
1060	scan eta 24.485287358447682 24.52528735844768 ...	7.247999315478731	41	45.29988586684546	825225	17T07:16:16.645
1061	scan eta 24.48545395301763 24.525453953017628 ...	7.2479903919179955	41	45.39994440789019	825226	17T07:17:29.285
1062	scan eta 24.485620479729707 24.525620479729707...	7.248003777267671	41	45.50001393990461	825227	17T07:18:41.675
1063	scan eta 24.485786938076057 24.525786938076056...	7.248006008164284	41	45.60004841981894	825228	17T07:19:54.516
1064	scan eta 24.485953327548682 24.52595332754868 ...	7.247999315478731	41	45.70013651204286	825229	17T07:21:07.734
1065	scan eta 24.48611964764225 24.52611964764225 0...	7.247999315478731	41	45.80016915716931	825230	17T07:22:20.295
1066	scan eta 24.486285897850248 24.526285897850247...	7.247997084586405	41	45.90025358268676	825231	17T07:23:32.951
1067	scan eta 24.48645207766398 24.52645207766398 0...	7.247997084586405	41	46.00029172898592	825232	17T07:24:45.077
1068	scan eta 24.48661818658014 24.52661818658014 0...	7.247997084586405	41	46.10037799198835	825233	17T07:25:58.004
1069	scan eta 24.486784224090517 24.526784224090516...	7.247999315478731	41	46.20041794807253	825234	17T07:27:10.215
1070	scan eta 24.486950189690138 24.526950189690137...	7.247999315478731	41	46.29948201236993	825235	17T07:28:21.932
1071	scan eta 24.487116082873204 24.527116082873203...	7.248003777267671	41	46.39956644660137	825236	17T07:29:35.004

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1072	scan eta 24.48728190313538 24.52728190313538 0...	7.248001546372486	41	46.499608253023894	825237	17T07:30:48.225
1073	scan eta 24.487447649969713 24.527447649969712...	7.247999315478731	41	46.59967412027305	825238	17T07:32:01.669
1074	scan eta 24.48761332287277 24.52761332287277 0...	7.247999315478731	41	46.6997381666011	825239	17T07:33:14.224
1075	scan eta 24.48777892134017 24.52777892134017 0...	7.247999315478731	41	46.79978224926296	825240	17T07:34:26.226
1076	scan eta 24.48794444486631 24.52794444486631 0...	7.248006008164284	41	46.899846289406376	825241	17T07:35:38.453
1077	scan eta 24.488109892946763 24.528109892946762...	7.248006008164284	41	46.999965345334665	825242	17T07:36:51.023
1078	scan eta 24.488275265078737 24.528275265078737...	7.248003777267671	41	47.0999872027625	825243	17T07:38:04.394
1079	scan eta 24.488440560758367 24.528440560758366...	7.248003777267671	41	47.200071196478376	825244	17T07:39:17.85
1080	scan eta 24.48860577948116 24.528605779481158 ...	7.248001546372486	41	47.300138904223765	825245	17T07:40:30.654
1081	scan eta 24.48877092074503 24.52877092074503 0...	7.247999315478731	41	47.40020661098404	825246	17T07:41:43.484
1082	scan eta 24.488935984046048 24.528935984046047...	7.247999315478731	41	47.500305716285226	825247	17T07:42:53.476
1083	scan eta 24.48910096888179 24.52910096888179 0...	7.248003777267671	41	47.60034386371189	825248	17T07:44:03.041
1084	scan eta 24.489265874748764 24.529265874748763...	7.248001546372486	41	47.70043564284726	825249	17T07:45:12.578
1085	scan eta 24.489430701147125 24.529430701147124...	7.247999315478731	41	47.79948294874252	825250	17T07:46:21.451

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
1086	24.48959544757162 24.52959544757162 0...	7.247999315478731	41	47.899554326852055	825251	20 17T07:47:30.428
	scan eta					
1087	24.48976011352227 24.52976011352227 0...	7.247997084586405	41	47.99962570305861	825252	20 17T07:48:39.905
	scan eta					
1088	24.48118798598153 24.52118798598153 0...	7.248996667402759	41	44.99971759668268	825253	20 17T07:49:53.135
	scan eta					
1089	24.481354781082356 24.521354781082355...	7.248996667402759	41	45.099774300129944	825254	20 17T07:51:01.942
	scan eta					
1090	24.48152150984613 24.521521509846128 ...	7.249003362004348	41	45.1998087879939	825255	20 17T07:52:11.055
	scan eta					
1091	24.48168817176769 24.52168817176769 0...	7.248998898935193	41	45.29986915072836	825256	20 17T07:53:19.697
	scan eta					
1092	24.481854766337623 24.521854766337622...	7.248998898935193	41	45.399951738283626	825257	20 17T07:54:28.725
	scan eta					
1093	24.4820212930497 24.5220212930497 0.0...	7.248998898935193	41	45.50001394059765	825258	20 17T07:55:38.039
	scan eta					
1094	24.48218775139507 24.52218775139507 0...	7.249001130469058	41	45.600074315918086	825259	20 17T07:56:47.718
	scan eta					
1095	24.48235414086869 24.52235414086869 0...	7.249001130469058	41	45.70012917991612	825260	20 17T07:57:56.908
	scan eta					
1096	24.482520460962245 24.522520460962244...	7.248998898935193	41	45.800189543052845	825261	20 17T07:59:05.455
	scan eta					
1097	24.482686711169247 24.522686711169246...	7.248998898935193	41	45.90023136163937	825262	20 17T08:00:14.419
	scan eta					
1098	24.482852890983988 24.522852890983987...	7.248998898935193	41	46.0003139525248	825263	20 17T08:01:23.745
	scan eta					
1099	24.48301899989914 24.52301899989914 0...	7.249001130469058	41	46.10035576943126	825264	20 17T08:02:32.915

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
	scan eta					
1100	24.48318503741051 24.52318503741051 0...	7.248996667402759	41	46.200417974720665	825265	17T08:03:42.692
	scan eta					
1101	24.483351003009137 24.523351003009136...	7.248996667402759	41	46.29948017862759	825266	17T08:04:51.824
	scan eta					
1102	24.483516896193212 24.52351689619321 ...	7.248994435871753	41	46.39954421512244	825267	17T08:06:01.109
	scan eta					
1103	24.48368271645438 24.523682716454378 ...	7.248998898935193	41	46.49963965093064	825268	17T08:07:11.04
	scan eta					
1104	24.48384846328972 24.52384846328972 0...	7.249001130469058	41	46.59967412184044	825269	17T08:08:20.424
	scan eta					
1105	24.484014136192766 24.524014136192765...	7.248998898935193	41	46.69975855412142	825270	17T08:09:29.58
	scan eta					
1106	24.484179734660177 24.524179734660176...	7.249003362004348	41	46.79980403435518	825271	17T08:10:38.182
	scan eta					
1107	24.48434525818531 24.52434525818531 0...	7.249001130469058	41	46.89986990882816	825272	17T08:11:46.925
	scan eta					
1108	24.48451070626677 24.52451070626677 0...	7.248998898935193	41	46.99996901142414	825273	17T08:12:55.865
	scan eta					
1109	24.484676078398746 24.524676078398745...	7.248998898935193	41	47.10000349068962	825274	17T08:14:05.366
	scan eta					
1110	24.484841374078375 24.524841374078374...	7.249001130469058	41	47.20009710121668	825275	17T08:15:15.382
	scan eta					
1111	24.485006592801152 24.52500659280115 ...	7.248998898935193	41	47.30013889999989	825276	17T08:16:25.525
	scan eta					
1112	24.485171734065023 24.525171734065022...	7.249001130469058	41	47.400206611241806	825277	17T08:17:34.335
	scan eta					
1113	24.485336797366056 24.525336797366055...	7.248998898935193	41	47.5002965600863	825278	17T08:18:43.828
	scan eta					
1114	24.485501782201798 24.525501782201797...	7.248998898935193	41	47.60034386397125	825279	17T08:19:53.099

	command	incident_energy	length	psi	scan	sta
1115	scan eta 24.485666688068772 24.52566668806877 ...	7.249001130469058	41	47.700413406800195	825280	17T08:21:02.427 20
1116	scan eta 24.485831514466124 24.525831514466123...	7.248998898935193	41	47.7994829517329	825281	17T08:22:11.7 20
1117	scan eta 24.48599626089163 24.525996260891628 ...	7.249001130469058	41	47.899582071958505	825282	17T08:23:21.356 20
1118	scan eta 24.486160926842263 24.526160926842262...	7.248998898935193	41	47.99964611238386	825283	17T08:24:30.768 20

In [18]:

```
# get smallest area for each energy
max_width = 0.01 # ignore wide peaks
res = {}
for scan in range(824168, 825675+1):
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    if len(n.beamOK) == 41: #it's a fine eta scan

        en = round(float(n.nx['entry1/sample/beam/incident_energy']), 3)
        psi = n.nx['entry1/before_scan/psi/psi']

        [centre, fwhm_sd, fwhm_area, xsum, height, area, m, c] = peak(n.eta, n.roi1
        #print(en, centre-np.mean(n.eta), np.max(n.eta)-np.min(n.eta), fwhm_sd, area

        if not np.isnan(fwhm_sd) and fwhm_sd < max_width:

            if en in res.keys():

                if area < res[en]['area']:
                    res[en] = {'area': area, 'fwhm_sd': fwhm_sd, 'fwhm_area': fwhm_a
            else:

                res[en] = {'area': area, 'fwhm_sd': fwhm_sd, 'fwhm_area': fwhm_area,

                #plot(n.eta, n.roi1_sum-n.scroi_bg_sum)

en, cts, psi , centre, fwhm_sd, fwhm_area = [], [], [], [], [], []
for pt in res:
    en += [pt]
    cts += [res[pt]['area']]
    psi += [res[pt]['psi']]
    fwhm_sd += [res[pt]['fwhm_sd']]
    fwhm_area += [res[pt]['fwhm_area']]
    centre += [res[pt]['centre']]

en, cts, psi, fwhm_sd, centre, fwhm_area = np.array(en), np.array(cts), np.array(psi

figure(); plot(en, cts, '-o'); title('area'); grid(1)
figure(); plot(en, psi, '-o'); title('psi'); grid(1)
figure(); plot(en, fwhm_sd, '-o'); title('fwhm_sd'); grid(1)
```

```
figure(); plot(en, fwhm_area, '-o'); title('fwhm_area'); grid(1)
figure(); plot(en, centre, '-o'); title('centre'); grid(1)
```


In [19]:

```
# Look at all eta scans for each energy

#figure()
en = 0
for scan in range(824168, 825675+1):
#for scan in range(824168, 824200+1):
#for scan in range(824168, 824170+1):

    enold = en
    n = pdnx(p % scan)
    en = round(float(n.nx['entry1/sample/beam/incident_energy']), 3)

    if enold - en != 0: #new figure for new energy
        figure()

    psi = n.nx['entry1/before_scan/psi/psi']
    n['psi'] = psi * np.ones(len(n))
    plot((n.eta-np.mean(n.eta))*2 + psi, n.roi1_sum-n.scroi_bg_sum) #eta width doubl
    ylim([0, 2e6])
    title('Energy %.4g keV' % en)
```


In []:

```


```

In [20]:

```

#schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3, [SumMaxPosition
#iw=50; jw=1; schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.)

#scroi_bg = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositi
#iw=13; jw=15; scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+j

# test file - found data ok
p= '/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-1/%i.nxs'
n=pdnx(p % 807001)

#recent file - no data
#p= '/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2/%i.nxs'
#n = pdnx(p % 824166)
#n = pdnx(p % 824168)

print(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.tree)

print(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.data.shape, sum(sum(sum(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.data))) )
print([sum(sum(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.data[i])) for i in range(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.

figure()
imshow(n.nx.entry1.pil3_100k.data[1])

```

pil3_100k:NXdata

```

TimeFromEpoch -> /entry1/instrument/atimetwo/TimeFromEpoch
TimeSec -> /entry1/instrument/etime/TimeSec
count_time -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/count_time
data -> 807001-pilatus3_100k-files/807001.hdf['/entry/instrument/detector/data']
delta -> /entry1/instrument/transformations/delta
gamma -> /entry1/instrument/transformations/gamma
ic1monitor -> /entry1/instrument/ic1monitor/ic1monitor

```

```

kappa -> /entry1/sample/transformations/kappa
maxval -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/maxval
maxx -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/maxx
maxy -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/maxy
mu -> /entry1/sample/transformations/mu
offsetdelta -> /entry1/instrument/transformations/offsetdelta
path -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/path
phi -> /entry1/sample/transformations/phi
rc -> /entry1/instrument/rc/rc
sum -> /entry1/instrument/pil3_100k/sum
theta -> /entry1/sample/transformations/theta
(3, 195, 487) -66
[-22, -22, -22]

```

Out[20]: <matplotlib.image.AxesImage at 0x7f2b6f9d4c88>

```

In [21]: #Official beam time 28-31 July 2020
#Mono problems and power outage - just a few hours to test cvscan script
#p='/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'
p='/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'

```

```

GDA script day30july2020b.py #pil3_thresh=SingleEpicsPositionerSetAndGetOnlyClass('pil3_tresh','BL16I-EA-
PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','BL16I-EA-PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','keV','%.2f',help='Pilatus3 100K
threshold via Epics Jython class') #schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3,
[SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1; schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.))
#scroi_bg = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=13;
jw=15; scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.-16)) sdic = { 'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh':
7.0, 'en_vals': frange(8.38-0.05, 8.38+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l2': {'eres': 7.932, 'ethresh': 6.7, 'en_vals': frange(7.932-0.03,
7.932+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.244, 'ethresh': 6.5, 'en_vals': frange(7.244-0.03, 7.244+0.05, 0.0005)} } l3_peak =
7.244 l3_points = frange(l3_peak-0.03, l3_peak+0.05, 0.001) # 81 points l1_peak = 8.38 #828185 - 830031
(shutter closed due to LN problem) pos atten 0 for ledge in ['l3', 'l1', 'l2']: pos pil3_thresh sdic[ledge]['ethresh']
pos energy sdic[ledge]['eres'] scancn idgap 0.002 21 checkbeam w .5 ic1 go maxval ucalibrate() pos psic 45 pos
hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 61 checkbeam pil3_100k .5 lcroi scroi go maxval scancn chi .05 21 checkbeam
pil3_100k .5 schiroi go maxval hh = hkl() for enval in sdic[ledge]['en_vals']: pos energy enval for psival in

```

```
frange(44, 49, .05): pos psic psival #pos hkl hh note('energy %.3f psi %.3f' % (enval, psival)) #scancn eta .001 41
checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi_bg scroi (delta_val, gamma_val, eta_val, mu_val, chi_val, phi_val, kphi_val) =
simhkl(hh) kth_val = eta_val - eta() + kth() cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03 kth_val+0.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .1
#night04aug2020a.py #u'/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/'
#pil3_thresh=SingleEpicsPositionerSetAndGetOnlyClass('pil3_tresh','BL16I-EA-PILAT-
03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','BL16I-EA-PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','keV', '%.2f', help='Pilatus3 100K threshold
via Epics Jython class') #schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3,
[SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1; schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.))
#scroi_bg = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=13;
jw=15; scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.-16)) sdic = {'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh':
7.0, 'en_vals': frange(8.38-0.05, 8.38+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l2': {'eres': 7.932, 'ethresh': 6.7, 'en_vals': frange(7.932-0.03,
7.932+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.244, 'ethresh': 6.5, 'en_vals': frange(7.244-0.03, 7.244+0.05, 0.0005)} } l3_peak =
7.244 l3_points = frange(l3_peak-0.03, l3_peak+0.05, 0.001) # 81 points l1_peak = 8.38 #830649 pos atten 0 for
ledge in ['l3', 'l1', 'l2']: pos pil3_thresh sdic[ledge]['ethresh'] pos energy sdic[ledge]['eres'] scancn idgap 0.002 21
checkbeam w .5 ic1 go maxval ucalibrate() pos psic 45 pos hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 61 checkbeam pil3_100k .5
lcroi scroi go maxval scancn chi .05 21 checkbeam pil3_100k .5 schiroi go maxval hh = hkl() for enval in
sdic[ledge]['en_vals']: pos energy enval for psival in frange(44, 49, .1): pos psic psival #pos hkl hh note('energy
%.3f psi %.3f' % (enval, psival)) #scancn eta .001 41 checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi_bg scroi (delta_val, gamma_val,
eta_val, mu_val, chi_val, phi_val, kphi_val) = simhkl(hh) kth_val = eta_val - eta() + kth() cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03
kth_val+0.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .04
```

```
In [22]: #scan timing tests
# cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03 kth_val+0.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .1 ## 21 sec/scan (12
# cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03 kth_val+0.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .02 ## 12 sec (2.4 sec
# cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03 kth_val+0.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .05 ## 14 sec (5 sec c
# time in days
#(160 + 200) * 100 * 14. /3600/24
#~ 3 days with 0.1 deg psi instead of 0.05
```

Files: 830649 - 838862 ok - all l3 data 839264 (e=8.3335, psi = 45.0) - 839335 (e = 8.3345, psi = 45) no data
841313 scan stopped with no beam - probably went off several scans before.. xxx - xxx energy xxx - xxx

In []:

In []:

Previous scans did not move chi and phi - start again 843373

```
# previous script had a bug: phi and chi not moved #u'/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/'
#pil3_thresh=SingleEpicsPositionerSetAndGetOnlyClass('pil3_tresh','BL16I-EA-PILAT-
03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','BL16I-EA-PILAT-03:CAM:ThresholdEnergy','keV', '%.2f', help='Pilatus3 100K threshold
via Epics Jython class') #schiroi = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('schiroi', pil3,
[SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=50; jw=1; schiroi.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.))
#scroi_bg = HardwareTriggerableDetectorDataProcessor('scroi_bg', pil3, [SumMaxPositionAndValue()]) iw=13;
jw=15; scroi_bg.setRoi(int(ci-iw/2.),int(cj-jw/2.-16),int(ci+iw/2.),int(cj+jw/2.-16)) sdic = {'l1': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh':
7.0, 'en_vals': frange(8.38-0.05, 8.38+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l1_end': {'eres': 8.38, 'ethresh': 7.0, 'en_vals':
[8.38]+frange(8.384, 8.38+0.05, 0.0005)}, 'l2': {'eres': 7.932, 'ethresh': 6.7, 'en_vals': frange(7.932-0.03, 7.932+0.05,
0.0005)}, 'l3': {'eres': 7.244, 'ethresh': 6.5, 'en_vals': frange(7.244-0.03, 7.244+0.05, 0.0005)} } l3_peak = 7.244
l3_points = frange(l3_peak-0.03, l3_peak+0.05, 0.001) # 81 points l1_peak = 8.38 #843459-849007 # beam
stopped for weekend; #849008- restart - alignment bad? No good peak first energy. Add extra energy for
alignment #849363 - pos atten 0 #for ledge in ['l1', 'l3', 'l2']: for ledge in ['l1_end', 'l3', 'l2']: pos pil3_thresh
sdic[ledge]['ethresh'] pos energy sdic[ledge]['eres'] scancn idgap 0.002 21 checkbeam w .5 ic1 go maxval
ucalibrate() pos psic 45 pos hkl [0, 0, 6] scancn eta .005 61 checkbeam pil3_100k .5 lcroi scroi go maxval scancn
chi .05 21 checkbeam pil3_100k .5 schiroi go maxval hh = hkl() for enval in sdic[ledge]['en_vals']: pos energy
```

```
enval for psival in frange(44, 49, .1): pos psic psival pos hkl hh note('energy %.3f psi %.3f' % (enval, psival))
#scancn eta .001 41 checkbeam pil3 .5 lcroi scroi_bg scroi #(delta_val, gamma_val, eta_val, mu_val, chi_val,
phi_val, kphi_val) = simhkl(hh) #pos chi chi_val phi phi_val eta eta_val #kth_val = eta_val - eta() + kth() kth_val =
kth() checkbeam() cvscan kthZebra kth_val-.03 kth_val+.03 .0005 kthZebraPil3 .04
```

```
In [23]: # Final data sets?

#for i in range(len(scan)):
#    print('%i\t%.3f' % (scan[i], en[i]))

#L1: 8.33 - 8.43 keV
#843463 - 854159

#L3: 7.244 - 7.294
#854160 - 862373

#L2: 7.932 - 7.932 (not complete)
#862374 - 863881
```

In []:

```
In [24]: # function to analyse image data and extract peak info in a dictionary

print_each_n = 100

from IPython.display import display, Javascript
import sys
import pickle
sys.path.append('/dls_sw/apps/scisoftpy/2.7')
sys.path.append('/dls_sw/i16/software/python')
from dlstools import *
from dlstools.pdinx import *
from matplotlib.pyplot import *

from dlstools.quickfit import *
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from time import sleep, asctime

%matplotlib notebook

ci, cj = 242, 95
iw=50; jw=50
lcroi = (int(ci-iw/2.), int(cj-jw/2.), int(ci+iw/2.), int(cj+jw/2.))
iw=13; jw=15
scroi = (int(ci-iw/2.), int(cj-jw/2.), int(ci+iw/2.), int(cj+jw/2.))
scroi_bg = (int(ci-iw/2.), int(cj-jw/2.-16), int(ci+iw/2.), int(cj+jw/2.-16))

def analyse_images(scans, p):

    res_dict = {}
    res_dict['scan'], res_dict['en'], res_dict['area'], res_dict['fwhm_sd'], res_dic

    for scan in scans:
        #figure(99)
        n = pdinx(p % scan)

        if scan == print_each_n * np.floor(scan / print_each_n): # display file name
            print(asctime() + '\t' + p % scan)

        if len(n) == 121: #it's a fine eta scan
```

```

res_dict['scan'] += [scan]
res_dict['en'] += [round(float(n.nx['entry1/sample/beam/incident_energy']
res_dict['psi'] += [float(n.nx['entry1/before_scan/psi/psi'])]]

r = scroi
n['scroi_sum'] = n.nx.entry1.instrument.kthZebraPil3.data[:, r[1]:r[3],

#fig = figure(99); pcolor(np.Log(n.nx.entry1.instrument.kthZebraPil3.dat
#fig.canvas.draw() # update

r = scroi_bg
n['scroi_bg_sum'] = n.nx.entry1.instrument.kthZebraPil3.data[:, r[1]:r[3]
[centre, fwhm_sd, fwhm_area, sum, height, area, m, c] = peak(n.kthZebra,
res_dict['centre'] += [centre]
res_dict['fwhm_sd'] += [fwhm_sd]
res_dict['fwhm_area'] += [fwhm_area]
res_dict['area'] += [area]
return res_dict

```

In []:

In [25]:

```

#function to filter peak data and select lowest area for each energy, removing peaks
# rejecting datasets where smallest area is first or last point

def filter_results(res_dict):
    # filter results in peak dictionary and return spectrum

    figure()
    plot(res_dict['en'], res_dict['area'], '.'); ylim([0, 1000]); title('peak area')

    figure()
    plot(res_dict['en'], res_dict['fwhm_area'], '.'); ylim([0, .02]); title('fwhm_ar

    ens = np.array(res_dict['en'])
    areas = np.array(res_dict['area'])
    width = np.array(res_dict['fwhm_area'])

    goodwidth = (width > 0.005) & (width < 0.0075)

    flags = ens>0 # List of True same size as ens
    enlist, arealist = [], []

    while True in flags:
        enlist += [ens[flags].min()]
        flags = ens> enlist[-1]

    for en in enlist:
        enflags = (ens == en) & goodwidth # each element with that energy and good w
        #print(enflags)
        ifirst, ilast = min(np.argwhere(enflags)), max(np.argwhere(enflags))
        #print(ifirst, ilast)
        en_areas = areas[enflags] # areas for particular energy
        area = min(en_areas)
        if area == en_areas[0] or area == en_areas[-1]: # if first or last then set
            arealist += [-100]
        else:
            arealist += [area]

    print('Frac. goodwith: %.2f' % (len(np.argwhere(goodwidth)) / len(ens)))
    return(enlist, arealist)

```

```

import pickle l3_scans = range(854160, 862373) # full l3 list test_scans = range(854160, 854260) # short test set
#scans = range(854160, 854180) # very short test set #scans = range(854160, 856160) # 20 x short test set
#l3_scans = range(854160, 857000) # L3 but miss out files from 857000 onwards as gaps in detector data
#p='/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs' p='/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs' l3_dict =
analyse_images(l3_scans, p) pickle.dump(l3_dict, open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l3_res_dict.p', "wb" ))
#test_dict = pickle.load( open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l3_res_dict.p' , "rb" )) # load back from pickle
file

```

```

In [26]: l3_dict = pickle.load( open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l3_res_dict.p' , "rb"

(enlist, arealist) = filter_results(l3_dict)

figure()
plot(enlist, arealist, '.g', label = 'Diffraction peak area (arb. scale)')

p = '/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2/%i.nxs'
n = pdnx(p % 823333) # L3 fluo
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
plot(n['DCMenergy'], n['i_norm']/100, '.', color='orange', label = 'Fluorecence (arb
xlim([7.23, 7.33]); ylim([0, 1600])
xlabel('Energy (keV)'); legend()
title('GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L3 edge')

```


Frac. goodwith: 0.81

Out[26]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L3 edge')

```
In [27]: import pickle

l2_scans = range(862374, 863881+1) # full l2 list
```

```
#p='/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'
p='/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'

l2_dict = analyse_images(l2_scans, p)

pickle.dump(l2_dict, open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l2_res_dict.p', "wb" )
```

```
Fri Feb 4 16:52:53 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:53:35 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:54:15 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:54:58 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:55:40 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:56:22 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/862900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:57:03 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:57:46 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:58:28 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:59:11 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 16:59:55 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:00:37 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:01:21 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:02:04 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:02:46 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/863800.nxs
```

In [28]:

```
l2_dict = pickle.load( open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l2_res_dict.p' , "rb"
(enlist, arealist) = filter_results(l2_dict)

figure()
plot(enlist, arealist, 'o')

p='/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2/%i.nxs'
n = pdnx(p % 823332) # L2 fluo
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
plot(n['DCMenergy'], n['i_norm']/100, '.', color='orange', label = 'Fluorecence (arb

plot(enlist, arealist, '.g', label = 'Diffraction peak area (arb. scale)')

xlabel('Energy (keV)'); legend()
title('GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L2 edge')
```


Frac. goodwith: 0.64

Out[28]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L2 edge')

In [29]:

```
import pickle

#l1_scans = range(849362, 854159+1) # full l1 list
l1_scans = range(843463, 854159+1) # full l1 list

#p='/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'
p='/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'

l1_dict = analyse_images(l1_scans, p)

pickle.dump(l1_dict, open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l1_res_dict.p', "wb" )
```

```
Fri Feb 4 17:03:37 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:04:21 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:05:05 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:05:49 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:06:33 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:07:20 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:08:05 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:08:49 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:09:33 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:10:16 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:11:00 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:11:44 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:12:29 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:13:13 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:13:58 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/844900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:14:42 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:15:25 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:16:09 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:16:53 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:17:38 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845400.nxs
```

Fri Feb 4 17:18:23 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:19:07 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:19:52 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:20:36 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:21:22 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/845900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:22:07 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:22:52 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:23:40 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:24:24 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:25:09 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:25:55 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:26:39 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:27:24 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:28:13 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:28:59 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/846900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:29:45 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:30:32 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:31:19 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:32:05 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:32:50 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:33:36 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:34:21 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:35:04 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:35:47 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:36:30 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/847900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:37:13 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:37:59 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:38:44 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:39:29 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:40:16 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:41:01 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:41:48 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:42:31 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:43:16 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:44:01 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/848900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:44:44 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:45:28 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:46:12 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:46:58 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:47:43 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:48:29 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:49:16 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:50:04 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:50:49 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:51:37 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/849900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:52:21 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:53:06 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:53:52 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:54:35 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:55:19 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:56:03 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:56:48 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:57:34 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:58:21 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:59:07 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/850900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 17:59:53 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:00:37 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:01:24 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:02:09 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:02:53 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:03:39 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:04:24 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:05:09 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:05:53 2022	/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851800.nxs

```

Fri Feb 4 18:06:38 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/851900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:07:23 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:08:08 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:08:54 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:09:41 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:10:26 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:11:13 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:11:58 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:12:43 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:13:28 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:14:13 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/852900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:14:57 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:15:41 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853100.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:16:25 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853200.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:17:08 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853300.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:17:52 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853400.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:18:37 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853500.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:19:21 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853600.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:20:05 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853700.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:20:50 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853800.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:21:34 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/853900.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:22:19 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/854000.nxs
Fri Feb 4 18:23:03 2022 /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/854100.nxs

```

In [30]:

```

l1_dict = pickle.load( open('/dls/science/users/spc93/data/ggg_l1_res_dict.p' , "rb"
(enlist, arealist) = filter_results(l1_dict)

figure()
#plot(enlist, arealist, 'o')
plot(enlist, arealist, '.g', label = 'Diffraction peak area (arb. scale)')

p='/dls/i16/data/2020/cm26473-2/%i.nxs'
n = pdnx(p % 823330) # L1 fluo
n['i_norm'] = n['sum']/n.ic1monitor
plot(n['DCMenergy'], n['i_norm']/100 - 2900, '.', color='orange', label = 'Fluorecen
xlim([8.33, 8.43]); ylim([0, 700])
xlabel('Energy (keV)'); legend()
title('GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L1 edge')

```


Frac. goodwith: 0.70

Out[30]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'GGG 006 resonant diffraction Gd L1 edge')

```
In [31]: p='/dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/%i.nxs'
scn, en = [], []
#for scan in range(843459, 843459+10):
for scan in range(843459, 863881+5): # Last ten should be empty?
    scn += [scan]
    try:
        n = pdnx(p % scan)
        en += [n.nx.entry1.sample.beam.incident_energy]
    except:
        en += [0]
```

=== Error loading NeXus file /dls/staging/dls/i16/data/2020/mm25913-2/843459.nxs

```
In [32]: figure()
plot(scn, en, '.')
```


Out[32]: [`<matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f2b7ad70710>`]

In []:

In []: